

Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) studies of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors and activators[†]

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Abstract : Known for decades, the metalloenzymes carbonic anhydrases (CAs, EC 4.2.1.1) are widespread all over the phylogenetic tree. In the last years, it has emerged that in addition to their well-known role for the development of diuretics or anti-glaucoma drugs, inhibitors of these enzymes may lead to novel antiobesity and anticancer therapies. Two mitochondrial CA isoforms are involved in lipogenesis and their inhibition leads to diminished fatty acid biosynthesis. Two Tran membrane, tumour associated isozymes are highly over expressed and involved in signalling/pH regulation processes within hypoxic tumors. Specific inhibitors for both types of such isoforms have been developed and some of their are in clinical evaluations. A review on Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships (QSARs) studies of CA inhibitors is presented. The expectations of QSAR models are initially discussed, followed by model validation, estimation of predictive power of QSAR models, modeling approaches, quality of data and statistical methods used in making QSAR analyses for this class of pharmacological agents. A variety of examples of QSAR studies related to aromatic, heterocyclic and/or aliphatic sulfonamide CA inhibitors are discussed in detail, for various CA isoforms among the 15 presently known in humans, which present interest in designing antioglaucoma, antiobesity or anticancer agents/diagnostic tools. Carbonic anhydrase activators targeting human isoforms I, II, IV, VII and XIV (present among others in the brain) may lead to novel therapies for Alzheimer's disease, memory therapy and aging, since the levels of such isozymes are much diminished in the brain of patients suffering of these diseases.

Keywords : CA inhibitor, CA activity, QSAR, regression analysis, molecular modeling.

1. Introduction

The Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships (QSARs) are mathematical models relating measured

biological activity of series of structurally related chemical compounds/pharmacological agents to the variation in their chemical structure. In cases in which some physico-

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

chemical properties or toxicities of such compounds are related to their structures, the methodology is called quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPRs) or quantitative structure-toxicity relationships (QSTRs), respectively. Such methodologies are widely used in environmental toxicology to understand the adverse effects of chemical compounds. These predictions are important to be done due to the large number of untested chemicals present in nature ultimately, and because of the high costs of biological testing¹⁻¹⁹.

QSAR models are now-a-days regarded as a scientifically credible tool for predicting and classifying biological activities of untested chemicals. QSAR has become inexorably embedded as an essential tool in the pharmaceutical industry, from lead discovery, optimization to lead development and computer-aided drug designing^{20,21}. A growing trend is to use QSAR early in the drug discovery process as a screening and enrichment tool to estimate for further development of those chemicals lacking drug like properties²¹ or those chemicals predicted to elicit a toxic response. The fundamental assumption of QSAR is that variations in the biological activity of a series of chemicals that target a common mechanism of action are correlated with variations in their structural, physical and chemical properties²².

Since presumably these structurally related properties of a chemical can be determined by experimental or computational mean much more efficiently than its biological activity using *in vivo* or *in vitro* approaches, a statistically validated QSAR model is capable of predicting the biological activity of a new chemical within the same series in lieu of the time-consuming and labor-intensive processes of chemical synthesis and biological evaluation. Applied judiciously, QSAR can save substantial amount of time, money, and human resources.

The molecular structure and parameters derived from molecular spectral data of organic compounds acting as drugs can be used as molecular descriptors for modeling biological activity²³. Such data-activity relationship is now-a-days called Quantitative Structure-Data-Activity Relationships (QSDARs) instead of QSAR the reason being QSDARs involved the use of spectroscopic data in establishing structure-activity relationship²⁴. As will be discussed in the following sections the chemical shifts in

NMR or force constant in IR (infra red) spectroscopy offer a powerful probe for the study of the immediate atomic environment in the molecule. The spectral parameters obtained from these molecular spectra are then called molecular descriptors, which then are used in QSDARs. Modern rational drug design, therefore, widely relies on building extensive QSAR/QSPR/QSTR/QSDAR models. The limitations of fundamental physical and chemical laws in direct quantification of biological activity made computational chemists to search for simplified but efficient ways of dealing with the phenomenon, such as by the means of molecular descriptors vis-à-vis graph theoretical invariants. Modern QSAR uses a broad range of atomic and molecular descriptors¹⁹. The empirical descriptors, such as substitution constants originated the field of early QSAR studies.

Hansch is considered as father of QSAR, who for the first time introduced this methodology in 1962²⁵. For the past 50 years, the use of QSAR has become increasingly helpful in understanding chemical and biological interactions in the drug design process, pesticide research, environmental pollution, in the area of toxicology etc. QSAR methodology is very useful in elucidating the mechanism of chemical-biological interactions; in particular enzyme action. In environmental toxicology QSARs are used to understand the adverse effects of chemicals, and to predict the biological effects of yet untested compounds. These predictions are done because of the large number of untested chemicals, and because of the high costs of biological testing. It is worth mentioning that, although sometimes taken as a criterion, prediction is not the primary goal of QSAR. If it results from interpolation, it is often trivial; if extrapolation goes too far outside the included parameter space, it usually fails. QSAR helps to understand structure-activity relationships in a quantitative manner and to find the borders of certain properties, e.g. the optimum lipophilicity within a series of analogs or the maximum size of a certain group in a stepwise procedure. The strategy and philosophy of QSAR enable chemists, pharmacologists and medicinal chemistry to look at their structures in terms of physicochemical properties instead of only considering certain pharmacophore groups in it. Nevertheless, QSAR methods are still used to prove and to quantify the underlying hypothesis regarding the

dependence of biological activities on physicochemical interactions. The predictive power of QSAR critically depends on the statistical quality of the data used to develop the model and estimate its parameters.

Parameters which encode certain structural features and properties are needed to correlate biological activities with chemical structures in a quantitative manner. Physicochemical properties, which are directly related to the extra molecular force involved in the drug-receptor interaction as well as to the transport and distribution properties of drugs, are of special value in developing QSAR model. In this respect hydrophobic, polar, electronic, and steric properties are most important. Now-a-days, graph theoretical descriptors, which are commonly known as topological indices are used in obtaining QSAR models.

The development of a QSAR for a given type of biological activity and a given type of chemical compounds involves the following steps :

- (1) Selecting a "training set" of compounds from an almost infinite universe of possible candidates;
- (2) Synthesizing or otherwise getting hold of pure samples of these compounds;
- (3) Obtaining appropriate biological activity-measurements from the training set compounds. Together these data form the $(n \times M)$ matrix Y , n being the number of training set-compounds, and M being number of biological activity measurements;
- (4) Translating the variation in structure among the training set compounds to the variation of "structure descriptor variables". That is, achieving a relevant quantitative description of the structural variation among the compounds. The resulting data are denoted X_{ik} for compound i , ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) and descriptor variable k ($k = 1, 2, \dots, k$). Together they form the $(n \times K)$ matrix X ;
- (5) Deriving a mathematical model connecting X and Y . This gives, among other results, a measure of how well Y is modeled and which variables in X that are important in the model (i.e. regression coefficients);
- (6) Validating the model by having it predict the biological activity for several new compounds, followed by

the actual biological testing of these compounds and the comparison of predictions with outcomes; and

(7) Interpreting the model by relating it to biological and chemical knowledge.

In general, QSAR methods have four main types. They are :

- A. Variety of docking methods, which models the interaction between proteins and small molecule ligands.
- B. Variety of 3D-QSAR methods, for example the CoMFA approach (Cramer, 1988).
- C. 3D-Database searching by 3D-pharmacophores.
- D. Traditional 2D-QSAR methods (Hansch, 1962) and variety of index descriptors methods.

In four types of QSAR mentioned above, type A, B and C are research main streams, with many successful systems run by large companies. Because our modeling target is the interaction between a single protein molecule and a small organic molecule in 3D space, to directly use the molecular 3D information is reasonable. From a cases review, it seems that the best method is a combination of the docking and the 3D-pharmacophore searching. Usually people use these two tools in turn in development of new drugs. This combination is used by many large companies now.

At this stage it is interesting to mention that the concept of QSAR dates back to the 19th century²⁵⁻²⁷. At that time QSAR was in foreground and prediction played only a minor role. Only a few parameters were used at that time. The chief among these parameter being $\log P$, π , σ , MR and Steric parameters. Latter in the beginning of 20th century a quantitative prediction was made. That is, QSARs began to explain structure-activity relationships by a quantitative manner. For that rules and conditions have been formulated to achieve valid correlations in that statistical methodology was applied. Now, quantitative prediction is made using quantum chemical, geometrical, connectivity values, electro-topology, WHIM (Weighed Holistic Invariant method) molecular descriptor and many other distance-based and connectivity type topological indices. Based on the origin of molecular descriptors used in calculations, QSAR methods can be divided into three

groups as shown below :

2. Model validation : Estimation of predictive power of QSAR models

It has been observed that the more independent variables are involved in MLR (Multiple Linear Regression) QSAR analysis, the higher is the probability of a chance correlation between predicted and observed activities²⁸⁻³⁰. This conclusion is true not only for MLR-QSAR, but also for any QSAR approach when the number of variables (descriptors) is comparable to or higher than the number of compounds in data set. Consequently, model validation is one of the most important aspects of QSAR analysis. The best way to validate a model is to perform cross-validation which is based on leave-one-out (LOO) or leave-some-out (LSO) cross-validation procedures²⁸⁻³⁰. The outcome from this procedure is the cross-validated parameters : PRESS (Predicted Residual Sum of Squares), SSY (Sum of the Squares of the response values), S_{press} (Uncertainty of Prediction), R^2_{CV} (or Q^2) (Overall Predictive ability) and PSE (Predictive Square Error). Frequently, R^2_{CV} (or Q^2) is used as a criterion of

both robustness and predictive ability of the model. Many authors consider high Q^2 (for instance, $Q^2 > 0.5$) as an indicator or even as the ultimate proof of the high predictive power of the QSAR model³¹⁻³⁵. They do not test the models for their ability to predict the activity of compounds of an external test set (i.e. compounds which have not been used in the QSAR model development). Other authors validate their models using only one or more compounds that were not used in QSAR model development, and still claim that their models are highly predictive. In contrast with such expectations, it has been shown that if a test set with known values of biological activities is available for prediction, there exists no correlation between LOO cross-validated Q^2 and correlation coefficient R^2 between the predicted and observed activities for the test set^{36,37}.

Another widely used approach to establish the model robustness is called y-randomization (randomization of response i.e. activities)^{36,37}. It consists of repeating the calculation procedure with randomized activities and subsequent probability assessment of the resultant statistics. Frequently, it is used along with cross-validation. It is expected that models obtained for the data set with randomized activity should have low values of Q^2 . However, sometimes models based on the randomized data have high Q^2 values due to chance correlation or structural redundancy³⁵⁻³⁷.

Some authors have suggested that the only way to estimate the true predictive power of a QSAR model is to compare the predicted and observed activities of sufficiently large external test set of compounds that were not used in the model development³⁵⁻³⁷.

To estimate predictive power of a QSAR model one needs the following statistical characteristics of the test model :

(1) Correlation coefficient R between the predicted and observed activities;

(2) Coefficient of determination i.e. predicted versus observed activities (R^2_{obs}) and observed versus predicted activities (R^2_{cal});

(3) Slopes k and k' of the regression lines through the origin. A QSAR model is predictive, if the following conditions are satisfied⁴⁵.

$$Q^2 > 0.5, \quad (1)$$

$$k^2 > 0.6, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{R^2 - R^2_0}{R^2} < 0.1 \quad (3)$$

$$0.85 \leq k \leq 1.15$$

(4) 5. Statistical methods

3. QSAR modeling

The QSAR modeling generally involves three steps :

(1) Collect or, if possible, design a training set of chemicals;

(2) Choose descriptors that can properly relate chemical structure to biological activities; and

(3) Apply statistical methods that correlate changes in structure with changes in biological activity.

Obtaining a good quality QSAR model with the ability to predict activity of a chemical outside the training set depends upon many factors in the approach and execution of each of the three steps mentioned above.

4. Quality of data

Data should come from the same assay protocol, and care should be taken to avoid inter-laboratory variability. Any bad data points will tend to corrupt the proper correlation of structure and activity. A technique that has been most used in QSAR is linear multiple regression which employs the least square method to find the equation of the "best-fit" of biological activity with a given combination of parameters (molecular descriptors). The limitations and some common pit falls of the multiple regression analysis were pointed by Tute^{38,39} : there must be a sufficient number of compounds included in the analysis to enable statistical significance to be reached, despite inexcusable errors in measurements 'A rule of thumb' was involved, that at least five data points (compounds) should be included for every parameter (molecular descriptor) in the equation. The parameters themselves should be well "spread" and one must avoid the peculiar danger of including one extreme value of any parameter, as a "best-fit" will inevitably pass through the extreme point. Rules of thumb^{38,39} for a good QSAR data set are that the dose-response relationship should be smooth, the potency (or affinity) should be reproducible, the activity range should span two or more orders of magnitude from the least active to most active chemicals in the series, the number of chemicals used to build the QSAR model should be sufficiently large to ensure statistical stability, the activities of the chemicals should be evenly distributed across the range of activity, and the chemicals selected for the training set should possess enough structural diversity to span the range of chemical space associated with the biological activity under study.

It is also critical that the QSAR method selected to develop the structure-activity correlation be suitable. Although the relationship between the molecular descriptor and biological activity may be linear or non-linear, it is still common practice today to deploy linear approaches such as multiple (or multivariate) linear regression (MLR) or partial least squares (P) regression to construct the QSAR model⁴⁰. For non-linear modeling, the Polynomial Neural Network (PNN) offers an alternative that combines the best features of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and MLR/PLS by providing the inherent non-linearity of the ANN with the desired analytical regression equation furnished by MLR and PLS⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. Several statistical approaches that are commonly used in QSAR modeling are reported in the literature⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. However, below we give the details of PRECLAV program which provides a set of PRECLAV descriptors and help in making detailed regression analysis.

6. Details of PRECLAV (Property Evaluation by Class Variables) Computer Program

The PRECLAV (Property Evaluation by Class Variables) computer program is used for the first time for modeling CA inhibition as well as activation. The program utilizes only "significant" descriptors in calculating the QSAR equations (proposing statistically significant models) descriptors that fulfill criteria (5).

$$r^2 > 4/N \quad (5)$$

where :

r^2 is the square of the Pearson linear correlation between the values of the analyzed descriptor and the values of the dependent property,

N is the number of molecules in the calibration set (here N = 21).

The program combines successively sets with 2, 3, k significant descriptors ($1 < k < 11$). A set of descriptors contains only descriptors that are sufficiently low intercorrelated and fulfill criteria (2).

$$r_{ij}^2 < N^{-1/2} \quad (6)$$

where :

r_{ij}^2 is the square of Pearson linear correlation between the values of two descriptors present in the same set.

Each set of descriptors has been used to calculate a multilinker QSAR equation of type (3).

$$IC = c_0 + \sum_{i=2}^k c_i \cdot D_i \quad (7)$$

where :

IC is the dependent property (inhibition constant),

c_0 is the free term (intercept),

c_i are the coefficients (weighting factors) of the descriptors,

D_i is some significant descriptors and

k is the number of descriptors in the set.

The c_i coefficients have been calculated with OLSM (Ordinary Least Square Method). Tens of thousands of equations of type (3) have been calculated. With each of the type (3) equation, the values of IC have also been calculated. These computed values have been compared with the observed values. The concordance between the calculated/observed values has been calculated using the quality function Q .

$$Q = K_{CV} \cdot (N - k)/N \quad (8)$$

where :

K_{CV} is Kendall cross-validated rank correlation between computed/observed values.

As the value of k increases, the quality Q of the equations increases, reaches a maximum, then decreases. For the prediction, the equation with the highest value of Q is used and the descriptors used in this equation are called "predictors".

For every predictor, the "utility" U has been calculated.

$$U = (R^2 - r^2)/(1 - r^2) \quad (9)$$

where :

R^2 is the square of the Pearson linear correlation between the observed values of IC and the values calculated with the equation containing k predictors and

R^2 is the square of the Pearson linear correlation between the observed values of IC and the values calculated with the equation containing $k-1$ predictors, that is without the analyzed descriptor.

The values of U are then normalized (the highest becoming 1000). The "useful" predictors ($U > 400$) are sufficiently well correlated with IC and not too well correlated with the other predictors.

Every "useful" predictor describes (reasonably) well the variation in the values of IC, and, at the same time, describes a different aspect than the other predictors. The

molecules are constructed using the molecular mechanics program, PCMODEL. The geometry of the minimum energy conformer is obtained by using the MMX force field and GMMX algorithms. The geometry is more rigorously optimized with the quantum mechanics program MOPAC. The output files created by MOPAC for each analyzed molecule are input files for PRECLAV program and they contain the values of some descriptors. Using the data from the files generated by MOPAC, PRECLAV computes most of the descriptors and performs the statistical analysis. In PRECLAV program the QSAR studies can be made with or without a testing set. In the case of QSAR studies with a testing set PRECLAV program uses the Class function for identifying the significant descriptors.

The "significant" descriptors satisfy the conditions (10) and (11) as given below :

$$C_v > 3 \quad (10)$$

$$Q > 1 \quad (11)$$

where C_v is the coefficient of variation for descriptor values and is defined by the following expression :

$$C_v = 100 \times d/V_m \quad (12)$$

where d is the standard deviation around the average value is the average absolute value and Q is the quality function for the analyzed descriptor and is given by the following expression :

$$Q = r^2/1 - C^a (1 - b \times r_{\min}^2) \quad (13)$$

where r^2 is the square of the Pearson linear correlation between the descriptor values and the dependent property values, r_{\min}^2 is the minimum value imposed for r^2 ; the default value of r_{\min}^2 , empirically established is $4/N$ (where N is the number of molecules from the training set); and C is Class function :

$$C = d_N/d_{N+k}, \text{ if } d_N < d_{N+k} \quad (14)$$

$$C = d_{N+k}/d_N, \text{ if } d_N \geq d_{N+k} \quad (15)$$

where d_N is d from formula (14) computed for from the training set, d_{N+k} is d from formula (15) computed for the entire database (N molecules from the training set + K molecules from the testing set).

It is considered that Class function measures how representative a sample, from the Statistical point of view is the training set in the joint set of the testing and training sets from the analyzed descriptor's point of view. If the testing set is missing then $C = 1$ for all descriptors and the condition (14) becomes $r^2 > b \times r_{\min}^2$.

The analyses of the training set molecules produce

tens of thousands of multi-linear QSAR equations (models) of the following form :

$$\text{Activity (or Property)} = c_0 + \sum c_k p_{K_a} \quad (16)$$

The “best” QSAR equation (model) is then selected according to the value of a cross-validation quality function, specific to PRECLAV. The aforementioned equation is then utilized for predicting the values of activity (or property) for the molecules in the training set. Once the computations were over, the testing set molecules are classified in three categories : “recommended for synthesis”, “uncertain”, and “un-recommended for synthesis”

The descriptors used in PRECLAV program are given in Appendix 1.

7. QSAR of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors

Before discussing QSAR of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors it is necessary to give a brief account on this versatile enzyme and its carbonic anhydrase inhibitors.

7.1. Carbonic anhydrase an ubiquitous enzyme

Carbonic anhydrases (CAs, EC 4.2.1.1) are widespread enzymes, present in mammals in at least 15 different isoforms. The 12 catalytically active isoforms play important physiological and pathophysiological functions and are strongly inhibited by aromatic/heterocyclic sul-

fonamides, sulfamides and sulfamates, among others. The catalytic and inhibition mechanisms of these enzymes are understood in great detail, and this greatly helped the design of potent inhibitors, some of which possess important clinical applications as antiglaucoma drugs, or in the management of some neuromuscular disorders. A recent discovery is connected with the involvement of CAs and their sulfonamide inhibitors in cancer : many potent CA inhibitors were shown to inhibit the growth of several tumour cell lines *in vitro* and *in vivo*, thus constituting interesting leads for developing novel antitumour therapies. The field of quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR), formalised by Hansch and others in the early 1960s, is the discovery of empirical relationships between the chemical structure of drugs and their biological activity. The emphasis is an empirical. Extending a QSAR to drugs other than those used to formulate it is always a new hypothesis, and although these extensions are often successful, it should be no cause for surprise if they break down in particular cases. With CA, as with other targets, the descriptor variables that have been used include topological indices, physical properties such as solvent partition coefficients and Hammett constants from reaction rate studies, and quantum theoretical parameters, such as orbital energies, atomic charges, polarisabilities etc.

Table 1. Higher vertebrate CA isozymes, their relative CO₂ hydrase activity, affinity for sulfonamide inhibitors and subcellular localization

Isozyme	Catalytic activity (CO ₂ hydration)		Affinity
for sulfonamides	subcellular localization		
CA I	Low	Medium	
Cytosolic CA II	High	Very high	Cytosolic
Cytosolic CA III	Very low		
CA IV	High	High	Plasma membrane
CA V	Moderate to high*	High	Mitochondria
CA VI	Moderate	Medium-low	Secreted into saliva
CA VII	High	Very high	Cytosolic
CARP VIII	Acatalytic	‡	Cytosol
CA IX	High	High	Plasma membrane
CARP X	Acatalytic	‡	Cytosol
CARP XI	Acatalytic	‡	Cytosol
CA XII	High	High	Plasma membrane
CA XIII	Low	High	Cytosol
CA XIV	Medium	High	Plasma membrane

*Moderate at pH 7.4, high at ≥ pH 8.2; ‡the native CARP isozymes do not contain Zn^{II}, so that their affinity for the sulfonamide inhibitors has not been measured. By site-directed mutagenesis it is possible to modify these proteins and transform them in enzymes with CA-like activity, which probably are inhibited by sulfonamides, but no studies on this subject are available at present; CA : Carbonic anhydrase; CARP : CA-related protein.

In higher vertebrates, including humans, 14 different CA isozymes or CA-related proteins were described (Table 1), with very different subcellular localizations and tissue distributions. Among the active enzymes, there are several cytosolic forms (CA I-III, VII and XIII), four membrane-bound isozymes (CA IV, IX, XII and XIV), mitochondrial form (CA V), as well as a secreted CA isozyme (CA VI). As discussed in this review, many of these isozymes are important targets for the design of inhibitors with clinical applications.

In addition to the physiological reaction, that is, the reversible hydration of CO₂ to bicarbonate, CAs catalyse a variety of other reactions, such as : the hydration of cyanate to carbamic acid, or of cyanamide to urea; the aldehyde hydration to *gem*-diols; and the hydrolysis of carboxylic, or sulfonic esters, as well as other less investigated hydrolytic processes. It should be mentioned that the previously reported phosphatase activity of CA III was recently proved to be an artifact. It is unclear at this moment whether other CA catalysed reactions than the CO₂ hydration has physiological significance.

Extensive work on inhibition of the zinc enzyme carbonic anhydrase (CA, EC 4.2.1.1) has been done in recent years, as this family of enzymes (15 isoforms known up to now in humans) emerged as interesting drug targets for designing many types of pharmacological agents. Carbonic anhydrases occupy a special place among the metallo-enzymes extensively studied in the last decade. These enzymes are ubiquitous in all kingdoms starting with *Archaea*, *Bacteria*, Algae and Green plants, and ending with superior animals, including vertebrates⁴⁵, and are encoded by five distinct, evolutionarily unrelated gene families : the α -CAs (present in vertebrates), the β -CAs (mainly present in *Bacteria* and plants), the γ -CAs (mainly present in *Archaea*), and the recently isolated δ - and ϵ -classes of CAs (present in marine diatoms and chemo litho-autotrophic bacteria, respectively).

The catalytic activity of carbonic anhydrase, the hydration of carbon dioxide to bicarbonate and a proton and their physiological function is essential for all the aforementioned organisms, as the CA-catalyzed reaction is fundamental in physiology, whereas the three chemical entities participating in it is ubiquitous, abundant and chemically critical in a multitude of processes. Thus, this

reaction is fundamental for respiration and transport of CO₂ between metabolizing tissues and excretion sites, secretion of electrolytes in a variety of tissues and organs, pH regulation and homeostasis, CO₂ fixation (for algae and green plants), several metabolic biosynthetic pathways, such as gluconeogenesis, lip genesis, and urea genesis, bone resorption, calcification, tumorigenicity (in vertebrate). In higher vertebrates, including humans, 15 different CA isozymes or CA-related proteins (CARP) were described so far, with very different subcellular localization and tissue distribution. Among the active enzymes, there are several cytosolic forms (CA I-III), CA VII, CA XIII), four membrane-bound isozymes (CA IV, CA IX, CA XII and CA XIV), a mitochondrial form (CA V), as well as a secreted CA isozyme (CA VI). Many of these isozymes are important targets for the design of inhibitors with clinical applications, and indeed, recently Supuran *et al.* described compounds with interesting applications as antiglaucoma, antiobesity, or antitumor agents among others.

7.2. CA inhibitors

Inhibitors (but also activators) of CAs may be exploited clinically in the treatment or prevention of a variety of disorders. In consequence, CA inhibitors (CAIs) and to a less extent up to now, CA activators (CAs) possess a variety of applications in therapy. Due to their important role, inhibitors of these enzymes may be exploited for the design of therapeutic agents useful in the management and prevention of many diseases. Sulfonamides represent an important class of biologically active compounds. With the sulfonamide as the common features, different classes of pharmacological agents have been obtained such as antibacterial sulfonamides, sulfonamides that inhibit the zinc enzyme carbonic anhydrase, the hypoglycemic sulfonamides extensively used in the treatment of some forms of diabetes, antithyroid drugs, and others.

A great number of sulfonamide derivatives were synthesized, characterized, tested, and are widely used in clinical medicine as pharmacological agents with a wide variety of biological actions. More specifically, sulfonamide inhibitors of CA are extensively used in clinical medicine and as diagnostic tools, their main applications being in the treatment of glaucoma, macular edema, epi-

lepsy, and other neurological disorders. CA inhibition with sulfonamides discovered by Mann and Keilin⁴⁶ has led to important drugs such as the sulfonamides with CA inhibitory properties. Several such drugs are presently available, such as recently introduced topical sulfonamides dorzolamide and brinzolamide, in addition to the classical, systematically acting inhibitors acetazolamide, methazolamide, ethoxzolamide, and dichlorophenamide which have been employed clinically for more than 45 years.

A large number of aromatic heterocyclic and more recently aliphatic sulfonamides have been synthesized and tested for their CA inhibitors properties⁴⁷. Sulfonamides CAIs derived from simple aromatic or heterocyclic sulfonamides have already shown excellent CA inhibitory properties against many CA isozymes isolated so far in diverse organisms. Many derivatives belonging to the heterocyclic and aromatic classes of sulfonamides have been synthesized and investigated for their biological activity. The aromatic/heterocyclic sulfonamides act as carbonic anhydrase inhibitors and other types of derivatives show diuretic activity, hypoglycemic activity, anticancer properties or may act as inhibition of the aspartic HIV protease being used for the treatment of AIDs and HIV infection among others⁵⁸. In view of the aforementioned discussion we will review QSAR of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors in three different categories :

- (1) QSAR related to aromatic (particularly benzene) sulfonamides;
- (2) QSAR related to heterocyclic sulfonamides; and
- (3) QSAR related to aliphatic sulfonamides.

7.3. QSAR related to aromatic sulfonamides

During the last few years, Supuran and co-workers have extensively studied different aromatic sulfonamides as potent carbonic anhydrase inhibitor. Those aromatic sulfonamides were proved to be strong inhibitors with low K_i values within the nanomolar range. Special attention was paid to aromatic sulfonamides substituted at the *para*-position as they exhibit higher affinity with the zinc enzyme compound to an *ortho*-substituted aromatic sulfonamide. This may be due to the steric impairment of the *ortho*-substituent for the binding of such compound to the Zn^{II} ion within the enzyme active site.

Due to the biological importance of sulfonamides as potent CAIs, QSAR models have been proposed for the prediction of CA inhibitory activity of aromatic sulfonamides using different molecular descriptors. This is also the case with heterocyclic as well as aliphatic sulfonamides. Maren, Balaban, Clare, Supuran, Khadikar, Sarimveis, Jurs, Gupta, Gao, Basak *etc.* are working on QSAR of CAIs. Balaban-Supuran-Khadikar⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹ has done extensive QSAR studies using distance-based and connectivity indices. Recently they have done very interesting study using Balaban and Balaban type indices. In addition, Khadikar group has successfully used NMR^{50,51} and IR parameters⁵² for QSAR study. Clare's⁵³⁻⁶² main interest is to use chiefly quantum chemical descriptors for such QSAR study. Other workers have more or less used Hansch approach in their QSAR study. It appears that the first review on such study is reported by Maren *et al.*⁶³ in that they have covered some interesting QSAR related to aromatic sulfonamides, heterocyclic sulfonamides and aliphatic sulfonamides and have also discussed the need of molecular factors to modulate structure-activity-relations. Since, this review was published in 1994 only results reported up to 1994 were included in this review. Recently in 2003 Gupta⁶⁴ has published a review covering some of the results reported on QSAR of the three types of sulfonamides mentioned above. Unfortunately, this review of Gupta is not comprehensive and deleted many interesting cases.

7.3.1. Studies on aromatic sulfonamides

Study of structure-activity correlations in this class of drugs are quite simple, and as stressed by Maren⁵⁹, may be "*the criteria for activity in this class are the simplest in pharmacology*". Indeed, all unsubstantiated sulfonamides of the type RSO_2NH_2 , where, R is an aromatic moiety show inhibitory properties towards this enzyme.

Sulfonamides bind in the ionized form of RSO_2NH_2 to the Zn^{II} ion within the CA active site, as the fourth ligand, substituting the zinc(II) – bound water molecules⁶⁵, perturbing in this way the whole catalytic cycle⁶⁶. Taking into account the clinical importance of these agents *per se*, and also the fact that they constituted the starting point for obtaining classes of widely used pharmacological agents, such as the thiazide diuretics, the high ceiling

diuretic and certain antithyroid compounds⁶⁷. We will first discuss the cases in that PRECLAV program is used in the inhibition studies on aromatic sulfonamides.

7.3.2. Use of PRECLAV program in QSAR studies on carbonic anhydrase (hCAI isozyme) by the sulfonamides containing a picolinoyl group

Recently Tarko Laszlo reported QSAR studies on carbonic anhydrase by the sulfonamides containing a picolinoyl group using PRECLAV program in that two QSAR studies in which the dependent property is the inhibitor activity over carbonic anhydrase (hCAI isozyme) of 21 sulfonamides containing picolinoyl group (Table 1) were discussed. All statistical calculations were performed using PRECLAV program. In the first QSAR study, only the specific predictors of PRECLAV have been used. The correlation between the observed values and the calculated values of activity is good ($s = 0.3431$, $r^2 = 0.9135$, $F = 63.4$, $r^2_{CV} = 0.8588$). In the second QSAR study both specific descriptors of PRECLAV and descriptors calculated using the DRAGON program were used. The correlation between the observed values and the calculated values of activity is very good ($s = 0.2199$, $r^2 = 0.9645$, $F = 162.8$, $r^2_{CV} = 0.9393$). The QSAR equations obtained point to the fact that the inhibitor activity decreases, if a high percentage of hydrogen in the molecule is present and is favored by the presence of alkyl groups, a high internal topological diversity, and condensed aromatic rings.

The virtual construction of the molecules and the geometry optimization has been done using the molecular mechanics software PCModel. The next step performed was the rigorous optimization of the geometry using the Mopac software for quantum mechanics calculations using the key-words string "am1 pulay gnorm=0.01 shift=50 geo-ok camp-king mmok bonds vectors". The output file from Mopac was used as input file for PRECLAV program. Using these data, PRECLAV calculated for each molecule the values for almost 400 whole molecule descriptors, specific for the program in question. No "grid" descriptors were used. Separately, for each molecule, the values for another 1400 descriptors, specific to this program have been calculated, using the DRAGON program. The statistic calculations, including the QSAR equations, have been performed using the PRECLAV program. The program has used only "sig-

nificant" descriptors in calculating the QSAR equations.

The results of applying the PRECLAV algorithm in the two QSAR studies were found as below. The quality of the equations was determined not only by the value of function Q , but also by the values of some usual statistical functions.

(a) QSAR study #1

Descriptors used : specific descriptors of the PRECLAV program

Number of significant descriptors : 130

QSAR of type (3) used for prediction :

$$c_0 = -12.0954$$

$$c_1 = 9.2180$$

D_1 is Percent of hydrogen-Minimum net charge of H atoms product ($U = 1000$)

$$c_2 = 1.0845$$

D_2 is $E_{LUMO+1} - E_{HOMO}$ gap ($U = 759$)

$$c_3 = 4.6031$$

D_3 is Spherical shape index 13 ($U = 756$)

Standard error s : 0.3431

Pearson square correlation r^2 : 0.9135

Fisher function F : 63.4

Pearson cross-validated square correlation r^2_{CV} : 0.8558

Kendall rank correlation K : 0.9143

Kendall cross-validated rank correlation K_{CV} : 0.8667

Quality Q : 0.7429

Number of outliers : 0

The lowest correlation with IC was computed for predictor D_3 ($r^2 = 0.2496$). The highest inter-correlation between predictors was computed for the pair D_1 , D_2 ($r^2 = 0.0195$).

The predictor with the highest usability for describing the values of IC is in this case D_1 . The value of IC is directly proportional with the value of D_1 . The study of the files provided by Mopac shows the fact that a low value for the "Minimum net charge of H atoms" is determined by the presence of the alkyl groups in the molecule. On the other hand, in the molecules presented above, high percentage of hydrogen is exhibited by the ones with low molecular mass, a low degree of substitution of the aromatic rings and/or without condensed cycles. The

Table 2. Structural details 21 sulfonamides used in PRECLAV program

fact that in QSAR #1 the product D_1 is a predictor can be interpreted as “the favorable effect on inhibitory activity of the presence of alkyl groups is diminished by a high percentage of hydrogen” or that “the favorable effect of the presence of alkyl groups is accentuated by a low percentage of hydrogen”.

(b) QSAR study #2

Descriptors used : descriptors of PRECLAV program and descriptors calculated with DRAGON program

Number of significant descriptors : 404

QSAR of type (3) used for prediction :

$$c_0 = 18.7491$$

$$c_1 = -17.9328$$

D_1 is Structural Information Content (neighborhood symmetry of 1-order) 14

$$(U = 1000)$$

$$c_2 = -1.9352$$

D_2 is R-CR-X atom-centered fragment 15 (U = 965)

$$c_3 = -1.1106$$

D_3 is R autocorrelation of lag5 weighted by atomic Sanderson electro negativities 16, 17 (U = 481)

Standard error s : 0.2199

Pearson square correlation r^2 : 0.9645

Fisher function F : 162.8

Pearson cross-validated square correlation r^2_{CV} : 0.9393

Kendall rank correlation K : 0.8857

Kendall cross-validated rank correlation K_{CV} : 0.8762

Quality Q : 0.7510

Number of outliers : 0

It was observed that in QSAR #2 no PRECLAV descriptors are present. Here, the lowest correlation with IC was computed for predictor D_3 ($r^2 = 0.2014$). The highest inter-correlation between predictors was computed for the pair D_1, D_3 ($r^2 = 0.2480$). The most useful predictors for describing IC are in this case D_1 and D_2 . The value of IC is inversely proportional with the values of D_1 and D_2 . Considering the physical significance of predictor D_1 we conclude that a high topological diversity of the molecular graph, from the point of view of the edge multiplicity and the vertex degree is favorable to the inhibitory activity. The presence of the D_2 predictor indicates the existence of condensed aromatic rings. We can conclude that this structural feature is favorable to the inhibitory activity.

The table given below records the observed and calculated values (rounded to three decimal points) of the inhibition constant IC.

The QSAR studies of the inhibitory activity over carbonic anhydrase (hCAI isozyme) using 21 sulfonamides

with picolinyl group using PRECLAV program lead to the following conclusions :

(i) The DRAGON descriptors seem to be more useful than the PRECLAV descriptors.

(ii) The inhibitory activity is disfavored by a high percentage of hydrogen in the molecule.

(iii) The inhibitory activity is favored by the presence of the alkyl groups, a high internal topological diversity and the presence of condensed aromatic rings.

Table 3. Observed and computed values of inhibition constant

Sulfonamide	IC _{observed}	IC _{computed}	
		by QSAR #1	by QSAR #2
i	4.35	4.313	4.189
ii	4.33	4.643	4.006
iii	4.29	3.758	4.132
iv	4.17	3.588	4.060
v	3.32	3.447	3.534
vi	3.31	3.420	3.220
vii	3.20	3.187	3.009
viii	3.04	2.985	3.412
ix	3.04	2.960	3.258
x	2.79	2.740	2.841
xi	2.78	3.047	2.814
xii	2.78	2.633	2.891
xiii	2.78	2.920	3.051
xiv	2.72	2.916	2.796
xv	2.17	2.365	2.494
xvi	1.60	1.776	1.786
xvii	1.49	1.326	1.106
xviii	1.30	1.771	1.402
xix	1.04	1.569	0.995
xx	1.00	1.324	1.234
xxi	1.00	0.350	0.811

7.3.3. First QSARs study on the inhibition of the tranmembrane XIV with sulfonamides using PRECLAV software

Very recently Singh, Khadikar and Supuran have reported first QSAR study on the inhibition of the tranmembrane XIV with sulfonamides using PRECLAV software.

Here the dependent property is the inhibitor activity over carbonic anhydrase (hCA XIV isozyme) of a series of sulfonamides including some clinically used derivatives actazolamide, methazolamide, ethoxzolamide,

dichlorophenamide, dorzolamide, brinzolamide, benzolamide, and zonisamide. Once again, all statistical calculations were done using PRECLAV program. The specific predictors of PRECLAV have been used. The correlation between the observed values and the calculated values of activity was good ($s = 0.2416$, $r^2 = 0.9259$, $F = 75.0196$, $r^2_{CV} = 0.8985$). The results obtained using specific descriptors of PRECLAV are compared with those in that descriptors calculated using the HYPER CHEM program are used. The QSAR equations obtained point to the fact that the inhibitor activity decreases, if a high percentage of hydrogen in the molecule is present and is favored by the presence of alkyl groups, a high internal topological diversity, and condensed aromatic rings.

It is worthy to mention that out of the 15 isoforms, the isozyme hCA XIV was the last to be discovered by Nishimori's group. It has been observed that hCA XIV is highly abundant in the brain, kidney, urinary bladder, liver etc. We have previously investigated the inhibition of most of the known human CAs except hCA XIV. It has been shown that these CAs are inhibited by sulfonamides and other types of inhibitors. Also, that these CA isozymes are druggable targets, and that their inhibitors may have applications in the design of glaucoma, antitumor, anticonvulsant or antiobesity therapies among others.

Recently one of the author (Supuran) for the first time reported inhibition of the transmembrane isozyme XIV with sulfonamides. However, till date no QSAR study is made on this important class of isozyme. This is the first report on such QSARs studies. Also, that here for the first time we have used PRECLAV as well as HyperChem parameters for obtaining statistically significant models. A comparison of the results obtained in both the cases indicated that excellent results are obtained using PRECLAV parameters.

In the set of 1-30 (Table 4) sulfonamides/sulfamates investigated for the inhibition of hCA XIV the compounds 22-30 as clinically used drugs, compounds 1-4, 9, 10, 16, 21-27, 29 and 3 are commercially available from Sigma-Aldrich, Merce, Alcon, Johan & Johan or DaiNippon, whereas compounds 5-8, 11-15, 20 and 28 were synthesized by one of the authors (Supuran). Singh,

Table 4. Structural details of sulfonamides/sulfamates used in the present study

Khadikar and Supuran performed their QSAR studies without an external validation set. The two QSAR studies used two different sets of descriptors. The dependent property was the inhibition constant = $\log K_i$ (hCA XIV), where K_i is the concentration of inhibitor where the in-

hibitory effect on hCA XIV isozyme starts. The values for K_i (nM) were converted into their log units (Table 5) were used in the computation, have been taken from literature²⁷. Table 6 records the list of best quality thirty descriptors for 30 compounds.

Table 5. The activities of the CA inhibitors (log hCA XIV) used in the present study

Compd.	log hCA XIV	Compd.	log hCA XIV
1	3.8129	2	3.6812
3	3.7323	4	3.5051
5	2.2552	6	1.3222
7	1.1760	8	1.8976
9	2.8325	10	2.7558
11	2.3851	12	1.1139
13	1.6812	14	3.5843
15	3.5125	16	2.8920
17	3.1613	18	3.4623
19	2.4471	20	1.8808
21	1.9493	22	1.6127
23	1.6334	24	1.3979
25	2.3891	26	1.4313
27	1.3802	28	1.5185
29	3.1643	30	3.7201

Table 6. List of best quality thirty descriptors for 30 compounds

Descriptor	r ²	Class ¹⁰	Quality
nrs	0.3817	1	2.8633
mas	0.3194	1	2.3958
vlm	0.2462	1	1.8472
sun	0.3265	1	2.4490
isv	0.2965	1	2.2240
adg	0.2514	1	1.8861
rms	0.2588	1	1.9414
mob	0.2492	1	1.8694
moc	0.2698	1	2.0238
igu	0.248	1	1.8601
igd	0.2517	1	1.8882
mot	0.2785	1	2.0894
ray	0.4007	1	3.0060
raz	0.5166	1	3.8755
zgg	0.2868	1	2.1515
nsc	0.2482	1	1.8619
ass	0.305	1	2.2878
nss	0.3606	1	2.7051
hia	0.466	1	3.4960
snu	0.3909	1	2.9321
qgf	0.3732	1	2.8000
lha	0.409	1	3.0681
lhb	0.2585	1	1.9389
lhc	0.2619	1	1.9645
lhe	0.4164	1	3.1241
lhf	0.2671	1	2.0040

Table-6 (contd.)

lhg	0.3055	1	2.2917
lhh	0.2398	1	1.7990
vel	0.2625	1	1.9696
hbb	0.2448	1	1.8368

Activity variation coefficient = 36.9%

I retain 97 significant

Descriptors (Quality > 1).

Statistical analysis parameters :

Molecules number of learning

set : 30

Molecules number of testing

set : 0

Final equation descriptors number : v < 7

descriptors/activity

correlation : r² > 0.1333

intercorrelation in > 2 descriptors sets : r² < 0.64

Applying the PRECLAV algorithm the results obtained by Singh, Khadikar and Supuran for the set of 30 compounds in their QSAR studies are presented below :

Table 7. Molecules of analyzed database include 33 virtual fragments for the entire set of 30 compounds :

The mass percents of 3 fragments are significant.

THE MOST SIGNIFICANT VIRTUAL FRAGMENTS by square correlation of 'the mass percent of fragment' and 'Property values' are

Fragment atoms	Specimen	Correlation sign	Square
H ₂ N	ZM1.out	1	0.3545
C ₆ H ₄	ZM4.out	1	0.1887
C ₂ HN ₃ S	ZM12.out	-1	0.1618

Correlation sign 1 means 'large mass percent of this fragment increase the Property value'.

Correlation sign -1 means 'large mass percent of this fragment decrease the Property value'.

Table 8. Best set (by r²) of 2 descriptors : raz and snu

s	= 0.4912
r ²	= 0.7127
F	= 34.7215
r ² CV	= 0.6734
rKCV	= 0.6184
quality	= 0.5772
max. quality	= 0.5986

Table 7 indicates that 'large mass percent of H₂N and C₆H₄ fragments increase the inhibition activity while large

Table 9. Best set (by r^2) of 3 descriptors : spm, mot, and snu

s	=	0.4353
r^2	=	0.7743
F	=	30.882
r^2CV	=	0.732
rKCV	=	0.6552
quality	=	0.5897
max. quality	=	0.6062

Percent of carbon

lhb : 634 $r^2 = 0.2585$ (+)

$E_{(LUMO)} - E_{(HOMO-1)}$ gap

pon : 463 $r^2 = 0.2298$ (-)

RMS of distances to geometric center (H and halogen atoms)

The analysis of this model indicated occurrence of tow outliers, the delegation of which yielded better results for the remaining set of 28 compounds.

Table 10. Best set (by r^2) of 4 descriptors : pca/ray/qgf/lhb/for the set of 30 compounds

s	0.4012
r^2	0.8083
F	27.4115
r^2CV	0.7600
rKCV	0.6184
quality	0.5359
max. quality	0.6062

Best set by quality

predictors/Activity correlation :

Max. lhb 0.2585

Min. pca 0.1839

predictors intercorrelation :

Max. pon/lhb 0.3159

Min. pca/pon 0.0815

predictors weighting factors of the best QSPR formula :

0.0662/-0.7852/0.8713/

... and C_0 coefficient (Intercept)...

mass percent of C_2HN_3S fragment decrease the inhibition activity. Also, that 4-descriptor model containing pca, ray, qgf, and lhb is the best model for modeling the inhibitory activity (Table 10). Using this model Singh, Khadikar and Supuran have estimated the activity which yielded the results given in the following Table 11.

Table 11

s	=	0.4775
r^2	=	0.7472
F	=	26.5993
r Kendall	=	0.7149
r^2CV	=	0.6965
rKCV	=	0.6736
quality	=	0.6062

Relative influence (+/-) of predictors on Activity within 0-1000 range :

pca : 1000 $r^2 = 0.1839$

The following Table 12 records list of best quality thirty descriptors for 28 compounds.

Using the information contained in Table 12 and ap-

Table 12. Estimated and observed activity for the thirty descriptors 28 compounds

	Estimated	Observed
ZM18	3.383	3.462
ZM4	3.229	3.505
ZM15	3.364	3.513
ZM14	3.389	3.584
ZM2	3.570	3.681
ZM30	2.916	3.720
ZM3	3.427	3.732
ZM12	0.854	1.114
ZM7	2.413	1.176
ZM6	2.802	1.322
ZM27	1.470	1.380
ZM24	1.267	1.398
ZM26	1.329	1.431
ZM28	1.651	1.519
ZM22	1.549	1.613
ZM23	1.508	1.636
ZM13	1.598	1.681
ZM20	2.253	1.881
ZM8	2.131	1.898
ZM21	2.170	1.949
ZM5	2.957	2.255
ZM11	2.260	2.385
ZM25	2.035	2.389
ZM19	2.162	2.447
ZM10	2.293	2.752
ZM9	2.572	2.833
ZM16	3.047	2.892
ZM17	2.889	3.161
ZM29	3.222	3.164
ZM1	3.576	3.813

Table 13. List of best quality thirty descriptors for 28 compounds

Descriptor	r ²	Class ¹⁰	Quality
nrs	0.5875	1	4.1114
mas	0.3992	1	2.7936
sun	0.4401	1	3.0795
xdg	0.3835	1	2.6836
adg	0.4132	1	2.8917
rms	0.3994	1	2.7952
mob	0.3411	1	2.3869
moc	0.3636	1	2.5446
igu	0.3453	1	2.4161
igd	0.3736	1	2.6144
mot	0.3732	1	2.6114
ray	0.4798	1	3.3574
raz	0.5842	1	4.088
pon	0.3764	1	2.6337
pla	0.3252	1	2.2756
zag	0.3363	1	2.3533
zgg	0.3729	1	2.6097
ass	0.4548	1	3.1828
nss	0.5299	1	3.7079
hia	0.4953	1	3.4664
snu	0.4755	1	3.3278
qgf	0.3604	1	2.5223
fel	0.3905	1	2.7329
lha	0.4652	1	3.2555
lhb	0.3216	1	2.2509
lhe	0.4822	1	3.3743
lhf	0.3373	1	2.3607
lhg	0.3447	1	2.4124
vel	0.3741	1	2.6182
xvs	0.3237	1	2.2655

plying the PRECLAV algorithm the results obtained by Singh, Khadikar and Supuran in their QSAR studies for the set of 28 compounds are presented below :

(1) Two variable model containing raz and nss as the correlating parameters

$c_0 = 4.6814$
 $c_1 = -1.6277$
 $D_1 = \text{raz}$, is Gyration radius Z of molecular area (U = 1000)
 $c_2 = 0.4543$
 $D_2 = \text{nss}$, is minim net charge of S atom (U = 965)
 Standard error $s = 0.3162$

Pearson square correlation $r^2 = 0.873$

Fisher function $F = 89.4955$

Pearson cross-validated square correlation $r^2_{CV} = 0.846$

Kendall cross-validated rank correlation $rKCV = 0.7513$

Quality $Q = 0.6977$

max. quality = 0.6977

Best set (by r²) of 3 descriptors containing pca, pon, lhb, as the correlating parameters

$c_0 = -6.2596$

$c_1 = 0.0642$

$D_1 = \text{pca}$, is Percent of carbon

(U = 1000)

$c_2 = 0.7902$

$D_2 = \text{pon}$, is RMS of distance to geometric center (H and Halogenations)

$c_3 = -1.0173$

$D_3 = \text{lhb}$, is $E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO-1}$ gap

Standard error $s = 0.267$

Pearson square correlation $r^2 = 0.9096$

Fisher function $F = 83.8137$

Pearson cross-validated square correlation $r^2_{CV} = 0.8891$

Kendall cross-validated rank correlation $rKCV = 0.836$

Quality $Q = 0.7464$

max. quality = 0.7559

(2) Best set (by r²) of 4 descriptors pca, ray, pon, and lhf containing, as the correlating parameters

$c_0 = 8.7924$

$c_1 = 0.0583$

$D_1 = \text{pca}$, is Percent of carbon

(U = 1000)

$c_2 = -64.7685$

$D_2 = \text{ray}$, is Gyration radius Y of molecular area

(U = 1000)

$c_3 = -0.4487$

$D_3 = \text{pon}$, is RMS of distance to geometric center (H and Halogenations) (U = 965)

$c_4 = -0.7438$

$D_4 = \text{lhf}$, is $1/E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO-1}$ ratio

Standard error $s = 0.2416$

Pearson square correlation $r^2 = 0.9259$

Fisher function $F = 75.0196$

Pearson cross-validated square correlation $r^2_{CV} = 0.8985$

Kendall cross-validated rank correlation $rKCV = 0.8095$

Quality $Q = 0.6939$

max. quality = 0.7559

Singh, Khadikar and Supuran observed that four variable model containing *pca*, *ray*, *pon*, and *lhf* as the correlating PRECLAV parameters is the most appropriate model for modeling log hCA XIV. This model is found as below :

$$\log \text{hCA XIV} = 8.7924 + 0.0583 (\pm 0.) \text{pca} - 64.7685 ((\pm 0.) \text{ray} - 0.4487 ((\pm 0.) \text{pun} - 0.7438 () \text{lhf}$$

$$n = 28, s = 0.2416, r^2 = 0.9259, F = 75.0196$$

The positive coefficient of *pca* indicates that increase in percent of carbon is favorable for the exhibition of log hCA XIV, while negative coefficients of *ray*, *pon*, and *lhf* indicate that decrease in Gyration radius *Y* of molecular area, RMS of distance to geometric center (H and Halogenations) and $1/E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO-1}$ ratio respectively are favorable for modeling the activity log hCA XIV. Using model expressed by eq. (13) Singh, Khadikar and Supuran estimated the activities. The results are given in Table 13.

Table 14. Estimated and observed values for 28 compounds

	Estimated	Observed
ZM12	0.941	1.114
ZM27	1.454	1.380
ZM24	1.210	1.398
ZM26	1.399	1.431
ZM28	1.705	1.519
ZM22	1.561	1.613
ZM23	1.575	1.633
ZM13	1.772	1.681
ZM20	2.069	1.881
ZM8	2.360	1.898
ZM21	2.183	1.949
ZM5	3.151	2.255
ZM11	2.282	2.389
ZM25	2.229	2.389
ZM19	2.476	2.447
ZM10	2.523	2.756
ZM9	2.708	2.833

Table-14 (contd.)

ZM16	3.163	2.892
ZM17	3.014	3.161
ZM29	3.199	3.164
ZM18	3.482	3.462
ZM4	3.343	3.505
ZM15	3.445	3.513
ZM14	3.521	3.584
ZM2	3.707	3.681
ZM30	3.046	3.72
ZM3	3.563	3.732
ZM1	3.714	3.813

$s = 0.2799$

$r^2 = 0.908$

$F = 82.2279$

$r \text{ Kendall} = 0.8677$

$r^2_{CV} = 0.887$

$rKCV = 0.8466$

quality = 0.7559

Relative influence (+/-) of predictors on Property within 0-1000 range :

pca : 1000 $r^2 = 0.1786 (+)$

Percent of carbon

pon : 813 $r^2 = 0.3763 (-)$

RMS of distances to geometric center (H and halogen atoms)

lhf : 757 $r^2 = 0.3382 (-)$

$1/E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO-1}$ ratio

This model doesn't have any outlier.

The data presented in Table 13 gave the following correlation between estimated and observed log hCA XIV :

(log hCA XIV) estimated = constant + c (log hCA XIV) observed

$s = 0.2799, r^2 = 0.908, F = 82.2279, r \text{ Kendall} = 0.8677, r^2_{CV} = 0.887, rKCV = 0.8466, \text{quality} = 0.7559$

The information given in the following Table 14 indicates that large mass percent of H_2N and C_6H_4 fragments increase the activity value, while large mass percent of C_3HN_3S and NH fragments decrease the activity value.

Table 15. The most significant virtual fragments for 28 compounds

Molecules of analyzed database include 32 virtual fragments

The mass percents of 4 fragments are significant

THE MOST SIGNIFICANT VIRTUAL FRAGMENTS by square

Correlation of 'the mass percent of fragment' and 'Property values' are

Correlation	Fragment atoms	Specimen
H ₂ N	ZM1.out	1
C ₂ HN ₃ S	ZM12.out	-1
C ₆ H ₄	ZM4.out	1
HN	ZM20.out	-1

Correlation sign 1 means 'large mass percent of this fragment increase the Property value'.

For arriving at the final conclusion Singh, Khadikar and Supuran have examined the aforementioned 2-, 3- and 4-descriptors models with regard to co-linearity problem. The models will be acceptable only when they are free from co-linearity defect. This can be made by investigating VIF (Variance Inflation Factor), Tolerance, Eigen-values and condition number for each of the descriptors present in a given model. These parameters are calculated using Ridge regression and are presented in Table 16.

Application of Ridge statistics provides important statistical parameters namely variance inflation factors (VIFs) for each of the parameters involved in the model. The VIF is defined for each variable in the equation and not for the equation as a whole, so there should be as many VIFs, as there are correlating parameters. The VIF is defined as :

$$VIF = 1/(1 - R_i^2) \quad (17)$$

where R_i is the multiple correlation coefficient of the i-th independent variable on all of the other independent variables. In the proposed models, all these VIFs should be less than 10 indicating that no co-linearity problem exists in the model.

A perusal of Table 16 shows that in all the three proposed models the descriptors evolved in them have VIF considerably smaller than 10 indicating that the models are free from the defect due to co-linearity.

The Ridge regression analysis also provides λ-statistics helping us to resolve the problem of co-linearity. The

λ-statistics is defined as below :

$$\lambda = 1/n \sum_{i=1} 1/\lambda_i \quad (18)$$

where n is the number of variables in the model (regression expression) and λ_i is the Eigen-values of the correlation matrix of the independent variables.

If λ < 5.0, the sub-set is considered free from co-linearity problem, and the equation (Model) is accepted. If λ is not < 5.0, then Eigen-vector matrix is examined. The Eigen-values presented in Table 16 confirm the above findings that the models are free from co-linearity problem.

Table 16. VIF, tolerance, Eigen-values and condition number for the proposed models for 28 compounds

Model used	Parameters	VIF	Tolerance	Eigen-values	Condition number
1	raz	1.0792	0.9266	1.270948	1.00
	nss	1.0792	0.9266	0.729052	1.74
2	pca	1.1242	0.8895	1.782087	1.00
	pon	1.5270	0.6549	0.784001	2.27
	lhb	1.4900	0.6711	0.433912	4.11
3	pca	1.2661	0.7899	2.198055	1.00
	ray	1.5204	0.6577	1.052973	2.09
	pon	2.2152	0.4514	0.516898	4.25
	lbf	2.6466	0.3778	0.232074	9.47

Singh, Khadikar and Supuran then discussed the modeling of log hCA XIV using quantum and chemical descriptors (Table 17). Table 17 summarizes statistically significant models indicating that the maximum quantum and chemical descriptors that can be used for modeling log hCA XIV is seven.

Table 17. Quantum and chemical descriptors used in the present study

MPC	Most positive charges
LNC	Least negative charges
MNC	Most negative charges
SPC	Sum of positive charges
SNC	Sum of negative charges
SAC	Sum of absolute charges
SSC	Sum of squares of charges
Kcal/mol	Highest occupied molecular orbital energy

Table-17 (contd.) descriptor model is given below :

Kcal/mol	Lowest unoccupied molecular orbital energy	$\log \text{hCA XIV} = -4.4337 + 0.0935 (\pm 0.0208) \lambda$
Kcal/mol	Electronegativity ($\chi = -0.5 (E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}})$)	$-0.0753 (\pm 0.0273) \text{DM}_y$
Kcal/mol	Hardness ($\eta = 0.5 (E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_{\text{LUMO}})$)	$-0.0082 (\pm 0.0017) \text{SA}$
Mol/Kcal	Softness ($S = 1/\eta$)	$-0.0050(0.0016) \text{H}_f$ (19)
(A ³)Kcal/mol	Electrophilicity ($\omega = \chi^2/2\eta$) Pol	$n = 30, s = 0.2323, r^2 = 0.6694, F = 12.657$
Debyes	Total molecular Dipole moment DM_l	A careful examination of this model indicated that it contains two outliers (compounds 6 and 8). Deletion of these compounds from the process of regression yielded a model with improved statistics :
Debyes	Molecular dipole moment at x-direction DM_x	$\log \text{hCA XIV} = -4.1311 + 0.0935 (\pm 0.0179) \lambda$
Debyes	Molecular dipole moment at y-direction DM_y	$-0.0688 (\pm 0.0235) \text{DM}_y$
Debyes	Molecular dipole moment at z-direction DM_z	$-0.0088 (\pm 0.0015) \text{SA}$
Kcal/mol	Heat of formation H_f	$-0.0051 (0.0014) \text{H}_f$ (20)
(A ²)	Surface area SA	$n = 28, s = 0.1948, r^2 = 0.7181, F = 22.765$
(A ³)	Volume V	The VIF, Eigen-values, tolerance and condition number recorded in the following Tables 19 and 20 show that
(A ³)	Ref : refractivity Ref	
(A ³)	Polarizability Pol	
log P	The log of Octanol-water partition coefficient	
Kcal/mol	Hydration energy HE	

Table 18. Statically significant models for modeling log K₁hCA (XIV) for 28 compounds

Model	Parameters number used	R ²	R ² A	S	F
1.	Ref	0.3727	0.3503	0.3024	16.637
2.	Pol, Pol	0.7778	0.4412	0.2804	12.450
3.	Pol, Pol, DM_y	0.5515	0.4998	0.2653	10.600
4.	SA, H_f , χ , DM_y	0.6694	0.0166	0.2322	12.672
5.	SA, H_f , χ , DM_y , V	0.7040	0.6423	0.224	11.416
6.	Ref, SA, H_f , χ , DM_y , V	0.7357	0.6608	0.2165	10.672
7.	Ref, SA, H_f , χ , DM_y , V, DM_x	0.7524	0.6736	0.2143	9.549

A perusal of Table 18 indicates that 7-descriptor model is the best for modeling the activity. The quality of this 7-descriptor model is much inferior to the 4-descriptor model using PRECLAV descriptors. However, even the 7-descriptor model is free from defect due to co-linearity. Further examination of these models (Table 17) indicated that 5-, 6- and 7-descriptor models contain one or two correlating descriptors in that their standard deviations were much larger than the respective coefficients. Such models are not allowed statistically and need not to be considered. So, we are left with the 4-descriptor model whose quality is also very much more compared to the 4-descriptor model using PRECLAV descriptors. This 4-

Table 19. VIF values for the proposed models for modeling log K₁hCA (XIV) for 28 compounds

Independent variable	Variance inflation factor	R-Squared vs other X's	Tolerance
SA	1.4386	0.3049	0.6951
H_f	1.2195	0.1800	0.8200
χ	1.1691	0.1446	0.8554
DM_y	1.2854	0.2220	0.7780

Since all VIF's are less than 10, multicollinearity is not a problem.

model expressed by eq. (18) is free from defect due to co-linearity.

It is clear, therefore, that in the present case the

Table 20. Eigen-values of the best models for modeling log K_{1hCA} (XIV) for 28 compounds

Independent variable	Eigen-value	Incremental	Cumulative percent	Condition number
SA	1.825503	45.64	45.64	1.00
H _f	1.034973	25.87	71.51	1.76
χ	0.659038	16.48	87.99	2.77
DM _y	0.480486	12.01	100.00	3.8

All condition numbers less than 100. Multico-linearity is not a problem.

PRECLAV descriptors are far superior descriptors compare to the quantum and chemical descriptors for modeling log hCA XIV. This is further confirmed the data presented in Tables 17 and 18.

The following conclusions were drawn by Singh, Khadikar and Supuran :

(a) The PRECLAV descriptors are more useful descriptors,

(b) The inhibitory activity is disfavored by C₃HN₃S and NH fragments,

(c) The inhibitory activity is favored by H₂N and C₆H₄ fragments.

7.3.4. QSAR studies for the inhibition of the trans-membrane isozymes XII and XIV of human carbonic anhydrase with a series of sulfonamides

Tarko and Supuran used a diverse series of aromatic/heterocyclic sulfonamides possessing inhibitory action against the human transmembrane isoforms XII (cancer-associated) and XIV of the metalloenzyme carbonic anhydrase (CA, EC 4.2.1.1) to develop QSAR models using PRECLAV program. Including all the 55 investigated sulfonamides in the calibration set, the predictive qualities of the QSAR equations were weak ($r^2 = 0.1771$, $F = 5.70$) for CA XII and good for CA XIV inhibition ($r^2 = 0.8222$, $F = 57.04$ before eliminating the outliers, and $r^2 = 0.8911$, $F = 67.07$ after eliminating them). The obtained models suggest a slightly different inhibition mechanism for the two isoforms. 3-Halogeno-4-aminobenzenesulfonamides were outliers for cajoled hopping for the inhibition of CA XIV. CA XIV inhibitory activity was proportional to the degree of molecular surface rugosity. For compounds of the type X-Ar-SO₂NH₂ and Ar⁰-Ar-SO₂NH₂ type, best inhibitors were detected when Ar/Ar⁰ incorporates a heterocyclic moiety. These studies may be helpful for the design of more specific CA XII/

XIV inhibitors, since this is the first QSAR model investigating them. They had applied the PRECLAV algorithm in three QSAR studies by using the set of CA XII/XIV inhibitors 1-55. The quality of the obtained equations is rejected by the value of the Q function and also by values of some usual statistical functions 2.1.

QSAR study #1

Dependent property : CA inhibitory activity against hCA XII (Table 1, column 4)

Number of molecules in the calibration set : 55

Number of significant descriptors : 7

Type (1) QSAR used for prediction :

$c_0 = 2.8945$

$c_1 = 0.9392$

D₁ is the complementary information content-neighborhood symmetry²¹ of 3-order

$c_2 = 12.371$

D₂ is the average valence connectivity index²² v^5

Standard error of values s value : 0.6370

Standard error of ranks s rank : 16.9411

Pearson square correlation r^2 : 0.1771

Fisher function F : 5.70

Pearson cross-validated square correlation r^2_{CV} : 0.1088

Kendall rank correlation K : 0.2970

Kendall cross-validated rank correlation KCV : 0.2310

Quality Q : 0.2226

Number of outliers : 2

The values of almost 1800 descriptors were calculated, but the number of descriptors identified as significant was quite low. The predictive quality of QSAR #1 equation was rather weak. This may be due to the fact that the calibration set is rather non-homogeneous, including many types of aromatic/heterocyclic sulfonamides, possessing an inhibition mechanism which may be slightly different between them (see discussion later in the text). In addition, the Pearson, Spearman, and Kendall correlations between the inhibitory activity against isozyme XII and isozyme XIV are very low (for 49 molecules $r^2 = 0.1574$, $q^2 = 0.1932$, and $s^2 = 0.1157$). This also suggests that many molecules from Table 1 inhibit the two isozymes by diverse mechanisms. A scatter-plot of this QSAR model is shown in Fig. 1.2.2.

QSAR study #2

Dependent property : Inhibitory activity against hCA XIV (Table 1, column 5)

Number of molecules in calibration set : 49

Number of significant descriptors : 264

Type (1) QSAR used for prediction :

$$c_0 = 1.0387$$

$$c_1 = 1.7577$$

D_1 is R autocorrelation of lag 3 weighted by atomic masses^{23,24}

$$c_2 = 0.7655$$

D_2 is M (Moran) autocorrelation of lag 5 weighted by atomic Sanderson electronegativities²⁵

$$c_3 = 0.0301$$

D_3 is variation coincident of distances to geometric center computed for H and halogen atoms

$$c_4 = 1.3187$$

D_4 is 100 \pm average Fukui electrophilic reaction index for N atoms

Standard error of values s value : 0.3600

Standard error of ranks s rank : 5.4199

Pearson square correlation r^2 : 0.8222

Fisher function F : 52.04

Pearson cross-validated square correlation r^2CV : 0.7770

Kendall rank correlation K : 0.7738

Kendall cross-validated rank correlation KCV : 0.7602

Quality Q : 0.6981

Number of outliers : 3

The lowest correlation with activity A was computed for predictor D_4 ($r^2 = 0.0854$). The highest Intercorrelation between predictors was computed for the pair D_3, D_4 ($r_2 = 0.1386$). The predictive quality of QSAR #2 is good. The outlier sulfonamides in the group of inhibitors shown in Table 1 are 8, 18, and 23. Probably 18 and 23 are outliers due to 2.3.

QSAR study #3

$$c_0 = 1.6753$$

$$c_1 = 1.7750$$

D_1 is R autocorrelation of lag 3 weighted by atomic masses^{23,24} ($U = 1000$)

$$c_2 = 0.7240$$

D_2 is 100 \pm maximum Fukui electrophilic reaction

index for N atoms ($U = 610$)

$$c_3 = 0.7974$$

D_3 is M (Moran) autocorrelation of lag 5 weighted by atomic Sanderson electronegativities²⁵ ($U = 439$)

$$c_4 = 0.0343$$

D_4 is variation coincident of distances to geometric center computed for H and halogen atoms ($U = 816$)

$$c_5 = 9.0602$$

D_5 is mean topological charge index of order 5²⁸

($U = 227$)

Standard error of values s value : 0.2827

Standard error of ranks s rank : 3.6818

Pearson square correlation r^2 : 0.8911

Fisher function F : 67.07

Pearson cross-validated square correlation r^2CV : 0.8567

Kendall rank correlation K : 0.8454

Kendall cross-validated rank correlation KCV : 0.8242

Quality Q : 0.7346

Number of outliers : 0

The lowest correlation with activity A was computed for predictor D_5 ($r_2 = 0.1316$). The highest Intercorrelation between predictors was computed for the pair D_3, D_5 ($r_2 = 0.2826$). The predictive quality of QSAR #3 is good and the number of outliers is 0. However, molecule 9 is a border limit outlier by applying the used criteria.

7.3.5. Substituted benzene sulfonamides

The first CA inhibitors QSAR studies reported⁶³ included substituted benzene sulfonamides of types (I)

In this QSAR modeling the Hansch-Fujita^{68,69} method was used for correlating biological activity with physico-chemical parameters of electronic nature. Kakeya *et al.*^{70,71} used a series of 19 derivatives of (I) which contained 3-*ortho* substituted derivatives for modeling $\log(1/K_I)$. In doing so, they have deleted the *ortho*-substituted derivatives of (I). The remaining set of compounds consists of *meta*-, *para*- and 3,4-disubstituted compounds. They arrived at the conclusion that Hammett's σ factors are linearly correlated with $\log 1/K_I$ (K_I being inhibition constant). The model obtained is given below :

$$\log(1/K_I) = 1.021 \sigma + 0.474 \quad (22)$$

$$N = 16, Se = 0.208, R = 0.938$$

Thus, one can see that σ is a parameter of greatest importance. The above eq. (22) indicates that an electron withdrawing constituent R is favorable for increased inhibitory properties towards CA for the sulfonamides of the type I.

In their further QSAR modeling Kakeya *et al.*⁷² observed that the quality of model expressed by eq. (22) is increased by the addition of hydrophobic parameter :

$$\log (1/K_I) = 0.800\sigma + 0.276\pi + 0.413 \quad (23)$$

$$N = 16, Se = 0.16, R = 0.965$$

Observe that by addition of π , there is significant increase in R and significant lowering of Se. In the above eq. (23) the coefficients of both σ and π are positive indicating that increase in their magnitude is favorable for the exhibition of $\log (1/K_I)$.

The results can be more precisely discussed by calculating Pogliani's quality factor Q. This parameter is defined in the literature⁷³⁻⁷⁵ as the ratio of correlation coefficient (R) to that of standard error of estimation (Se) i.e. $Q = R/Se$. This quality factor (Q) is considered to express the predictive power of the model. By the definition Q, we observe that increase in R, decrease in Se results into increase in Q, and thus increase in the predictive power of the proposed model. In the present case Q for the model expressed by eq. (22) is 4.51 and that for the model expressed by eq. (23) is 6.03, thus indicating that the latter model is superior to that of the former model.

7.3.6. Benzene sulfonamides of the type (II)

Hansch and co-workers⁶⁸ have performed yet another QSAR study using benzene sulfonamides of the type II. The interesting part of this study being the use of larger number of *ortho*-substituted benzene sulfonamides of the type (I). In addition to the parameters σ and $\log P$, this group has used two supplementary indicator parameters I_1 and I_2 , the first indicator parameter relates to *meta*-substituted compound (I) and the second corresponds to *ortho*-substituted compounds (I). As is well-known these indicator parameters assume only two values (unity when a particular type of group is present and 0 (zero) in the absence of that particular group. Using these parameters the binding constant (K_i in H^{-1}) of sulfonamides (I) to human CA II was modeled. Instead of K_I , $\log K$ was used to express the biological activity of these drugs (I). The model obtained by Hansch⁶⁸ is mentioned below :

$$\log K = 1.55\sigma + 0.64 \log P - 2.07 I_1 - 3.28 I_2 + 6.94 \quad (24)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.204, R = 0.991$$

From the above eq. (24) we observe that *ortho*-substituted benzene sulfonamides (I) have 2000 times' lower affinity for CA II, as compared to the corresponding *para*-substituted congeners. Once again, we observe the importance of the electronic and hydrophobic effects of the substituent in controlling the binding of (I) to the enzyme i.e. CA II.

From the model expressed by eq. (24) we observe that the coefficients of both σ and $\log P$ are positive while that of I_1 and I_2 are negative. This means that electron withdrawing substituents and $\log P$ are favorable for the exhibition of $\log K$, while the presence of *meta*- and *ortho*-substituents is not favorable for the exhibition of $\log K$.

7.3.7. Disulfonamides

Kishida and Manabe⁷⁶ reported QSAR study on disulfonamides of the type (II) :

(II)

In proposing their QSAR model, Kishida and Manabe⁷⁶ used Hansch-Fujita method⁶⁹. The set of 21 disulfonamides used had diuretic property also. Multiple regression analysis was performed, assuming that each of the substituting groups R_1 - R_3 possesses a different role in the enzyme-inhibitory interaction. The conclusion of these calculations was that the different groups R_1 - R_3 do not change significantly the electronic state of the SO_2NH_2 moieties. Thus, Kishida and Manabe⁷⁶ used only the hydrophobic constituent constants π_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) and proposed the following model for modeling $\log IC_{50}$.

$$\log IC_{50} = -0.5674 + 0.2125 \pi_1 + 2.1814 \pi_2 - 2.8731 (\pi_3 - 0.6193)^2 \quad (25)$$

$$N = 19, Se = \text{not reported}, R = 0.9486$$

Eq. (25) suggests that R_1 and R_2 generally influence in a positive manner the affinity of the inhibitor CA, R_3 displays a parabolic and negative influence, probably due to the steric hindrance of the SO_2NH_2 group, which cannot coordinate so easily within the active cavity, once the inhibitor is bound there.

7.3.8. Benzene sulfonamides of the type (III)

De-Benedetti⁷⁷ modeled the binding energy to CA for a series of 20 benzene sulfonamides of the type (III) :

(III)

In proposing their model De-Benedetti's group⁷⁷ used AMBER program 78. The geometric and conformation of the ionized sulfonamide (ArSO_2NH^-) were optimized by the AM_1 method using AMPAC program⁷⁹. They observed that drug binding to enzyme induced an insignificant conformational change of the polypeptide backbone but the sulfonamides experience an induced fit by binding, generally involving rotation by $40\text{--}90^\circ$ of the aromatic rings. The most important fact revealed by their study was that the spread in computed binding energies (BE) is mostly due to the van der Waals term (E_{vdw}).

Before proposing their QSAR model, De-Benedetti's⁷⁷ has calculated a series of MO indices : the total net charges on the amide group (q_{NH^-}), the total net charge on the two oxygen atoms of the SO_2 moiety; the total net charge of the SO_2NH^- group ($q_{\text{SO}_2\text{NH}^-}$) and the energy of the frontier orbital, E_{HOMO} . The best-equations obtained by them are found as below :

$$\log \pi_{50} = -0.159 \text{ BE} - 5.43 \quad (26)$$

$$N = 16, \text{ Se} = 0.17, R = 0.93$$

$$\log \pi_{50} = -0.142 E_{\text{vdw}} - 2.95 \quad (27)$$

$$N = 16, \text{ Se} = 0.15, R = 0.95$$

Here, $\log \pi_{50}$ represent the logarithm of the inhibition indices (how many times a sulfonamide is more active than sulfanilamide).

The most important conclusion of this valuable study⁷⁷ is that CA discrimination towards its inhibitors is dominated by short range van der Waals forces rather than by electrostatic interactions, although it is the ionized sulfonamide that binds to the zinc(II) ions.

7.3.9. Carotti *et al.* QSAR models

Carotti *et al.*⁸⁰ also used the benzene sulfonamides of the type (I) considering a larger set than that used by De-Benedetti⁷⁷. This group mainly consists of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzene sulfonamides of the type (III). In proposing their QSAR model Carotti⁸⁰ separated their compounds in two groups : *meta*- and *para*-substituted compounds. For the *para*-substituted derivative the following model was proposed :

$$\log 1/K_1 = 0.63 \pi + 0.96 \sigma + 5.94 \quad (28)$$

$$N = 18, \text{ Se} = 0.303, R = 0.927$$

In case of *meta*-substituted derivatives the following model was found most suitable for modeling $\log 1/K_1$:

$$\log 1/K_1 = 1.19 \sigma + 0.37 \pi - 0.18 B_{5,3} + 5.85 \quad (29)$$

$$N = 14, \text{ Se} = 0.199, R = 0.925$$

Here $B_{5,3}$ is the sterimol parameter⁸¹ For the combined set, the following model was proposed :

$$\log 1/K_1 = 0.95 \pi + 0.54 \pi - 0.35 B_{3,5} + 6.29 \quad (30)$$

$$N = 31, \text{ Se} = 0.294, R = 0.914$$

This eq. (30) was used to predict the activity of a new congener, 3- NO_2 -4- OC_6H_{13} . When this was synthesized, it was found to be the most active member of the series, and was adequately predicted by eq. (30).

7.3.10. Testa and Purcell QSAR model

Testa and Purcell⁸² used the method of Hansch⁶⁹, more precisely data of King and Burgen⁸³ in that they have also added a few thiophene analogues and proposed the following QSAR model :

$$\log K = 0.26 (\pm 0.14) \log P + 0.6226 (\pm 0.0226) V_s + 1.08 (\pm 0.04) D \quad (31)$$

$$N = 34, \text{ Se} = 0.54, R = 0.997$$

It was concluded that the affinity constant of the sulphonamides used for CA inhibition is structural dependent and depends only to a very limited extent on partition properties. Also, that electronic character of the substituents has no role in obtaining statistically significant model. In the above eq. (31) V_s is the molar volume of the substituents calculated using Bondi's procedure⁸⁴. D is the distance in Angstroms between the S atom in the sulfonamide and the first carbon atom falling into one of the four possible sectors of the enzyme.

7.3.11. Use of frontier electron density

Shinagawa and Shinagawa⁸⁵ modeled the CA I activity using frontier electron density of the lowest vacant orbital and the amide group position ($f_{\text{NH}_2}^{\text{N}}$). For that they have used Krebs data⁸⁶ and Huckel method for quantum mechanical calculation. The model is found below :

$$\log (1/IC_{50}) = 3.13 + 5.51 f_{\text{NH}_2}^{\text{N}} \quad (32)$$

$$N = 22, \text{ Se} = \text{not reported}, R = 0.774$$

This shows that CA I activity is linearly proportional to $f_{\text{NH}_2}^{\text{N}}$. For smaller group thiazides similar results were

obtained :

$$\log (1/IC_{50}) = 1.69 + 8.62 r_{NH_2}^N \quad (33)$$

N = 6, Se = not reported, R = 0.875

However, slightly better results are obtained using formal charge at the amide group position (Q_{NH_2}) :

$$\log (1/IC_{50}) = -1.32 + 11.2 Q_{NH_2} \quad (34)$$

N = 22, Se = not reported, R = 0.780

$$\log (1/IC_{50}) = -8.13 + 19.8 Q_{NH_2} \quad (35)$$

N = 6, Se = not reported, R = 0.885

It was assumed by Shinagawa and Shinagawa⁸⁵ that the NH_2 group is probably involved in hydrogen bonding with the OH^- ion on one side and the imidazole ring on the other side in the enzyme. An oxygen atom of the SO_2 in the sulfonamide moiety is supposed to bind with the Zn^{II} of the enzyme.

7.3.12. Another QSAR study on benzene sulfonamide of the type (III)

Vedani and Meyer⁸⁷ performed a computer graphic study on the benzene sulfonamides of the type (III). Their purpose was to investigate the mode of binding of these compounds to CA II. Their study showed that these benzene sulfonamide (III) bind with CA II through the formation of hydrogen bonds between *meta*- or *para*-substituents and some hydrogen bond donor site in the active site of the enzyme.

7.3.13. QSAR study on *para*-substituted aromatic sulfonamides as carbonic anhydrase II inhibitors using topological information indices

Melagraki *et al.*⁸⁸ made QSAR study on *para*-substituted aromatic sulfonamides as carbonic anhydrase II inhibitors using topological information indices. They observed that a series of *para*-substituted aromatic sulfonamide and their topological indices are correlated linearly with the inhibitory activity of CA II. Very good results were obtained using multi-parametric regressions. These results further showed that the topological information indices are quite useful for modeling CA II inhibition. Among the proposed models, the best multiparametric models given below were found statistically significant.

(1) Best bi-parametric model

$$\log K_1 = 0.96 (\pm 0.40) \chi + 0.6852 (\pm 0.15) N_{ring} - 4.57 \quad (36)$$

N = 47, R = 0.8149, $R^2 = 0.6642$, $R^2_A = 0.6489$, RMS = 0.2926, F = 43.52

(2) Best tri-parametric model

$$\log K_1 = 0.93 (\pm 0.39) \chi + 0.56 (\pm 0.51) {}^0\chi - 0.79 (\pm 0.17) N_{ring} - 5.79 \quad (37)$$

N = 47, R = 0.8356, $R^2 = 0.6984$, $R^2_A = 0.6773$, RMS = 0.2773, F = 33.18

(3) Best tetra-parametric model

$$\log K_1 = 0.94 (\pm 0.37) \chi - 1.00 (\pm 0.64) {}^0\chi^v - 0.71 (\pm 0.65) {}^v\chi^v - 0.85 (\pm 0.17) N_{ring} - 4.98 \quad (38)$$

N = 47, R = 0.8534, $R^2 = 0.7283$, $R^2_A = 0.7024$, RMS = 0.2832, F = 28.14

(4) Best penta-parametric model

$$\log K_1 = 0.71 (\pm 0.67) {}^0\chi - 0.30 (\pm 0.37) \chi - 0.90 (\pm 0.41) {}^0\chi^v - 1.01 (\pm 0.65) {}^v\chi^v - 0.87 (\pm 0.21) N_{ring} - 5.49 \quad (39)$$

N = 47, R = 0.8541, $R^2 = 0.7296$, $R^2_A = 0.6966$, RMS = 0.2625, F = 22.12

7.3.14. New QSAR procedure for quantum-theoretical QSAR for some carbonic anhydrase inhibitors with diverse aromatic rings

Clare and Supuran⁵³ have proposed a new QSAR procedure for quantum theoretical QSAR for some carbonic anhydrase inhibitors with diverse aromatic rings. Their QSAR study is based almost entirely on quantum theoretical descriptors calculated for a large and heterogeneous group of aromatic and heteroaromatic carbonic anhydrase inhibitors. They have used orbital energy, nodal angles, atomic charges and some other intuitively appealing descriptors. Most calculations were done at the B3LYP/6-314* level of theory. In this study, Clare and Supuran⁸⁵ claimed that for the first time they have treated five-member rings by the same means that they have used for benzene rings in the past. The flip regression techniques used by them has been expanded to encompass automatic variable selection. The statistical quality of their results was not equal to those which they have used for benzene derivatives, but is very good considering the non co-generic nature of the compounds used. They observed that the most significant correlation was with charge on the atoms of the sulfonamide group, followed by the nodal orientation and salvation energy calculated by COSMO and the charge polarization of the molecule calculated as

the mean absolute Mulliken charge over all atoms. The models obtained by Clare and Supuran⁵³ are summarized below

(1) Models for CA I

In case of CA I following two models was proposed

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_1 = & -0.153 (1.9) \cos 2\phi_H - 0.406 (5.8) \sin 2\phi_H \\ & - 1.465 (7.3) \cos 4\phi_L + 1.228 (13.7) \sin 4\phi_L \\ & + 0.0214 (4.2) \Delta H_S + 0.554 (7.9) \pi_{\text{tail}} \\ & + 8.035 (10.9) Q_M - 84.95 (19.4) Q_N \\ & - 0.0035 (3.2) \pi_{\text{xx}} - 0.471 (6.4) E_{\text{SH}} - 76.36 \quad (40) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 144, R^2 = 0.828, Q^2 = 0.800, \text{Se} = 0.41, \alpha_{\text{rand}} = 3 \times 10^{-38}$$

$\phi_{\text{H opt}} = 34.7^\circ, \phi_{\text{L opt}} = 80.0^\circ$, significant auto correlations

$$\text{Lag 16 } R = +0.26, \text{Lag 25 } R = -0.32$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_1 = & -0.2208 (2.7) \cos 2\phi_H - 0.4274 (5.6) \sin 2\phi_H \\ & - 1.2627 (5.3) \cos 4\phi_L + 1.3262 (12.7) \sin 4\phi_L \\ & + 0.0210 (4.2) \Delta H_S + 0.5637 (7.7) \pi_{\text{tail}} \\ & + 0.5422 (3.2) E_L + 7.9811 (10.8) Q_M \\ & - 95.57 (10.9) Q_N - 0.0040 (3.6) \pi_{\text{xx}} \\ & + 26.67 (2.9) Q_H - 0.421 (5.7) E_{\text{SH}} - 106.10 (41) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 144, R^2 = 0.836, Q^2 = 0.802, \text{Se} = 0.41, \alpha_{\text{rand}} = 1 \times 10^{-36}$$

$\phi_{\text{H opt}} = 31.3^\circ, \phi_{\text{L opt}} = 78.4^\circ$, significant auto correlations

$$\text{Lag 16 } R = +0.24, \text{Lag 25 } R = -0.22$$

Here, N is the number of compounds in the regression, R^2 is the square multiple correlation coefficient, Q^2 is the cross-validated correlation coefficient (i.e. based on the leave one out technique), Se is the standard error of estimate, α_{rand} is the statistical significance of the flip regression based on randomizing the dependent variable, $\phi_{\text{H opt}}$ and $\phi_{\text{L opt}}$ are the values of ϕ_{H} and ϕ_{L} that minimize K_1 (i.e. maximize the activity) calculated from the coefficients of the trigonometric terms and the numbers in the parentheses are the magnitude of the Student's t value for each term. At value greater than approximately 2 indicates a term that is significant with better than 95% confidence and larger values are indicative of terms of greater importance in explaining $\log K_1$.

(2) For CA II

Clare and Supuran obtained the following three models for CA II inhibitory activity

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_1 = & -0.425 (5.4) \cos 2\phi_H - 0.880 (12.4) \sin 2\phi_H \\ & - 0.498 (2.5) \cos 4\phi_L + 0.256 (3.1) \sin 4\phi_L \\ & + 0.030 (7.1) \Delta H_S + 1.317 (9.3) E_H \\ & + 0.426 (6.1) \pi_{\text{tail}} + 7.013 (9.3) Q_M \\ & - 70.05 (19.6) Q_H - 0.368 (3.1) E_{\text{SL}} + 47.24 \quad (42) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 144, R^2 = 0.869, Q^2 = 0.848, \text{Se} = 0.40, \alpha_{\text{rand}} = 3 \times 10^{-55}$$

$\phi_{\text{H opt}} = 147.9^\circ, \phi_{\text{L opt}} = 6.8^\circ$, significant auto correlations

$$\text{Lag 16 } R = +0.31, \text{Lag 28 } R = -0.25$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_1 = & -0.166 (2.1) \cos 2\phi_H - 0.810 (11.6) \sin 2\phi_H \\ & - 0.858 (3.9) \cos 4\phi_L + 0.150 (2.0) \sin 4\phi_L \\ & + 10.29 (4.4) Q_C + 0.0354 (8.6) \Delta H_S \\ & - 1.324 (9.5) E_H + 0.467 (6.8) \pi_{\text{tail}} \\ & + 7.53 (10.2) Q_M - 38.65 (18.0) Q_O \\ & - 0.709 (4.8) E_{\text{SL}} - 53.41 \quad (43) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 144, R^2 = 0.876, Q^2 = 0.854, \text{Se} = 0.39, \alpha_{\text{rand}} = 6 \times 10^{-58}$$

$\phi_{\text{H opt}} = 140.8^\circ, \phi_{\text{L opt}} = 2.5^\circ$, significant auto correlations

$$\text{Lag 16 } R = +0.31, \text{Lag 29 } R = -0.24$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_1 = & 0.0847 (1.1) \cos 2\phi_H - 0.846 (11.5) \sin 2\phi_H \\ & - 1.289 (5.9) \cos 4\phi_L + 0.103 (1.4) \sin 4\phi_L \\ & + 0.0316 (6.0) \Delta H_S - 1.191 (8.6) E_H \\ & + 0.531 (7.4) \pi_{\text{tail}} + 8.125 (10.2) Q_M \\ & - 0.0032 (3.0) \pi_{\text{xx}} - 34.66 (20.3) Q_O \\ & - 0.285 (4.2) E_{\text{SH}} - 0.469 (4.0) E_{\text{SL}} - 49.26 \quad (44) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 144, R^2 = 0.878, Q^2 = 0.853, \text{Se} = 0.39, \alpha_{\text{rand}} = 2 \times 10^{-15}$$

$\phi_{\text{H opt}} = 132.1^\circ, \phi_{\text{L opt}} = 1.1^\circ$, significant auto correlations

$$\text{Lag 16 } R = +0.22$$

Clare and Supuran⁵³ recommended that the model expressed by eq (44) is the most satisfactory of any that was obtained. On the basis of Student's t test Q_O is the most significant term, followed by $\sin 2\phi_H$ and Q_M . From the coefficients of $\sin 2\phi_H$ and $\cos 2\phi_H$ they calculated an optimum ϕ_H and similarly ϕ_L . The angles for the nodes of the LUPO are a relatively small contributor, along with Q_C and E_{SL} . The parameters E_H , ΔH_S and π_{tail} are moderate contributors. Much the same impression may be obtained pictorially

(3) For CA IV

According to Clare and Supuran⁵³ for CA IV the following two models are statistically more significant :

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_i = & 0.396 (4.0) \cos 2\phi_H - 1.091 (11.6) \sin 2\phi_H \\ & - 1.963 (7.1) \cos 4\phi_L + 0.277 (3.1) \sin 4\phi_L \\ & + 0.0455 (9.7) \Delta H_S - 1.409 (8.8) E_H \\ & + 0.279 (3.5) \pi_{\text{tail}} + 0.548 (3.6) E_L \\ & + 5.72 (6.7) Q_M - 33.50 (5.7) Q_N - 36.38 \quad (45) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 144, R^2 = 0.850, Q^2 = 0.826, Se = 0.46, \alpha_{\text{rand}} = 6 \times 10^{-37},$

$\phi_{H \text{ opt}} = 55.0^\circ, \phi_{L \text{ opt}} = 88.0^\circ$, significant auto correlations :

$$\text{Lag 6 : } R = -0.38; \text{Lag 8 : } R = +0.22; \text{Lag 12 : } R = -0.29$$

$$\text{Lag 16 : } R = +0.23; \text{Lag 20 : } R = -0.27$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_i = & 0.414 (4.3) \cos 2\phi_H - 1.085 (11.7) \sin 2\phi_H \\ & - 2.053 (7.5) \cos 4\phi_L + 0.289 (3.3) \sin 4\phi_L \\ & + 0.0381 (6.7) \Delta H_S - 1.221 (6.8) E_H \\ & + 0.364 (4.1) \pi_{\text{tail}} + 0.430 (2.7) E_L \\ & + 5.049 (5.6) Q_M - 34.1 (5.9) Q_N \\ & - 0.0025 (2.2) \pi_{\text{xx}} - 35.50 \quad (46) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 144, R^2 = 0.855, Q^2 = 0.831, Se = 0.45, \alpha_{\text{rand}} = 4 \times 10^{-37},$$

$\phi_{H \text{ opt}} = 55.4^\circ, \phi_{L \text{ opt}} = 88.0^\circ$, significant auto correlations :

$$\text{Lag 4 : } R = -0.37; \text{Lag 8 : } R = +0.23; \text{Lag 12 : } R = -0.29;$$

$$\text{Lag 16 : } R = +0.23; \text{Lag 20 : } R = -0.27$$

7.3.15. Jurs development of QSAR and classification models for a set of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors

Mattioni and Jurs⁸⁹ proposed a development of quantitative structure-activity relationships and classification models for a set of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors. Mathematical models were developed by them to find out quantitative structure activity relationships that correlate chemical structure and inhibition toward three carbonic anhydrase isozymes : CA I, CA II and CA IV. Numerical descriptors were generated to encode important topological, geometric and electronic features of molecular structure. After descriptor generation, multiple linear regression and computational neural network (CNN) analyses were performed on various descriptor subsets to find superior models of prediction committees of five CNN, were

utilized to average final predicted values for the 142-compound data set. For inhibitors of CA I, an 8-5-1 CNN committee produced a training set rms error of 0.105 log K_i ($R^2 = 0.994$) and prediction set rms error of 0.208 log K_i ($R^2 = 0.980$). Training and prediction set rms error of 0.140 log K_i ($R^2 = 0.992$) and 0.231 log K_i ($R^2 = 0.971$), respectively, were produced by a 9-5-1 CNN committee for inhibitory of CA II. For prediction of CA IV inhibitors, an 8-5-1 CNN committee produced training and prediction set rms errors of 0.147 log K_i ($R^2 = 0.992$) and 0.211 log K_i ($R^2 = 0.991$), respectively. In addition, classification models were built by Clare and Supuran using k-nearest neighbor (kNN) analysis to solve two- and three-class problems for inhibitors of CA IV. A three-descriptor classification model proved superior in labeling compounds as active or inactive inhibitors for the two-class problem : Training and prediction set percent classification, rates of 100% and 87.1%, respectively, were obtained. For the three class (active/moderate/inactive) problem, a five-descriptor model was deemed optimal producing training set percent classification rates of 98.8% and prediction set rate of 79%.

7.3.16. QSAR study on some sulfonamide drugs with lower intra-ocular pressure, using the ACE non-linear statistical method

Clare and Supuran⁵⁴ reported a QSAR study on some sulfonamide drugs with lower intra-ocular pressure, using the ACE non-linear statistical method. They developed quantum chemical QSAR expressions for a heterogeneous group of 36 sulfonamides which have been shown to lower intra-ocular pressure in *in vivo* tests of animals. They observed that using the ACE statistical technique the lowering of intra-ocular pressure correlated non-linearly with K_i for carbonic anhydrase inhibition. Chemical variables were found to be relevant to CA inhibition included the dipole moment vector, the frontier orbital energies, the salvation energy determined by the COSMO model, the electrostatic potential based charges on the atoms of the sulfonamide group, and the size and polarizability of the molecule. The most appropriate model for modeling K_i is found as below :

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_i = & - 3.51 (\pm 0.62) Q_c + 41.7 (\pm 17.2) S^E_N \\ & - 1.17 (\pm 0.25) D_1 \\ & + 0.0827 (+0.0120) \mu_{S-N} \\ & - 0.0157 (\pm 0.0032) \Delta H_S \\ & - 0.0205 (\pm 0.00315) \pi \\ & + 0.968 (\pm 0.161) E_{L-H} + 7.03 \quad (47) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 36, R^2 = 0.817, Q^2 = 0.658, Se = 0.25, \wedge = 2.84, F = 17.92, P = 7 \times 10^{-10}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Also, } \log K_{in} = & 5.16 (\pm 1.06) Q_c + 724.8 \\ & (\pm 154.0) S^E_S + 0.169 (\pm 0.040) A_x \\ & + 0.341 (\pm 0.065) A_y \\ & + 0.00645 (\pm 0.00181) S \\ & + 0.0882 (\pm 0.0199) \log P + 93.03 \quad (48) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 35, R^2 = 0.637, Q^2 = 0.362, Se = 0.50, \wedge = 2.42, F = 8.18, P = 0.00004$

7.3.17. QSAR analysis for CA II

Gao and Bajorth⁹¹ have reported a comparison of binary and 2D QSAR analysis using inhibitors of human carbonic anhydrase II (CA II) as a test set. They observed an overall predictive accuracy of 94% for binary QSAR and of 84% for 2D QSAR models. For both models, preferred molecular descriptor sets were identified, which were overlapping but not identical. Both binary and 2D QSAR captured important molecular features of CA II inhibitory, notably the presence of a sulfonamide group, which is critical for binding, but also hydrophobicity. Promising results were obtained when the derived QSAR models were used to test a set of CA II inhibitors not included in the training set. In binary QSAR, previously unobserved boundary effects were detected both in the analysis of known inhibitors and when screening a large combinatorial library for putative inhibitors. The complementary use of binary and conventional 2D QSAR was thought to increase the accuracy of the lead discovery process by QSAR techniques.

Statistically significant model was found as below :

$$\begin{aligned} \log I/C = & 0.71 \text{}^1\chi^v - 0.35 \text{}^0\chi^v + 0.66 \text{}^1k \\ & - 0.23 \text{}^2k - 0.33 \text{apol} \\ & + 0.67 I + 0.18 \log P \\ & + 0.37 (\log P)^2 + 0.46 \quad (49) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 280, R^2 = 0.84, Q^2 = 0.82, Se = 0.98, \log P_o = 1.34$

There is parabolic correlation with log P, which has an optimal log P value of 1.34 ($\log P_o = 1.34$). This means that the CA II inhibitory activity increase initially with the increase in log P values of inhibitions until a log P value of 1.34 than the inhibitory activity decreases with any further increase in log P values. Interestingly, the sum of atomic polarizability (α) is important for the enzyme-inhibitor interaction. Polarizability is an indication of charge-induced dipole or dipole-induced dipole interactions, and/or van der Waals interactions. In the present

case, dipole moment descriptors of the inhibitors were not significant. An important similarity between binary and 2D QSAR is the requirement of the SO_2NH_2 structural fragment of the inhibitor molecules. Both binary and 2D QSAR captured the similar structural features of carbonic anhydrase II inhibitors.

7.3.18. Quantum chemical QSAR of a group of benzene disulfonamides

Clare and Supuran⁵⁵ reported quantum chemical QSAR for a group of benzene disulfonamides containing both a primary and secondary sulfonamide moiety. These compounds are powerful inhibitors of several isozymes of the benzene carbonic anhydrase. Separate QSAR models were proposed for inhibition of isozymes CA I, CA II and CA IV using descriptors mainly derived from molecular orbital calculation for the semi-empirical AM1 method activity was found to be dependent on electrostatic potential-based charges on the atoms of both sulfonamide groups, HOMO and LUMO energies, dipole moments and lipophilicity.

The models obtained by Clare and Supuran⁵⁵ are given below :

(1) For CA I

Three models were proposed for modeling inhibitory activity ($\log IC_{50}$) against CA I.

The QSAR models proposed by Supuran

$$\begin{aligned} (1) \log IC_{50} = & 5.79 (\pm 2.12) Q_{57} \\ & + 4.26 (\pm 1.01) Q_{H17} \\ & - 0.0326 (\pm 0.011) \mu_x \\ & + 0.299 (\pm 0.108) E_H \\ & + 0.600 (\pm 0.145) E_L \\ & - 2.12 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 1.14 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{yy} \\ & - 0.0209 (\pm 0.0088) \Delta H_s \\ & + 3.13 (\pm 0.96) Q_{C1} - 10.30 \quad (50) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 72, R^2 = 0.019, Q^2 = 0.512, Se = 0.22, \wedge = 3.10, F = 12.8, P = 1 \times 10^{-12}$

$$\begin{aligned} (2) \log IC_{50} = & 3.73 (\pm 1.30) Q_{C1} \\ & + 4.74 (\pm 1.12) Q_{H17} \\ & + 0.310 (\pm 0.103) E_H \\ & + 0.821 (\pm 0.170) E_L \\ & - 13.84 (\pm 5.25) Q_{O1} \\ & - 0.0201 (\pm 0.0089) \Delta H_s \\ & + 0.328 (\pm 0.084) I_3 - 20.73 \quad (51) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 72, R^2 = 0.610, Q^2 = 0.517, Se = 0.22, \wedge =$

4.85, $F = 14.3$, $P = 5 \times 10^{-11}$
 (3) $\log IC_{50} = -3.33 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 9.2 \times 10^{-4}) \pi_{22}$
 $+ 0.533 (\pm 0.087) E_H$
 $+ 0.378 (\pm 0.117) E_L + 7.91$ (52)
 $N = 72$, $R^2 = 0.540$, $Q^2 = 0.500$, $Se = 0.23$, $\Delta = 1.04$, $F = 26.6$, $P = 2 \times 10^{-11}$

(2) For CA II

In this case also three models were proposed as below :

(1) $\log IC_{50} = 2.63 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 1.34 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{yy}$
 $+ 3.67 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 1.23 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{zz}$
 $- 1.12 (\pm 0.244) Q_{N13}$
 $+ 0.239 (\pm 0.0117) \mu$
 $+ 0.644 (\pm 0.173) E_L$
 $- 0.115 (\pm 0.046) \log P$
 $- 4.16 (\pm 1.14) Q_{02}$
 $- 0.592 (\pm 0.095) I_3 - 7.50$ (53)

$N = 72$, $R^2 = 0.682$, $Q^2 = 0.594$, $Se = 0.24$, $\Delta = 1.75$, $F = 16.9$, $P = 4 \times 10^{-13}$

(2) $\log IC_{50} = 4.53 (\pm 0.97) Q_{c1}$
 $+ 0.0251 (\pm 0.103) \mu_x$
 $+ 0.551 (\pm 0.176) E_L$
 $+ 3.49 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 1.06 \times 10^{-3}) V_w$
 $- 0.183 (\pm 0.049) \log P$
 $- 2.91 (\pm 1.09) Q_{02}$
 $+ 3.06 (\pm 0.58) Q_{m+p} - 6.98$ (54)

$N = 72$, $R^2 = 0.663$, $Q^2 = 0.591$, $Se = 0.25$, $\Delta = 2.85$, $F = 18.0$, $P = 3 \times 10^{-13}$

(3) $\log IC_{50} = -1.45 (\pm 0.26) Q_{N13}$
 $+ 0.649 (\pm 0.153) E_L$
 $- 1.25 (\pm 0.330) D_1$
 $- 0.189 (\pm 0.0486) \log P$
 $- 3.18 (\pm 1.08) Q_{02}$
 $- 0.532 (\pm 0.056) I_3 - 3.30$ (55)

$N = 72$, $R^2 = 0.652$, $Q^2 = 0.581$, $Se = 0.25$, $\Delta = 1.69$, $F = 20.3$, $P = 3 \times 10^{-13}$

(3) For CA IV

Here also three models were proposed as given below :

(1) $\log IC_{50} = -0.891 (\pm 0.317) Q_{N13}$
 $+ 0.322 (\pm 0.134) E_H$

$+ 0.377 (\pm 0.166) E_L$
 $- 0.921 (\pm 0.367) D_1$
 $- 0.184 (\pm 0.060) \log P$
 $- 2.885 (\pm 1.108) Q_{02}$
 $- 0.350 (\pm 0.101) I_3 - 0.45$ (56)

$N = 72$, $R^2 = 0.661$, $Q^2 = 0.591$, $Se = 0.25$, $\Delta = 2.21$, $F = 17.9$, $P = 6 \times 10^{-13}$

(2) $\log IC_{50} = 1.409 (\pm 0.405) Q_{5/4}$
 $- 0.0261 (\pm 0.0104) \mu_x$
 $+ 0.405 (\pm 0.117) E_H$
 $+ 0.327 (\pm 0.134) E_L$
 $- 0.122 (\pm 0.045) \log P + 2.296$ (57)

$N = 72$, $R^2 = 0.630$, $Q^2 = 0.581$, $Se = 0.26$, $\Delta = 1.36$, $F = 22.5$, $P = 4 \times 10^{-13}$

(3) $\log IC_{50} = -0.0210 (\pm 0.0101) \mu_x$
 $+ 0.604 (\pm 0.109) E_H$
 $- 4.44 (\pm 0.83) Q_{02} - 0.73$ (58)

$N = 72$, $R^2 = 0.600$, $Q^2 = 0.560$, $Se = 0.26$, $\Delta = 1.21$, $F = 33.9$, $P = 6 \times 10^{-13}$

7.3.19. Quantum chemical QSAR of a group of 1,3,4-thiadiazole and 1,3,4-thiadiazoline di-sulfonamides with carbonic anhydrase inhibitory properties

Supuran and Clare⁵⁶ have described quantum chemical QSAR expression for 20 1,3,4-thiadiazole disulfonamides and 20 1,3,4-thiadiazole disulfonamide inhibitors of carbonic anhydrase, for isozymes CA I, CA II and CA IV using AM1 method. The charges on the atoms of the sulfonamide moiety were found of central importance, as is also the electric field in the neighborhood of the primary sulfonamide group. Also, the polarizability of the molecule is implicated in an anisotropic manner. A new feature of their study was correlation with salvation energy of the molecule, calculated by the COSMO continuum Modelan and Clare⁹¹ is given below, separately for CA I, CA II and CA IV.

(1) Results for CA-I inhibition

Using all the 40 compounds the following statistically significant model was proposed by Supuran and Clare⁵⁶ :

$\log IC_{50} = 9.29 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 1.38 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{xH}$
 $- 5.72 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 2.31 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{zz}$
 $- 13.04 (\pm 2.87) Q_{Nr2} + 17.07 (\pm 4.59) Q_{Sr}$
 $+ 1.560 (\pm 0.790) Q_{s2}$
 $+ 6.90 \times 10^{-2} (\pm 1.82 \times 10^{-2}) \mu_x - 50.83$ (59)

$N = 40$, $R^2 = 0.753$, $Q^2 = 0.628$, $Se = 0.289$, $\wedge = 2.87$, $F = 16.78$

They observed that in this model four compounds are the cationic compounds and these acted as outliers. Deleting these four compounds from the regression procedure the following model was proposed :

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & -3.68 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 1.44 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{zz} \\ & + 3.152 (\pm 1.074) Q_{Cr2} \\ & + 0.157 (\pm 0.023) \mu_x \\ & + 0.40 (\pm 0.168) \log P \\ & - 24.62 (\pm 4.01) Q_{UA} - 44.1 \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

$N = 36$, $R^2 = 0.700$, $Q^2 = 0.570$, $Se = 0.201$, $\wedge = 2.41$, $F = 13.98$

With an aim of obtaining still better models, Supuran and Clare⁵⁶ have attempted separate modeling of 20 thiadiazoles and 20 thiadiazolines and proposed the following models :

(a) *Model with 20 thiadiazoles*

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & 59.43 (\pm 6.57) Q_{v1} \\ & + 0.1359 (\pm 0.0329) \mu_x \\ & - 0.0300 (\pm 0.0116) \mu_z \\ & - 0.0204 (\pm 0.0073) \Delta H_s \\ & + 98.87 (\pm 10.30) Q_{U1} + 27.83 \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

$N = 20$, $R^2 = 0.909$, $Q^2 = 0.502$, $Se = 0.18$, $\wedge = 4.45$, $F = 27.54$

(b) *For 20 thiadiazolines*

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & 8.47 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 1.43 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{xx} \\ & + 5.871 (\pm 1.791) Q_{s2} \\ & - 1.787 (\pm 0.367) E_H \\ & - 1.575 (\pm 0.325) E_L \\ & + 0.501 (\pm 0.0100) \Delta H_s \\ & - 82.31 (\pm 17.76) Q_{01} \\ & - 16.36 (\pm 4.16) Q_{02} \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

$N = 20$, $R_2 = 0.917$, $Q^2 = 0.0712$, $Se = 0.21$, $\wedge = 4.54$, $F = 18.92$

(2) *Results for CA II inhibition*

(a) *For all the 40 compounds*

Considering all the 40 compounds the inhibitory activity against CA II, was investigated by Supuran and Clare⁵⁶ and proposed the following model :

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & 8.93 (\pm 1.20 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{xy} \\ & + 6.68 (\pm 1.15) Q_{Cr1} \\ & + 18.97 (\pm 4.94) Q_{v1} \\ & - 0.736 (\pm 0.266) E_H \\ & + 0.0667 (\pm 0.0211) \mu_x \\ & - 0.0417 (\pm 0.0160) \mu_z \\ & + 0.0275 (\pm 0.0081) \Delta H_s - 64.15 (62-\wedge) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 40$, $R^2 = 0.719$, $Q^2 = 0.475$, $Se = 0.304$, $\wedge = 2.47$, $F = 11.70$

Here also, for the reason given above, the same set of four compounds was detected from the regression, which then resulted into following model with improved quality :

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & -7.05 (\pm 1.07) Q_{Cr1} \\ & + 13.19 (\pm 4.35) Q_{S1} \\ & - 0.677 (\pm 0.140) E_H \\ & + 0.126 (\pm 0.016) \mu_x \\ & - 0.0421 (\pm 0.0144) \mu_z \\ & + 0.298 (\pm 0.133) \log P \\ & + 0.0302 (\pm 0.0083) \Delta H_s + 46.52 \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

$N = 36$, $R^2 = 0.876$, $Q^2 = 0.777$, $Se = 0.152$, $\wedge = 2.60$, $F = 28.06$

Also, Supuran and Clare⁵⁶ attempted QSAR modeling separately for the thiadiazoles and the thiadiazoline. The models are given below :

(b) *Model for 20 thiadiazoles*

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & 63.34 (\pm 6.97) Q_{S1} \\ & - 0.696 (\pm 0.204) E_{H1} \\ & - 0.1346 (\pm 0.0343) \mu \\ & - 0.0504 (\pm 0.0135) \mu_z \\ & - 0.0406 (\pm 0.0077) \Delta H_s \\ & + 104.7 (\pm 10.6) Q_1 + 22.46 \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

$N = 20$, $R^2 = 0.902$, $Q^2 = 0.150$, $Se = 0.18$, $\wedge = 4.24$, $F = 19.93$

(c) *Model for 20 thiadiazolines*

No statistically valid model was obtained.

(3) *Results for CA IV inhibition*

The modeling procedure adopted by Supuran and Clare⁵⁶ for proposing the models for CA IV inhibition remains the same as discussed in earlier two cases. First of all the 40 compounds were considered in the modeling procedure, followed by deletion of the four outliers and

finally proposing separate modeling for the thiadiazoles and the thiadiazolines. These models are given below :

(a) *All the 40 compounds*

$$\log IC_{50} = 7.31 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 9.65 \times 10^{-4}) \pi_{xx} - 5.570 (\pm 1.43) Q_{Cr1} + 11.46 (\pm 4.90) Q_{S1} - 0.0602 (\pm 0.0201) \mu_H - 37.1 \quad (65)$$

N = 40, R² = 0.632, Q² = 0.444, Se = 0.34, \wedge = 1.48, F = 15.07

Deletion the referred four outliers gave the following model with improved statistics.

$$\log IC_{50} = -2.798 (\pm 0.336) Q_{Nr1} + 8.447 (\pm 3.732) Q_{S1} + 0.1800 (\pm 0.0230) \mu_c + 0.5295 (\pm 0.1682) \log P + 0.0298 (\pm 0.0076) \Delta H_{sc} - 20.11 \quad (66)$$

N = 36, R² = 0.769, Q² = 0.646, Se = 0.20, \wedge = 1.99, F = 20.25

(b) *Model for 20 thiadiazoles*

$$\log IC_{50} = 7.36 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 1.04 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{xx} - 18.90 (\pm 6.72) Q_{N1} + 0.1228 (\pm 0.0452) \mu_x - 22.29 \quad (67)$$

N = 20, R² = 0.760, Q² = 0.340, Se = 0.29, \wedge = 1.14, F = 16.8

(c) *Model for 20 thiadiazolines*

$$\log IC_{50} = 7.29 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 1.22 \times 10^{-3}) \pi_{yy} - 1.628 (\pm 0.384) E_H + 0.0977 (\pm 0.0226) \mu_x - 105.4 (\pm 21.5) Q_{O1} - 208.9 \quad (68)$$

N = 20, R² = 0.822, Q² = 0.358, Se = 0.25, \wedge = 1.96, F = 17.23

7.3.20. Quantum chemical QSAR for a group of sulfonamide Schiff base inhibitors of carbonic anhydrase

Supuran and Clare⁵⁷ discussed quantum chemical quantitative structure-activity relations for a group of sulfonamide Schiff base inhibitors of carbonic anhydrase. A series of sulfanilamide Schiff base inhibitor of CA I and CA II have been studied by the semiempirical AM1 method. The charges on the atoms of the sulfonamide group and the dipole moment were calculated by four methods : (1) standard vacuum calculation; (2) a solution calculation by the COSMO method; (3) a solution calculation with the charges and dipole moment, and (4) a calculation by the older CNDO method. The data were

subjected to a classical multiple regression analysis with care to avoid the possibility of chance correlation or collinearity. The ACE technique was also used to allow the nonlinearity. A number of statistically significant equations were derived. The ESP-based charges gave the best equations (models). Supuran and Clare⁵⁷ claimed that study is the first study which evidenced by means of QSAR calculation isozyme – specific features of the two isozymes CA I and CA II, in their interaction with sulfonamide inhibitors.

The models proposed by Supuran and Clare⁵⁷ are given below, where in we have mentioned models for CA I and CA II inhibition separately :

(1) *CA I inhibition*

As mentioned above, the modeling of CA-I inhibition was performed by the four methods, as given below :

(a) *Solution* : On applying all the possible subsets and principal components procedure, the best two equations proposed by Supuran and Clare⁹² are given below :

$$(i) \log K_i = 0.1003 (\pm 0.0189) D_x - 0.0949 (\pm 0.0203) D_z + 3.133 (\pm 0.635) D_1 - 736.7 (\pm 95.9) Q_H + 0.3893 (\pm 0.0473) \log P + 80.81 (\pm 16.52) S_m^E - 907.7 (\pm 148.0) (S_P^E - 0.5 S_O^E) + 472.5 \quad (69)$$

N = 35, R² = 0.838, Q² = 0.683, Se = 0.190, \wedge = 3.66, F = 19.0

$$(ii) \log K_i = -0.0727 (\pm 0.0205) D - 0.00790 (\pm 0.00130) P_{xx} - 286.0 (\pm 97.1) Q_H + 0.2986 (\pm 0.0506) \log P + 0.5931 (\pm 0.2260) pK_1 + 0.0629 (\pm 0.0297) pK_2 + 160.8 \quad (70)$$

N = 35, R² = 0.765, Q² = 0.584, Se = 0.222, \wedge = 3.00, F = 15.0

(b) *Solution ESP* : Application of all the possible subsets MLR/ PCA technique to the solution ESP results for CA I yielded following two statistically significant models :

$$(i) \log K_i = -11.74 (\pm 3.65) Q_S - 1.773 (\pm 0.0621) D_1 + 0.1956 (\pm 0.0451) \log P + 1.00062 (\pm 0.157) pK_1 + 172.8 (\pm 62.0) S_P^E + 59.07 \quad (71)$$

N = 35, R² = 0.762, Q² = 0.573, Se = 0.218, \wedge = 2.52, F = 18.5

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(ii) } \log K_i &= -12.63 (\pm 3.78) Q_S \\ &- 0.00374 (\pm 0.00129) P_{xx} \\ &+ 0.2601 (\pm 0.0531) \log P \\ &+ 0.9130 (\pm 0.1574) pK_1 + 25.5 \quad (72) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 35, R^2 = 0.736, Q^2 = 0.609, Se = 0.226, \wedge = 2.84, F = 20.9$$

Supuran and Clare⁵⁷ observed that application of the ACE technique of Breiman and Friedmat⁹² to eq. (73) led to the transformation plots and a piecewise linear fit of the first two variables to the equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_i &= -24.53 (\pm 4.53) Q^*_S \\ &- 0.00340 (\pm 0.00120) P^*_{xx} \\ &+ 0.2461 (\pm 0.0395) \log P \\ &+ 0.6935 (\pm 0.1269) pK_1 + 60.1 \quad (73) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 35, R^2 = 0.813, Q^2 = 0.729, Se = 0.189, \wedge = 2.48, F = 33.2$$

(c) *Vacuum* : Application of all the possible subsets MLR/PCA technique to the CA-I vacuum results gave the following model :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i) } \log K_i &= 0.1111 (\pm 0.0280) D_x \\ &- 0.1248 (\pm 0.0308) D_z \\ &- 0.00792 (\pm 0.00129) P_{xx} \\ &- 291.1 (\pm 70.4) Q_M \\ &+ 0.3675 (\pm 0.0432) \log P \\ &+ 0.7025 (\pm 0.2210) pK_1 \\ &- 401.2 (\pm 178.8) (S^E_P - 5S^E_O) + 143.1 \quad (74) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 35, R^2 = 0.811, Q^2 = 0.624, Se = 0.200, \wedge = 4.30, F = 16.9$$

(d) *CNDO* : Application of all the possible subsets MLR/PCA technique to the CA I CNDO yielded following two models :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i) } \log K_i &= 0.0671 (\pm 0.0257) D \\ &+ 0.2912 (\pm 1.2030) E_L \\ &+ 3.214 (\pm 0.7381) D_1 \\ &+ 0.2982 (\pm 0.0449) \log P \\ &+ 1.050 (\pm 0.1731) pK_1 \\ &+ 144.44 (\pm 28.60) S^E_O + 56.7 \quad (75) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 34, R^2 = 0.783, Q^2 = 0.540, Se = 0.215, \wedge = 2.45, F = 16.2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(ii) } \log K_i &= -0.0620 (\pm 0.0259) D \\ &+ 2.855 (\pm 0.707) D_1 \\ &+ 0.2936 (\pm 0.0450) \log P \\ &+ 0.9842 (\pm 0.1700) pK_1 \\ &+ 137.5 (\pm 27.7) S^E_O + 54.04 \quad (76) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 34, R^2 = 0.767, Q^2 = 0.578, Se = 0.259, \wedge = 2.50, F = 18.4$$

In terms of Q^2 , the effectiveness of the best model for each series as a prediction was :

$$\text{Solution ESP} > \text{Solution} > \text{Vacuum} > \text{CNDO} \quad (77)$$

(2) CA II Inhibition

We now discuss the models proposed by Supuran and Clare⁵⁷ in modeling CA II inhibition. Different models are proposed depending upon the four methods mentioned above.

(a) *Solution* : Application of all the possible subsets MLR/PCA technique to the CA II solution made by Supuran and Clare⁵⁷ to propose the following four models :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i) } \log K_{ii} &= 184.3 (\pm 62.4) Q_S \\ &+ 3.070 (\pm 0.805) D_1 + 1.455 (\pm 0.241) I_p \\ &- 1506.6 (\pm 186.6) (S^E_P - 0.5S^E_O) - 538.0 \quad (78) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 35, R^2 = 0.783, Q^2 = 0.702, Se = 0.308, \wedge = 2.82, F = 30.7$$

Analysis of eq. (78) by the ACE technique led to the equation :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(ii) } \log K_{ii} &= 156.6 (\pm 55.9) Q_S \\ &+ 3.599 (\pm 0.768) D^*_1 \\ &+ 1.390 (\pm 0.206) I_p \\ &- 1605.8 (\pm 188.1) (S^E_P - 0.5S^E_O)^* - 453.3 \quad (79) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 35, R^2 = 0.817, Q^2 = 0.745, Se = 0.283, \wedge = 2.54, F = 37.9$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(iii) } \log K_{ii} &= 3.441 (\pm 0.850) D_1 \\ &- 312.12 (\pm 104.52) Q_H \\ &+ 1.5494 (\pm 0.2580) I_p \\ &- 1541.8 (\pm 196.4) (S^E_P - 0.5S^E_O) + 196.4 \quad (80) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 35, R^2 = 0.788, Q^2 = 0.715, Se = 0.318, \wedge = 2.98, F = 28.2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(iv) } \log K_{ii} &= 3.992 (\pm 0.845) D^*_1 \\ &- 238.8 (\pm 88.5) Q^2_H \\ &+ 1.447 (\pm 0.220) I_p \\ &- 1617.8 (\pm 196.8) (S^E_P - 0.5S^E_O)^* + 96.7 \quad (81) \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 35, R^2 = 0.821, Q^2 = 0.755, Se = 0.295, \wedge = 2.63, F = 34.2$$

(b) *Solution ESP* : Equations similar to (81) were obtained with extra terms D_1 , P_{zz} or P_{xx} and an equation with two extra terms D and D_1 . In each case, these extra terms had $\alpha > 0.05$. Analysis of one of this equation by the ACE technique led to the following equation :

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_{ii} = & -0.0651 (\pm 0.0212) D_X \\ & - 9916.1 (\pm 3916.9) Q_{II} \\ & + 6114.2 (\pm 2407.7) Q^2_{II} \\ & + 1.1921 (\pm 0.2413) I_p \\ & - 603.5 (\pm 58.7) (S^E_P - 0.5S^E_m) \\ & - 113.6 (\pm 25.1) (Q_M + Q_P) + 4007.0 \quad (82) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 35, R^2 = 0.854, Q^2 = 0.794, Se = 0.274, \wedge = 67.43, F = 27.5$

The massive co-linearity in this eq. (82) is entirely due to the correlation between Q_{II} and Q^2_{II} . Because of the functional relationship between these two variables, the eq. (82) is not invalidated by the co-linearity, but it did become necessary to carry out the calculation in double precision to avoid numerical instability. As may be seen from the values, Q_{II} and Q^2_{II} are the weakest contenders for inclusion in the equation, but their inclusion does substantially improve the predictivity. This equation gave the best Q^2 for the CA II solution ESP results.

(c) **Vacuum** : Application of all the possible subsets MLR/PCA technique to the CA II vacuum yielded following two models :

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \log K_{ii} = & -179.3 (\pm 65.1) Q_{II} \\ & - 122.1 (\pm 16.2) Q_P - 37.7 (\pm 15.5) \\ & Q_m + 185.6 (\pm 47.1) S^E_O + 169.0 \quad (83) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 35, R^2 = 0.786, Q^2 = 0.735, Se = 0.324, \wedge = 3.15, F = 27.1$

$$\begin{aligned} (ii) \log K_{ii} = & 119.6 (\pm 0.0000) Q_C \\ & - 417.3 (\pm 0.0000) Q_{II} \\ & + 1.254 (\pm 0.0000) I_p \\ & - 80.8 (\pm 0.00148) (Q_m + Q_P) \\ & + 0.9639 (\pm 0.00034) (E_L - E_H) + 275.6 \quad (84) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 35, R^2 = 0.829, Q^2 = 0.774, Se = 0.294, \wedge = 3.31, F = 27.7$

This eq. (84) was the best equation for CA II in the vacuum series.

(d) **CNDO** : Application of all the possible subsets MLR/PCA technique to the CA II CNDO gave the following model :

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_{ii} = & 0.1633 (\pm 0.0430) D_X \\ & + 6.577 (\pm 1.285) D_1 - 541.0 (\pm 109.8) Q_{II} \\ & + 0.2439 (\pm 0.0721) \log P \\ & + 0.9760 (\pm 0.2386) pK_1 \\ & - 633.6 (\pm 86.6) (S^E_P - 0.5S^E_m) + 152.3 \quad (85) \end{aligned}$$

$N = 35, R^2 = 0.828, Q^2 = 0.725, Se = 0.308, \wedge = 4.75, F = 20.9$

7.3.21. QSAR based on semi-empirical atomic charges and dipole moments in hypervalent sulfonamides

Clare and Supuran⁵⁸ calculated Mulliken and ESP-based atomic charges and dipole moments for a group of substituted methane sulfonamides using several *ab initio* and semi-empirical methods in order to find the most reliable semi-empirical method of calculating these quantities in hypervalent molecules. They found that the *ab initio* Mulliken charges on the sulfonamide H were meaningless and that the *ab initio* ESP-based atomic charges calculated using any non-minimal basis set well reproduced the dipole moments. The semi-empirical results were less satisfactory, but in general, the ESP-based charges were more promising than the Mulliken charges, and CNDO-based dipole moments agreed better with *ab initio* dipole moments that with those calculated by AM₁ or PM₃. Clare and Supuran⁵⁸ argued that all charges for hypervalent molecules such as sulfonamides, calculated with semi-empirical methods, should be treated with caution.

7.3.22. QSAR involving kinetic rate constants

Clare and Supuran⁵⁹ have investigated quantitative structure-activity correlations involving kinetic rate constants of 20 sulfonamide inhibitors of carbonic anhydrase non-congeneric series. Only common factor in these compounds is the sulfonamide group, which is attached to a variety of substituted aromatic and hetero-aromatic nuclei. The important factors were local factors such as Mulliken charges on atoms of the sulfonamide group, and global factors such as the size and shape of the molecule, its calculated frontier orbital charges, and its lipophilicity. Good correlations were obtained with the equilibrium constant and the kinetic association rate constant, but not with the kinetic dissociation rate constant.

In this study Clare and Supuran⁵⁹ reported modeling of association rate constant (k_{on}), dissociated rate constant (k_{off}) and inhibition constant K_1 . This thermodynamic inhibition constant (K_1) is related to the kinetic parameters by the following formula :

$$K_1 = k_{off}/k_{on} \quad (86)$$

They claimed that their study is the first QSAR study involving kinetic as well as thermodynamic inhibition constant for 20 sulfonamides for which literature data regarding association and dissociation rates were avail-

able⁶⁰. The objective of their study was two fold : (i) to enable simple prediction of the potency of as yet unsynthesizing substances and (ii) to throw light on the mechanism of action of drug, and their interaction with the active site of the enzyme. The procedure used by Clare and Supuran⁹⁴ indicated that statistical significance was 0.0017 for $\log k_{on}$ and 0.0023 for $\log K_1$. Thus, for these models, the risk of chance correlation in the stepwise regression is at an acceptable level. No significant model could be obtained for $\log k_{off}$. The models obtained for $\log k_{on}$ and $\log K_1$ using Effroymsons algorithm was found as below :

$$\log K_{on} = 51.2 Q_N + 1.22 E_L + 0.373 A_X - 0.139 V_w + 0.125 A_w + 6.33 \quad (87)$$

$$\log K_1 = - 55.7 Q_N - 1.64 E_L + 0.459 D - 0.572 A_X - 0.251 A_Y + 0.625 \log P - 8.56 \quad (88)$$

The best five descriptor eq. (87) with an R^2 of 0.838 and involving Q_N , E_L , A_X , V_w and A_w was the best subset, in terms of its C_p of -1.61.

In addition, the following optimal linear regression models were proposed by Clare and Supuran⁵⁹ :

$$\log K_{on} = 51.2 (\pm 11.1) Q_N + 1.22 (\pm 0.40) E_L + 0.373 (\pm 0.111) A_X - 0.138 (\pm 0.028) V_w + 0.125 (\pm 0.026) A_w + 6.33 \quad (89)$$

$$R^2 = 0.839, Q^2 = 0.669, Se = 0.705, F = 14.5, \alpha = 4 \times 10^{-8}, \text{ all } \alpha_i < 0.01$$

$$\log K_1 = - 46.5 (\pm 10.6) Q_N - 0.988 (\pm 0.38) E_L + 0.418 (\pm 0.106) A_X + 0.144 (\pm 0.027) V_w - 0.128 (\pm 0.025) A_w - 3.26 \quad (90)$$

$$R^2 = 0.857, Q^2 = 0.701, Se = 0.669, F = 16.8, \alpha = 2 \times 10^{-5}, \text{ all } \alpha_i < 0.002$$

A repetition of all the possible subsets regressions with A_w term deleted gave more satisfactory results. For one and two variable subsets, better results were identical. For three variables, a good subset obtained with π_{zz} , A_Y and A_L ($C_p = 1.89$, $R^2 = 0.666$), with Q_N and then Q_O substituting for A_Y with less satisfactory statistics, and the fourth and fifth best equations contain Q_N , A_X and D and E_L , respectively.

The best four-descriptor equation was less satisfactory ($C_p = 2.38$, $R^2 = 0.702$), but contained Q_N , π_{zz} , A_Z and one of A_Y , E_L and D in order of increasing C_p .

The best five-descriptor equation ($C_p = 2.08$, $R^2 = 0.757$) contained Q_N , E_L , D , A_X and $\log P$. With less satisfactory fit, E_H substituted for E_L ($C_p = 2.90$). The

remaining four of the best six five-descriptor equations contained Q_N , A_Z and π_{zz} with combination of E_L , A_Y and D .

The best six-descriptor equation was the overall best with $C_p = 1.37$ and $R^2 = 0.822$. It contained Q_N , E_L , D , A_X , A_Y and $\log P$. In the three next best equations, π_{zz} substituted for A_Y and then E_H substituted for E_L , followed by A_X for A_Y . In the best seven-descriptor equation, A_Z and π_{zz} replaced A_Y in the best six-descriptor equation, giving $C_p = 2.78$ and $R^2 = 0.837$. The activity parameters $\log k_{on}$ and $\log K_1$ are very strongly negatively correlated. The optimal fit for $\log k_{on}$ with six variables was :

$$\log K_{on} = 60.3 (\pm 12.8) Q_N + 1.91 (\pm 0.49) E_L + 0.551 (\pm 0.100) A_X + 0.286 (\pm 0.131) A_Y - 0.446 (\pm 0.111) D - 0.659 (\pm 0.212) \log P + 11.30 \quad (91)$$

$$R^2 = 0.823, Q^2 = 0.580, Se = 0.767, F = 10.1, \alpha = 3 \times 10^{-4}, \text{ all } \alpha_i < 0.01 \text{ except } A_Y (0.047)$$

Substitution of the compound variables $\pi_{xx} + \pi_{yy} + \pi_{zz}$ for π_{xx} , π_{yy} and π_{zz} ; A_w/V_w for A_w and V_w and of $E_L - E_H$ for E_L and E_H did not lead to improved models. Similarly, substitution of various sums of Q_s , Q_H , Q_O and Q_N for Q_N did not improve the statistics.

In order to determine whether the fit of eq. (91) could be improved by non-linear transformations of the independent variables, the ACE technique of Breiman and Friedman was applied this method.

Yet another model was proposed for modeling $\log k_{on}$:

$$\log K_{on} = 66.4 (\pm 10.8) Q_N + 2.11 (\pm 0.41) E_L + 0.571 (\pm 0.085) A_X + 0.535 (\pm 0.150) A_Y' - 0.418 (\pm 0.087) D - 0.976 (\pm 0.227) \log P' + 11.11 \quad (92)$$

$$R^2 = 0.879, Q^2 = 0.732, Se = 0.634, F = 15.71, \alpha = 3 \times 10^{-5}, \text{ all } \alpha_i < 0.001 \text{ except } A_Y' = 0.0035$$

Similarly, the following model was proposed for $\log K_1$:

$$\log K_1 = - 61.0 (\pm 11.5) Q_N - 1.82 (\pm 0.43) E_L - 0.592 (\pm 0.091) A_X - 0.484 (\pm 0.166) A_Y' + 0.434 (\pm 0.093) D + 0.919 (\pm 0.242) \log P' - 8.41 \quad (92-A)$$

$$R^2 = 0.864, Q^2 = 0.677, Se = 0.678, F = 13.76, \alpha = 6 \times 10^{-5}, \text{ all } \alpha_i < 0.001 \text{ except } A_Y' = 0.012$$

Thus, the regression for log K_1 gives very similar result to log k_o , but with somewhat poorer statistics.

7.3.23. QSAR study of positively charged sulfonamide inhibitors

Supuran and Clare⁶¹ reported a QSAR study of positively charged sulfonamide inhibitors containing 28 carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, derivatives of tri-, tetra- and penta-substituted 1-(2-sulfonamido-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl) pyridinium perchlorates. Several of these derivatives are new compounds. The conclusion of the study was that action is greatly modulated by electronic effects on the pyridinium ring. The most significant effects were enhancement of activity with increased positive charge on this ring, weakening of activity with increasing HOMO energy, and a dependence on anisotropic polarizability which may be attributed to London forces. The following models were proposed for modeling log IC_{50} :

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & 7.66 (\pm 0.09) \times 10^{-3} D_{xx} \\ & + 19.4 (\pm 1.3) Q_O - 64.3 (\pm 8.7) S_m^E \\ & + 1.87 (\pm 0.16) E_{L-H} \\ & + 8.56 (\pm 0.2) Q_D + 12.99 \end{aligned} \quad (93)$$

$N = 28$, $R = 0.964$, $R^2_{CV} = 0.866$, $Se = 0.259$, $F = 57.4$

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & 1.09 (\pm 0.17) \times 10^{-2} P_{xx} \\ & - 1.76 (\pm 0.47) \times 10^{-2} P_{yy} \\ & + 1.38 (\pm 0.34) \times 10^{-2} P_{zz} \\ & + 27.7 (\pm 3.5) Q_O \\ & + 6.62 (\pm 1.87) Q_m \\ & - 1.92 (\pm 0.24) E_H - 19.2 \end{aligned} \quad (94)$$

$N = 28$, $R = 0.929$, $R^2_{CV} = 0.801$, $Se = 0.37$, $F = 22.1$

Both these eqs. (93) and (94) are very highly significant. The first is largely free from co-linearity problem, while the second one is borderline.

A third statistically highly significant model was proposed :

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & 9.82 (\pm 1.62) \times 10^{-3} P_{xx} \\ & + 0.188 (\pm 0.040) V_m - 4.13 (\pm 1.27) \pi_m \\ & + 14.1 (\pm 1.7) Q_O + 13.1 (\pm 2.9) Q_m \\ & + 2.06 (\pm 0.25) E_{L-H} - 11.64 \end{aligned} \quad (95)$$

$N = 28$, $R = 0.931$, $R^2_{CV} = 0.728$, $Se = 0.36$, $F = 22.7$

This was the only equation in which the substituent hydrophobicity and volume terms were significant at the

5% level. Supuran and Clare⁶¹ observed that in eq. (95) one compound was an outlier, the detection of which gave the following model :

$$\begin{aligned} \log IC_{50} = & 1.07 (\pm 0.12) \times 10^{-2} P_{xx} \\ & - 1.83 (\pm 0.33) \times 10^{-2} P_{yy} \\ & + 1.25 (\pm 0.25) \times 10^{-2} P_{zz} \\ & + 28.3 (\pm 2.5) Q_O + 6.42 (\pm 1.34) Q_m \\ & - 1.90 (\pm 0.17) E_H - 18.6 \end{aligned} \quad (96)$$

$N = 27$, $R = 0.964$, $R^2_{CV} = 0.886$, $Se = 0.26$, $F = 43.2$

It is not apparent why the detected compound is anomalous.

7.3.24. QSAR study using topological indices for inhibition of carbonic anhydrase II sulfanilamide and Schiff's bases

Balaban *et al.*⁹³ reported QSAR study using topological indices for inhibition of carbonic anhydrase II by sulfanilamide's and Schiff bases. The study involved with 29 benzene sulfonamides and 35 sulfanilamide Schiff bases. They have used two methodology involving ridge regression and the CODESSA program, and these results were those of previous studies. Good correlations were found for sulfanilamide's, and less satisfactory results for Schiff's bases when the number of molecular descriptors is kept below five.

(1) Results with CODESSA for sulfanilamide's

The CODESSA program⁹⁴ in that among hundreds of molecular descriptors that it computes, it selects the best correlations with the fewest given number of parameters. The two- and three-parameters used for modeling log K_C were found as below :

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_C = & - 0.277 (\pm 0.021) \text{Min}_{e-n} A_{c-s} \\ & + 67.43 (\pm 9.324) \text{Avg } V_C - 188.5 \end{aligned} \quad (97)$$

$N = 29$, $R = 0.927$, $Se = 0.549$, $F = 79.07$, $Q = 1.688$, $R^2 = 0.856$, $R^2_{CV} = 0.835$

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_C = & - 2.916 (\pm 0.252) J \\ & + 2.154 (\pm 0.170) \text{Min}_{n-n} R_{C-H} \\ & + 12.16 (\pm 0.724) \text{Avg } \beta_O - 48.4 \end{aligned} \quad (98)$$

$N = 29$, $R = 0.982$, $Se = 0.278$, $F = 230.3$, $Q = 3.532$, $R^2 = 0.965$, $R^2_{CV} = 0.950$

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_C = & 304.2 (\pm 64.80) \text{Max } 1-e_{R_O} \\ & - 3.096 (\pm 0.189) J \\ & + 2.916 (\pm 0.205) \text{Min}_{n-n} R_{C-H} \\ & + 12.2 (\pm 0.533) \text{Avg } \beta_O - 67.01 \end{aligned} \quad (99)$$

N = 29, R = 0.991, Se = 0.204, F = 323.5, Q = 48.56, R² = 0.982, R²_{CV} = 0.971

(2) Results with CODESSA for Schiff's bases

$$\log K (\text{CA II}) = -2.815 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 3.833 \times 10^{-4}) \text{ WM SA} + 0.331 (\pm 0.058) \text{ RPCS} + 0.269 \quad (100)$$

N = 35, R = 0.869, Se = 0.325, F = 49.45, Q = 2.673, R² = 0.756, R²_{CV} = 0.702

The three molecular descriptors for the same set yielded the following model :

$$\log K (\text{CA II}) = 8.075 (\pm 1.597) \text{ RNAB} - 5.345 \times 10^{-6} (\pm 7.336 \times 10^{-7}) \text{ GI} - 13.64 (\pm 3.977) \text{ MV/XYZB} + 2.203 \quad (101)$$

N = 35, R = 0.873, Se = 0.335, F = 33.26, Q = 2.606, R² = 0.763, R²_{CV} = 0.690

8.0. Heterocyclic sulfonamides inhibitors

Heterocyclic sulfonamides are very potent CA inhibitors⁹⁵⁻⁹⁸. A large number of such compounds was synthesized and tested towards CA isoenzymes⁹⁹⁻¹⁰¹ since the pioneering work of Roblians (Jr.)¹⁰² which reported these inhibitors in 1950s. QSAR study of some heterocyclic sulfonamide inhibitors are already discussed in the earlier section, the reason being they were included in the study of benzene sulfonamide inhibitors. It is worthy to mention again that although three 1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-sulfonamide derivatives were already included in the QSAR study of Kakeya *et al.*⁷⁰⁻⁷² this number was obviously insufficient for proposing a QSAR model for the whole class of heterocyclic sulfonamide inhibition.

8.1. QSAR study on 1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-sulfonamide

The first QSAR study on 1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-sulfonamide was reported by Kishida^{76,103} who employed LCAO (linear combination of atomic orbital), HMO and Hansch-Fujita method in their calculation, for a series of nine 1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-sulfonamide derivatives whose general structure is given below :

Fig. 1. General structure of 1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-sulfonamide.

Kishida⁷⁶ reported that electrophilic/nucleophilic super-delocalizability of atoms belonging to the SO₂NH₂ group are almost constant for the series of investigated

compounds, which means that the reactivity of this moiety is not the determining factor for the biological activity. On the other hand, the energy level of the HOMO was not correlated, whereas, that of the LUMO was highly correlated (R = 0.9439), which implies that inhibitors act as electron acceptors in their interactions with CA as that a positively charged atom plays a key role in this interaction. This atom was found to be the exocyclic nitrogen from position 5. By considering the net charge of this atom, Q_N and the hydrophobicities of substituent from position 5, π the following equation was proposed :

$$-pI_{50} = -1.7313 + 6.3877 Q'_N + 0.1393 \pi \quad (102)$$

N = 9, R = 0.9438, F_{2,6} = 24.46

The above eq. (102) suggests that groups from the 5-position of the heterocyclic ring interact both hydrophobically as well as electro statistically with amino acid residues in the CA active site, which is consistent with crystallographic data of different adducts of CA with heterocyclic sulfonamides¹⁰⁹.

8.2. QSAR study on acetazolamide

Kishida group^{76,103} using the CNDO/2 (Complete neglect of differential overlap) method calculated the interaction energies of acetazolamide and some of its congeners with several histidine residues from the CA active site, pointing out that the 5-acylamido substituents contribute to the stabilization of enzyme inhibitors complexes by means of electronic and hydrophobic interactions.

Fig. 2. Structure of acetazolamide.

8.3. QSAR study on thiophene, 1,3-thiazole and 1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives

Vedani and Mayer (Jr.)¹⁰⁴ examined some thiophene 1,3-thiazole and 1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives by means of their interactive molecular graphic molecular modeling method. This study showed that the water bound within the enzyme active site participated in stabilization of E-I complexes due to its interaction with different atoms from the inhibitor molecule.

8.4. QSAR study by De-Benedetti's group

Some much documented QSAR studies for heterocyclic sulfonamides were reported by Menziani and De-Benedetti¹⁰⁵. Different MO indices were calculated for a series of 30 heterocyclic sulfonides derivative of 1,3,4-

thiadiazole, 1,3-thiazole and thiophene-sulfonamides :

Fig. 3. General structure of heterocyclic sulfonamides in the QSAR calculation by Menziani and De-Benedetti's group.

The best correlation obtained for these inhibitors are mentioned below :

$$(i) \log II_{50} = 37.84 q_{SO_2NH_2} + 8.78 \quad (103)$$

$$N = 28, Se = 0.304, R = 0.909$$

$$(ii) \log II_{50} = 119.74 q_O + 64.73 \quad (104)$$

$$N = 28, Se = 0.364, R = 0.899$$

$$(iii) \log II_{50} = 113.62 q_{NH_2} + 6.87 \quad (105)$$

$$N = 28, Se = 0.496, R = 0.80$$

Here, q represents the total net charge ($\sigma + \pi$) of the oxygen atom (q_O), the NH_2 moiety (q_{NH_2}) and the SO_2NH_2 moiety ($q_{SO_2NH_2}$) respectively.

Improved correlations could not be obtained by multiple regressions with different combinations of the orthogonal MO indices used, and, unfortunately, hydrophobic parameters were not included in the model. Any now, this valuable study stresses the primary role of the SO_2NH_2 moiety in determining the CA inhibitory properties of such derivatives.

Binding energies to the enzyme were also calculated¹⁰⁵ for seven 1,3,4-thiadiazole sulfonamides, but a QSAR equation was not proposed, presumably due to the small number of derivatives included in the study. The conclusions of such QSAR studies on heterocyclic sulfonamides were in fact very similar to those obtained for the aromatic sulfonamides previously mentioned, and studied by this group¹⁰⁵, i.e. the dominant term responsible for the variation in binding energies of the inhibitors to enzyme, is the van der Waals (E_{vdw}) and not the electrostatic one.

8.5. QSAR study on 2-substituted 1,3,4-thiadiazole-5-sulfonamides

Menziani and De-Benedetti¹⁰⁵ reported a QSAR study on 12 2-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazole-5-sulfonamides based on quantum chemical indices, calculated by the AM1 method.

Fig. 4. General structure of compounds included in the QSAR study of Menziani and De-Benedetti.

These authors have also calculated binding energies to CA by molecular mechanics using the AMISER force field. A good correlation ship was obtained between the enzyme inhibition index ($\log II_{50}$, defined as the concentration needed to retard the hydrolysis reaction by 50%, relative to unsubstituted compound), and the calculated binding charge. The following models were proposed :

$$\log II_{50} = -0.199 BE - 4.84 \quad (106)$$

$$N = 12, Se = 0.22, R = 0.96$$

The binding charge was then correlated to quantum chemical indices according to the following relationships :

$$BE = 45.4 E_{HOMO} + 212.8 \quad (107)$$

$$N = 11, Se = 1.116, R = 0.88$$

$$BE = -547 q_{SO_2NH} - 318.9 \quad (108)$$

$$N = 11, Se = 1.32, R = 0.92$$

Relationships were also obtained with the sum of absolute charges on atoms of the substituents R, and the nucleophilic super delocalizability of the HOMO on the sulfonamide nitrogen. These relationships were interpreted as indicating that binding is enhanced by decreasing the nucleophilic reactivity of the SO_2NH^- group. A limitation of this approach is that although the molecular mechanics BE term would account for electrostatic and dispersion forces, it may miss more stable electronic effects, which would then be lost to the QSAR.

Menziani and DeBenedetti¹⁰⁵ using a similar molecular modeling approach showed the consistency of the QSAR's for 16 benzene sulfonamides and the same in heterocyclic sulfonamides by combining in the same QSAR both classes of compounds, using as a descriptor the BE and an indicator variable I, which was zero for heterocyclic and unity for the benzene sulfonamides. The model obtained was as below :

$$\log II_{50} = -0.181 BE - 2.12 I - 4.18 \quad (109)$$

$$N = 28, Se = 0.199, R = 0.982$$

This has lost nothing compared with eq. (109) and indicates that thiadiazoles are uniformly 132 times more active than benzene sulfonamides, and that their activity is modulated by substituents in the same way.

8.6. Kishida QSAR

Kishida and co-workers^{76,103} observed that in heterocyclic sulfonamides have the general structures presented in the above figure. The charges of the exocyclic nitrogen attached to the 5-position of the ring and the hydrophobic property of the whole NR_1R_2 group at this position were also found to control CA inhibition potency

according to the following eq. (110) :

$$\log II_{50} = 6.3877 Q_x + 0.1393 \pi - 1.7353 \quad (110)$$

$$N = 9, R = 0.948, F = 24.56$$

This eq. (95) suggests that while the nitrogen at 5-substituent may have the electrostatic interaction with some site in the CA, the NR₁R₂ group as a whole might participate in the hydrophobic interaction with a particular segment of the same site.

The QSAR studies on heterocyclic sulfonamides made by Supuran and Clare group are already discussed in the earlier section.

8.7. Aliphatic sulfonamides

In case of aliphatic sulfonamides, the generally accepted idea was that they are very poor CA inhibitors¹⁰⁶. Maren and Conny¹⁰⁷ showed that strong CA inhibitors can be designed and obtained from the class of sulfonamides also. However, it has been shown that aliphatic sulfonamides can also be developed as strong CA inhibitor¹⁰⁸ and for a small series aliphatic sulfonamides as shown in following figure showed an excellent linear correlation with pK_a and pK_i values of the aliphatic sulfonamides¹⁰⁹.

Fig. 5. General structure of aliphatic sulfonamides.

Here, R is substituted or unsubstituted alkyl group, such as CF₃, C₂F₅, C₄F₉, FCH₂, CF₃CH₂, ClCH₂, CH₃ and CHF₂.

Gupta *et al.*¹¹⁶ reported a QSAR study on a series of sulfonylated amino acid hydroxane. They have used Kier and Hall first-order valence connectivity for proposing their QSAR model and the electro topological state (E-state) index of some atoms. The proposed models were found as below :

For CA I

$$\log (1/K_i) = 5.755 - 0.177 (\pm 0.060) {}^1\chi^v$$

$$- 0.335 (\pm 0.103) S_S + 0.513 (\pm 0.166) S_N$$

$$+ 0.427 (\pm 0.121) I \quad (111)$$

$$N = 23, Se = 0.13, R = 0.969, F = 68.89$$

For CA II

$$\log (1/K_i) = 5.065 - 0.089 (\pm 0.087) {}^1\chi^v$$

$$- 0.353 (\pm 0.128) S_S + 0.597 (\pm 0.209) S_N$$

$$+ 0.364 (\pm 0.076) I \quad (112)$$

$$N = 28, Se = 0.19, R = 0.920, F = 31.55$$

For CA IV

$$\log (1/K_i) = 6.580 - 0.158 (\pm 0.038) {}^1\chi^v$$

$$- 0.231 (\pm 0.062) S_S + 0.338 (\pm 0.101) S_N$$

$$+ 0.364 (\pm 0.076) I \quad (113)$$

$$N = 23, Se = 0.09, R = 0.978, F = 124.24$$

From the QSAR models discussed so far we observed that there is only one case of Gupta group¹¹², in that topological indices are used. Below we give an exhaustive review of QSAR modeling, in that topological indices are used. Balaban, Supuran, Clare and Khadikar are responsible for such topological indices oriented QSAR modeling of carbonic anhydrase inhibition.

9.0 QSAR study on carbonic anhydrase inhibition using topological indices

In this section we will discuss the use of distance-based and connectivity type indices in developing quantitative structure-activity relationships for modeling carbonic anhydrase inhibition.

9.1. QSAR study on sulfonamide Schiff's bases inhibitors of CA using Wiener index

It was probably for the first time in 1999 Saxena and Khadikar¹¹¹ have used topological indices in QSAR study on sulfanilamide Schiff's base inhibitors of carbonic anhydrase CA I and CA II. The activities of these compounds were correlated with the Wiener index W¹¹² and the data were subjected to a classical regression analysis with due care to avoid the possibility of chance correlation or co-linearity. The results have shown that W index is quite successful in modeling the activities of sulfonamide Schiff's bases. Using classical regression analysis, Khadikar and Saxena¹¹² observed that W index alone is incapable of modeling both CA I and CA II inhibitors, however, excellent results are obtained by splitting the data set into three to four categories.

9.2. QSAR studies on some antimalarial sulfonamides using Wiener (W) and Szeged (Sz) indices

Khadikar and co-workers have reported an interesting QSAR study on some antimalarial sulfonamides using W¹⁰⁹ and Sz¹¹³⁻¹¹⁷ indices. They observed that in multiparametric regression better results are obtained showing that W index gave slightly better results than those in which Sz index is involved. However, the statistics of the pro-

posed models were not that excellent. It is worthy to mention that they have used indicator parameters in proposing their QSAR models.

9.3. QSAR studies on ureido and thiouredo derivatives of aromatic/heterocyclic sulfonamides using distance-based and connectivity type indices

Khadikar *et al.*¹²³ reported QSAR studies on carbonic anhydrase (h CA I) for a series of ureido and thiouredo derivatives using distance-based (W, Sz, B, J) and connecting type ($^0\chi^v$, $^1\chi^v$) topological indices. An excellent model reported by them is the hexaparametric model containing W, Sz, B, J, IP₁ and IP₂. This model contained highly correlations W and Sz indices. Their inclusion in the model is justified by Randić¹²⁴ recommendations. This model is found as below :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pK}_i = & -0.0037 (\pm 0.0012) W \\ & + 0.0034 (\pm 7.8340 \times 10^{-4}) Sz \\ & - 0.4551 (\pm 0.1326) B \\ & + 1.3288 (\pm 0.1358) J \\ & + 0.5425 (\pm 0.2399) IP_1 \\ & + 1.3799 (\pm 0.1139) IP_2 - 2.643 \end{aligned} \quad (114)$$

$$N = 39, Se = 0.3235, R = 0.9401, F = 40.559, Q = 2.9067$$

The opposite signs of the coefficients of W and Sz were attributed to their high co-linearity.

9.4. QSAR study on antitumor activity of sulphonamide analogs of oncolytic sulphonylureas using Wiener index (W)

Khadikar *et al.*¹¹⁹ proposed a QSAR model for the estimation of antitumor activity of sulfonamide anchors of oncolytic sulphonylurea urea. The model obtained is as below :

$$\begin{aligned} \% \text{ inhibition (antitumor activity)} = \\ - 0.0627 W + 183.3278 \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 26, R = -0.7988$$

9.5. QSAR study on sulfanilamide Schiff's bases

Khadikar *et al.*¹²⁰ has reported QSAR study on sulfanilamide Schiff's base inhibition of carbonic anhydrase using distance-based topological indices. The regression analysis of the data had shown that the activities of the compounds used in the inhibition of CA II can be modeled in multiparametric model in that some indicator parameters are also involved. The following six models were proposed.

$$\begin{aligned} (1) \log K (\text{CA II}) = & -2.3666 (\pm 0.7414) J \\ & - 0.8239 (\pm 0.7520) I_1 + 4.8475 \end{aligned} \quad (115)$$

$$N = 35, Se = 0.3664, R = 0.8418, F = 38.917, Q = 2.2975$$

$$\begin{aligned} (2) \log K (\text{CA II}) = & -2.037 (\pm 0.6942) J \\ & - 0.7225 (\pm 0.1145) I_1 \\ & + 0.3903 (\pm 0.1150) I_2 + 4.1609 \end{aligned} \quad (116)$$

$$N = 35, Se = 0.3373, R = 0.8722, F = 32.802, Q = 2.5838$$

$$\begin{aligned} (3) \log K (\text{CA II}) = & -1.7274 (\pm 0.6732) J \\ & + 7.6428 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 3.5770 \times 10^{-4}) \log RB \\ & + 1.0357 (\pm 0.2009) I_1 \\ & + 0.4017 (\pm 0.1423) I_2 + 3.4374 \end{aligned} \quad (117)$$

$$N = 35, Se = 0.3194, R = 0.8902, F = 30.719, Q = 3.2289$$

$$\begin{aligned} (4) \log K (\text{CA II}) = & -0.0199 (\pm 0.0041) W \\ & - 1.7587 (\pm 0.5086) MRI \\ & + 0.0315 (\pm 0.0081) \log RB \\ & + 1.2527 (\pm 0.2211) I_1 + 0.8889 \end{aligned} \quad (118)$$

$$N = 35, Se = 0.2841, R = 0.9172, F = 30.719, Q = 3.7119$$

$$\begin{aligned} (5) \log K (\text{CA II}) = & -0.0197 (\pm 0.0038) W \\ & - 0.1201 (\pm 0.0490) ^1\chi^v \\ & - 1.5152 (\pm 0.4758) MRI \\ & + 0.0076 (\pm 0.0015) Sz \\ & + 0.0328 (\pm 0.0074) \log RB \\ & + 1.2420 (\pm 0.2027) I_1 + 1.3627 \end{aligned} \quad (119)$$

$$N = 35, Se = 0.2604, R = 0.9334, F = 31.564, Q = 3.5645$$

$$\begin{aligned} (6) \log K (\text{CA II}) = & -0.0213 (\pm 0.0039) W \\ & - 0.1107 (\pm 0.0469) ^1\chi^v \\ & - 0.2488 (\pm 0.1844) ^1\chi \\ & - 1.3641 (\pm 0.4821) MRI \\ & + 0.0076 (\pm 0.0015) Sz \\ & + 0.0411 (\pm 0.0096) \log RB \\ & + 1.2435 (\pm 0.1995) I_1 + 2.8538 \end{aligned} \quad (120)$$

$$N = 35, Se = 0.2567, R = 0.9377, F = 28.107, Q = 3.6529$$

9.6. QSAR study on CA inhibitor activity of disulfonamides (effect of halogen substitution)

QSAR study on CA inhibitory activity ($\log IC_{50}$) of disulfonamides using a large series of distance-based to-

pological indices was proposed by Khadikar and co-workers¹²¹. This is the first report; in that Padmakar-Ivan index¹²²⁻¹²⁷ was used for modeling CA inhibitory activity of disulfonamides. They discussed the effect due to halogen substitution nearer (*ortho*-position) to SO₂NH₂ groups. The results have shown that halogen substitution at R₃ has pronounced effect on the inhibitory activity.

Fig. 6. General structure of disulfonamides with halogen substitution at R₁, R₂ and R₃.

The following seven models were proposed :

$$(1) \log IC_{50} = 0.0300 (\pm 0.0038) PI - 0.7564 \quad (121)$$

$$N = 10, Se = 0.2623, R = -0.9416, F = 262.26, Q = 3.9848$$

$$(2) \log IC_{50} = -0.0361 (\pm 0.0035) PI + 0.3993 (\pm 0.1410) I_2 + 0.4214 \quad (122)$$

$$N = 10, Se = 0.1725, R = 0.9732, F = 62.7274, Q = 5.6414$$

$$(3) \log IC_{50} = -0.0131 (\pm 0.0039) PI - 4.3617 \quad (123)$$

$$N = 10, Se = 0.3631, R = -0.7625, F = 29.664, Q = 2.0100$$

$$(4) \log IC_{50} = -1.1839 (\pm 0.1803) {}^2\chi + 2.4023 \quad (124)$$

$$N = 10, Se = 0.2221, R = -0.9184, F = 183.85, Q = 4.1351$$

$$(5) \log IC_{50} = 1.1664 (\pm 0.1653) {}^2\chi - 0.2105 (\pm 0.1314) I_1 + 2.3403 \quad (125)$$

$$N = 10, Se = 0.2030, R = 0.9410, F = 27.0014, Q = 4.6355$$

$$(6) \log IC_{50} = -0.1593 (\pm 0.1073) {}^1\chi - 1.4757 (\pm 0.1593) I_2 + 5.0107 \quad (126)$$

$$N = 10, Se = 0.1121, R = 0.9823, F = 96.8257, Q = 8.7636$$

$$(7) \log IC_{50} = 11.4514 (\pm 1.7713) {}^1\chi - 0.1874 (\pm 0.0299) PI + 0.2918 (\pm 0.1635) I_2 - 44.5088 \quad (127)$$

$$N = 21, Se = 0.2917, R = 0.8814, F = 19.2759, Q = 3.0216$$

9.7. QSAR study on inhibition of tumor associated isoenzymes IX with aromatic heterocyclic sulfonamides

QSAR study on the tumor-associated transmembrane carbonic anhydrase IX (CA IX) isoenzyme was made by Khadikar and Supuran and co-workers¹²⁸ using a large pool of distance-based topological indices – W, Sz, PI, ⁰χ, ¹χ, ²χ, ⁰χ^v, ¹χ^v, ²χ^v. A combined set of 32 aromatic and heterocyclic compounds, including the six clinically used derivatives, acetazolamide, methazolamide, ethoxzolamide, dichlorophenamide, dorzolamide and brinzolamide were used for proposing the QSAR models. The results have shown that the inhibition of the tumor-associated isoenzyme with aromatic and heterocyclic sulfonamides can be modeled excellently in multiparametric regression after introduction of indicator parameters. The predictive power of the proposed models was discussed using probable error of coefficient (PE), variance inflation factor (VIF) and cross-validated parameters. The following five models were proposed :

$$(1) \log K_1 (\text{h CA IX}) = 2.3551 - 0.1223 (\pm 0.0287) {}^2\chi + 0.4905 (\pm 0.1122) I_3 \quad (128)$$

$$N = 32, Se = 0.3085, R = 0.7150, R^2_A = 0.4775, F = 15.1629, Q = 2.3176$$

$$(2) \log K_1 (\text{h CA IX}) = 2.6141 - 0.3804 (\pm 0.1258) {}^1\chi + 0.5025 (\pm 0.2425) {}^2\chi^v + 0.4879 (\pm 0.1070) I_3 \quad (129)$$

$$N = 32, Se = 0.2955, R = 0.7529, R^2_A = 0.5204, F = 12.2176, Q = 2.5478$$

$$(3) \log K_1 (\text{h CA IX}) = 2.4664 - 0.3643 (\pm 0.1193) {}^1\chi + 0.5092 (\pm 0.2291) {}^2\chi^v + 0.2962 (\pm 0.1434) I_2 + 0.3930 (\pm 0.1112) I_3 \quad (130)$$

$$N = 32, Se = 0.2796, R = 0.7933, R^2_A = 0.5707, F = 11.2545, Q = 2.8372$$

$$(4) \log K_1 (\text{h CA IX}) = 3.7804 - 0.7091 (\pm 0.3046) {}^1\chi + 0.5123 (\pm 0.2270) {}^2\chi^v + 0.00462 (\pm 0.0038) I_1 + 0.3119 (\pm 0.1427) I_2 + 0.3520 (\pm 0.1151) I_3 \quad (131)$$

N = 32, Se = 0.2770, R = 0.8040, $R^2_A = 0.5785$, F = 9.5077, Q = 2.9025

$$(5) \log K_1 (\text{h CA IX}) = 3.9171 \\ - 0.5583 (\pm 0.3274) {}^1\chi \\ + 0.1447 (\pm 0.1212) {}^2\chi \\ + 0.4171 (\pm 0.2403) {}^2\chi^v \\ + 0.0053 (\pm 0.0038) \text{PI} \\ + 0.3771 (\pm 0.15717) I_2 \\ + 0.3480 (\pm 0.1142) I_3 \quad (132)$$

N = 32, Se = 0.2741, R = 0.8158, $R^2_A = 0.5852$, F = 8.2903, Q = 2.9687

9.8. QSAR study on aromatic and heterocyclic sulfonamides containing 8-quinoline-sulfonyl moieties, with topical activity as antiglaucoma agents using first-order valency connectivity index (${}^1\chi^v$)

Khadikar and co-workers¹²⁹ reported QSAR study on aromatic/heterocyclic sulfonamides containing 8-quinoline-sulfonyl CA inhibitors using Kier and Hall^{130,131} first-order valence connectivity index ${}^1\chi^v$ ¹³². Excellent results are obtained against all the three isozymes, CA I, CA II and CA IV of the zinc enzyme CA. They observed that indicator parameters need to be added in modeling for obtaining excellent results. The following models were proposed :

(1) Modeling of log (h CA I)

$$\log K_1 (\text{h CA I}) = - 0.2435 (\pm 0.0334) {}^1\chi^v \\ - 0.8008 (\pm 0.1736) I_2 \\ - 2.0818 (\pm 0.1703) I_3 + 5.3835 \quad (133)$$

N = 41, Se = 0.4546, R = 0.9251, F = 73.224, Q = 2.0350

(2) Modeling of log K_i (h CA II)

$$\log K_1 (\text{h CA II}) = - 0.0661 (\pm 0.0164) {}^1\chi^v \\ - 0.5308 (\pm 0.0820) I_2 \\ - 1.4832 (\pm 0.0810) I_3 + 2.5489 \quad (134)$$

N = 41, Se = 0.2148, R = 0.9551, F = 128.057, Q = 4.4405

(3) Modeling of K_i (b CA IV)

$$\log K_1 (\text{h CA IV}) = - 0.1608 (\pm 0.0216) {}^1\chi^v \\ - 0.7079 (\pm 0.1093) I_2 \\ - 1.3426 (\pm 0.1070) I_3 + 3.5781 \quad (135)$$

N = 41, Se = 0.2862, R = 0.9307, F = 79.787, Q = 3.2519

9.9. Topological modeling of lipophilicity, diuretic activity and CA I activity of benzene sulfonamide using molecular connectivity

Khadikar and co-workers¹²⁹ proposed QSAR models for modeling lipophilicity, diuretic activity and carbonic anhydrase inhibition activity of benzene sulfonamide using molecular connectivity indices. Initially, they have used a large series of distance-based topological indices. Their results showed that the topological approach used by them were quite useful for modeling carbonic anhydrase inhibition and that the use of molecular connectivity was the best for this purpose. Excellent results were obtained in multiparametric regression. The results obtained are given below :

(1) Modeling of lipophilicity (log P)

$$\log P = 0.8905 - 1.1348 (\pm 0.059) {}^0\chi \\ + 0.7658 (\pm 0.1207) \pi \quad (136)$$

N = 16, Se = 0.2982, R = 0.8697, $R^2_A = 0.7190$, F = 43.4713

(2) Modeling of diuretic activity (log I/C)

$$\log I/C = - 0.2279 - 0.4200 (\pm 0.0943) \sigma \quad (137)$$

N = 16, Se = 0.2129, R = 0.7657, F = 19.8409

(3) Modeling of carbonic anhydrase inhibition (log K_i)

The following two models were proposed for modeling carbonic inhibition activity (log K_i) using benzene sulfonamides :

$$(i) \log K_i = 2.9766 + 0.4727 (\pm 0.1191) {}^2\chi \quad (138)$$

N = 16, Se = 0.4401, R = 0.7277, F = 15.7580

$$(ii) \log K_i = 4.5778 + 0.1593 (\pm 0.0852) {}^1\chi \\ + 0.5928 (\pm 0.1240) \sigma + 0.3306 (\pm 0.0828) \pi \quad (139)$$

N = 16, Se = 0.1725, R = 0.9655, $R^2_A = 0.9226$

9.10. QSAR studies of benzene sulfonamides : Modeling of binding constants of sulfonamides to human CA-II

The binding constants (log K) of benzene sulfonamide to human CA II were modeled by Khadikar¹³² using a large series of distance-based topological indices. They have also investigated the need or otherwise of the hydrophobic parameter (log P) for such topological modeling of log K. In both the cases excellent results were obtained. In multiparametric models involving indicator parameters they observe that introduction of hydrophobic parameter (log P) yielded improved statistics. The following results were obtained.

9.11. Models without involvement of log P

Following three models were proposed, in that log P was not present as the correlating parameter :

$$(1) \log K = 2.1443 + 0.4220 (\pm 0.023) {}^0\chi^v + 2.4495 (\pm 0.1959) I_1 \quad (140)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.5010, R = 0.9394, R^2_A = 0.8735, F = 97.0066, Q = 1.8751$$

$$(2) \log K = 3.5111 - 0.0216 (\pm 0.0084) W + 0.0200 (\pm 0.0069) Sz + 1.9486 (\pm 0.2289) I_1 \quad (141)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.4545, R = 0.9488, R^2_A = 0.8866, F = 73.942, Q = 1.9979$$

$$(3) \log K = 1.9828 - 0.0238 (\pm 0.00813) W + 0.0199 (\pm 0.0066) Sz + 0.8407 (\pm 0.4450) {}^2\chi^v + 1.9132 (\pm 0.2190) I_1 \quad (142)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.4525, R = 0.9548, R^2_A = 0.8968, F = 61.855, Q = 2.1100$$

9.12. Models containing log P as one of the correlating parameters

In this case also three models were suggested, one of which contained log P and an indicator parameter I.

$$(1) \log K = 4.8259 + 0.6748 (\pm 0.0979) \log P + 2.4335 (\pm 0.1937) I \quad (143)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.4955, R = 0.9408, R^2_A = 0.8763, F = 100.197, Q = 1.8987$$

$$(2) \log K = 2.2096 + 0.4347 (\pm 0.0987) \log P + 0.4226 (\pm 0.1060) {}^2\chi + 2.5167 (\pm 0.1559) I_1 \quad (144)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.3952, R = 0.9642, R^2_A = 0.9213, F = 110.276, Q = 2.4400$$

$$(3) \log K = 1.6434 + 0.4033 (\pm 0.0546) \log P + 0.4350 (\pm 0.0585) {}^2\chi + 3.0451 (\pm 0.1104) I_1 + 1.0549 (\pm 0.1383) I_2 \quad (145)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.2180, R = 0.9897, R^2_A = 0.9761, F = 286.500, Q = 4.5400$$

10.0. QSAR study on water-soluble sulfonamides incorporating β -alanyl moieties using molecular connectivity indices

Khadikar and co-workers¹³³ reported a QSAR study on a series of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, more precisely on water-soluble sulfonamides incorporating β -

alanyl moieties, possessing long lasting intra-ocular pressure lowering properties. In this study also they have used a long series of distance-based topological indices. The regression analysis has shown that out of the pool of topological indices used, ${}^1\chi$ (first-order Randic connectivity indices) is the best one for modeling CA inhibitory properties against all the three investigated isozymes, the cytosolic CA I and CA II and the membrane-bound CA IV. Here also excellent results are obtained in multiparametric modeling. Following models were proposed :

10.1. Modeling of log K₁ (hCA I)

Following five models were proposed for modeling log K₁ (hCA I)

$$(1) \log K_1 (\text{hCA I}) = 6.4759 - 0.4563 (\pm 0.0588) {}^1\chi \quad (146)$$

$$N = 49, Se = 0.7814, R = -0.7664, F = 66.885$$

$$(2) \log K_1 (\text{hCA I}) = 6.5421 - 0.4148 (\pm 0.0377) {}^1\chi - 1.2582 (\pm 0.1636) I_2 \quad (147)$$

$$N = 49, Se = 0.5225, R = 0.9052, F = 104.363$$

$$(3) \log K_1 (\text{hCA I}) = 6.7621 - 0.4239 (\pm 0.0361) {}^1\chi - 0.4307 (\pm 0.1795) I_1 - 1.4046 (\pm 0.1673) I_2 \quad (148)$$

$$N = 49, Se = 0.4974, R = 0.9165, F = 78.695$$

$$(4) \log K_1 (\text{hCA I}) = 3.7166 - 0.3551 (\pm 0.0330) {}^1\chi + 1.1389 (\pm 0.2402) I - 0.8425 (\pm 0.1713) I_1 - 1.2586 (\pm 0.1410) I_2 \quad (149)$$

$$N = 49, Se = 0.4092, R = 0.9455, F = 92.817$$

$$(5) \log K_1 (\text{hCA I}) = 4.0181 - 0.3617 (\pm 0.0323) {}^1\chi + 1.0254 (\pm 0.2407) J - 0.8013 (\pm 0.1678) I_1 - 1.3744 (\pm 0.1498) I_2 + 0.5054 (\pm 0.2647) I_3 \quad (150)$$

$$N = 49, Se = 0.3974, R = 0.9499, F = 79.447$$

10.2. Modeling of log K₁ (hCA II)

In this case two models were proposed for modeling log K₁ (hCA II)

$$(1) \log K_1 (\text{hCA II}) = 2.2447 - 0.1593 (\pm 0.0219) {}^1\chi + 0.3728 (\pm 0.1656) J - 0.5423 (\pm 0.1140) I_1 - 0.9305 (\pm 0.1018) I_2 + 0.1013 (\pm 0.1799) I_3 \quad (151)$$

N = 49, Se = 0.2700, R = 0.9166, R²_A = 0.8215, F = 45.152

$$(2) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = 2.1843 - 0.1580 (\pm 0.0216) {}^1\chi^v + 0.3955 (\pm 0.1523) I_1 - 0.5805 (\pm 0.1122) I_2 - 0.9073 (\pm 0.0928) I_3 \quad (152)$$

N = 49, Se = 0.2679, R = 0.9159, R²_A = 0.8242, F = 57.275

10.3. Modeling of K_i (hCA IV)

Only one model was proposed for modeling log K_i (hCA IV)

$$\log K_i (\text{hCA IV}) = 2.7452 - 0.1811 (\pm 0.0250) {}^1\chi^v + 0.5123 (\pm 0.1866) J - 0.8039 (\pm 0.1300) I_1 - 0.9189 (\pm 0.1161) I_2 + 0.2796 (\pm 0.2052) \quad (153)$$

N = 49, Se = 0.3080, R = 0.9077, R²_A = 0.8034, F = 40.223

11.0. QSAR study on topically acting sulfonamides incorporating GABA moieties : A molecular connectivity approach

Khadikar and Supuran group¹³⁴ have reported a QSAR study on topically acting sulfonamides incorporating GABA moiety using first-order valence connectivity index, ¹χ^v. The inhibitory activity against three isozymes CA I, CA II (cystolic forms) and CA IV (membrane bound form) were considered for this purpose). All the three activities were excellently modeled by ¹χ^v in multiparametric regression containing indicator parameter. The models obtained were found as below :

11.1. Modeling log K_i (hCA I)

The following two models were proposed for modeling log K_i (hCA I)

$$(1) \log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = - 0.4434 (\pm 0.0425) {}^1\chi^v - 1.2086 (\pm 0.1703) I_3 + 6.4391$$

N = 50, Se = 0.5500, R = 0.8987, F = 98.708, Q = 1.6340

$$(2) \log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = - 0.4869 (\pm 0.0523) {}^1\chi^v + 0.2686 (\pm 0.1912) I_1 - 1.1730 (\pm 0.1705) I_3 \quad (154)$$

N = 50, Se = 0.5444, R = 0.9031, F = 67.824, Q = 1.6589

11.2. Modeling of log K_i (hCA II)

$$\log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = - 0.1593 (\pm 0.0188) {}^1\chi^v - 0.4052 (\pm 0.0940) I_2 + 0.8649 (\pm 0.0907) I_3 + 3.0080 \quad (155)$$

N = 48, Se = 0.2542, R = 0.9226, F = 53.853, Q = 3.6295

11.3. Modeling of log K_i (hCA IV)

$$\log K_i (\text{hCA IV}) = - 0.2309 (\pm 0.0281) {}^1\chi^v - 0.4644 (\pm 0.1303) I_2 - 0.8581 (\pm 0.1218) I_3 \quad (156)$$

N = 50, Se = 0.3629, R = 0.8730, F = 49.134, Q = 2.4

12.0. QSAR study of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors using Balaban and Balaban type indices

In this section we now discuss the cases of QSAR study in that the carbonic anhydrase inhibition is modeled using Balaban and Balaban type indices.

12.1. Supramolecular complexing ability vis-à-vis estimation of pK_a of substituted sulfonamides : Dominating role of Balaban index

Balaban, Khadikar and Supuran group⁴⁸ have reported QSAR study on supra molecular complexing ability vis-à-vis estimation of pK_a of substituted sulfonamides, in that Balaban index; J⁴⁹ played a dominating role. In addition to other distance-based topological indices, this group had also used Balaban and Balaban type indices (J₁, J_m, J_v, J_c, J_e and J_p). The results have shown that the most discriminating Balaban index (J) combined with indicator parameters yielded excellent models. The results obtained also established the superiority of J index over other Balaban type indices. The statistics is improved when one of the indicator parameters was replaced by molar volume (MV). The sulfonamides used by them have the following general formula :

Fig. 7. General formula of the sulfonamides used.

Following 8 models were proposed to model pK_a

$$(1) \text{pK}_a = 7.0112 (\pm 3.3571) J \\ - 1.2754 (\pm 0.173) {}^1\chi \\ + 1.3806 (\pm 0.1992) I_Y \\ + 1.1750 (\pm 0.3064) I_N + 6.1992 \quad (157)$$

$$N = 43, \text{Se} = 0.5395, R = 0.8822, R^2_A = 0.7549, \\ F = 33.337, Q = 1.64$$

$$(2) \text{pK}_a = 10.9771 (\pm 2.3387) J \\ - 0.9651 (\pm 0.1253) {}^1\chi \\ + 0.6959 (\pm 0.1678) I_Y \\ + 2.1750 (\pm 0.2535) I_N \\ - 26.8775 (\pm 3.9361) \eta + 40.2072 \quad (158)$$

$$N = 43, \text{Se} = 0.3775, R = 0.9695, R^2_A = 0.8884, \\ F = 67.802, Q = 2.52$$

$$(3) \text{pK}_a = 14.3950 (\pm 1.9047) J \\ - 1.3058 (\pm 0.1170) {}^1\chi \\ + 0.0472 (\pm 0.0066) MV \\ + 2.7078 (\pm 0.1750) I_N \\ - 32.7892 (\pm 2.5299) \eta + 37.5052 \quad (159)$$

$$N = 43, \text{Se} = 0.2961, R = 0.9693, R^2_A = 0.9313, \\ F = 114.939, Q = 3.27$$

$$(4) \text{pK}_a = 5.9591 (\pm 1.8458) J_z \\ - 0.6349 (\pm 0.2032) {}^1\chi \\ + 0.0372 (\pm 0.0090) MV \\ + 3.0883 (\pm 0.2904) I_N \\ - 36.5252 (\pm 4.3535) \eta + 48.0876 \quad (160)$$

$$N = 43, \text{Se} = 0.4172, R = 0.9380, R^2_A = 0.8637, \\ F = 54.225, Q = 2.25$$

$$(5) \text{pK}_a = 5.9591 (\pm 1.8458) J_z \\ - 0.6349 (\pm 0.2032) {}^1\chi \\ + 0.0372 (\pm 0.0090) MV \\ + 3.0883 (\pm 0.2904) I_N \\ - 36.5252 (\pm 4.3535) \eta + 48.0876 \quad (161)$$

$$N = 43, \text{Se} = 0.4172, R = 0.9380, R^2_A = 0.8637, \\ F = 54.225, Q = 2.25$$

$$(6) \text{pK}_a = 0.3768 (\pm 0.5861) J_v \\ - 1.0205 (\pm 0.1809) {}^1\chi \\ + 0.0341 (\pm 0.0105) MV \\ + 2.5832 (\pm 0.2766) I_N \\ - 28.4378 (\pm 3.9560) \eta + 56.2534 \quad (162)$$

$$N = 43, \text{Se} = 0.4697, R = 0.9208, R^2_A = 0.8272, \\ F = 41.223, Q = 1.960$$

$$(7) \text{pK}_a = 11.4858 (\pm 4.2230) J_e \\ - 1.4668 (\pm 0.2254) {}^1\chi \\ + 0.0521 (\pm 0.0115) MV \\ + 2.9460 (\pm 0.2859) I_N \\ - 3.5051 (\pm 4.1097) \eta \quad (163)$$

$$N = 43, \text{Se} = 0.4312, R = 0.9337, R^2_A = 0.8544, \\ F = 50.293, Q = 2.165$$

$$(8) \text{pK}_a = 3.0863 (\pm 1.6951) J_p \\ - 0.4232 (\pm 0.3830) {}^1\chi \\ + 0.0183 (\pm 0.0129) MV \\ + 2.5679 (\pm 0.2666) I_N \\ - 32.1517 (\pm 4.3979) \eta + 54.6784 \quad (164)$$

$$N = 43, \text{Se} = 0.4527, R = 0.9267, R^2_A = 0.8396, \\ F = 49.979, Q = 2.05$$

12.2. QSAR study on benzene sulfonamide carbonic anhydrase inhibitors : Topological approach using Balaban index

Khadikar and co-workers¹³⁵ have also reported QSAR study on benzene-sulfonamide anhydrase inhibitor using Balaban index *J*. They observed that excellent model is obtained even in nonparametric regression. Furthermore, using the combination of the Balaban index (*J*) with the first-order Randic connectivity index (¹ χ) together with indicator parameters tremendous improvement in the statistics had occurred. The benzene sulfonamides inhibitors used by Khadikar and Supuran group¹⁴¹ have the general formula given in the following figure :

Fig. 8. General formula of benzene sulfonamides used.

The following models were proposed to model inhibitory activity represented by $\log K_c$:

$$(1) \log K_c = 31.4072 - 9.0189 (\pm 0.5809) J \quad (165)$$

$$N = 29, \text{Se} = 0.4287, R = -0.9541, F = 274.192, \\ Q = 2.2256$$

$$(2) \log K_c = 25.8505 - 7.6003 (\pm 0.6591) J \\ + 0.805 (\pm 0.190) I \quad (166)$$

$$N = 29, \text{Se} = 0.336, R = 0.9731, F = 232.104, Q \\ = 2.8961$$

$$(3) \log K_c = 20.3759 - 6.1371 (\pm 0.6623) J \\ + 0.194 (\pm 0.514) {}^1\chi \\ + 1.1330 (\pm 0.1775) I \quad (167)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.2736, R = 0.9829, F = 238.138, Q = 3.5925$$

$$(4) \log K_c = 18.3126 - 6.538 (\pm 0.6004) J \\ + 0.7504 (\pm 0.1999) {}^1\chi \\ - 0.0025 (\pm 8.6322 \times 10^{-4}) W \\ + 1.2837 (\pm 0.1651) I \quad (168)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.2412, R = 0.9873, F = 231.859, Q = 4.0933$$

12.3. QSAR prediction of CA I, CA II and CA IV inhibitory activity : Relative correlation potential of Balaban and Balaban type indices

Khadikar and co-workers¹³⁶ have reported relative correlation potential of Balaban and Balaban type indices in predicting CA I, CA II and CA IV inhibitory activity. In achieving their goal they have used Balaban and Balaban type indices together with other distance based and connectivity type indices. The inhibitory activity is expressed as $\log K_i$ (hCA I), $\log K_i$ (hCA II) and $\log K_i$ (hCA IV). Using multiparametric regression analysis excellent models are obtained which are given below :

12.3.1. Modeling of $\log K_i$ (hCA I)

$$(1) \log K_i \text{ (hCA I)} = 2.7557 + 2.7735 (\pm 0.3810) J \\ - 0.8116 (\pm 0.2039) J_{\text{hept}} \\ - 0.4288 (\pm 0.0399) {}^1\chi \\ - 0.6601 (\pm 0.1526) I_1 \\ - 1.4771 (\pm 0.1255) I_2 \quad (169)$$

$$N = 25, Se = 0.2259, R = 0.9876, R^2_A = 0.9688, F = 149.963$$

$$(2) \log K_i \text{ (hCA I)} = 8.5449 + 1.1639 (\pm 1.0167) J \\ - 0.9700 (\pm 0.2150) J_{\text{hept}} \\ + 0.0307 (\pm 0.0181) \text{BAC} \\ - 0.8062 (\pm 0.2258) {}^1\chi \\ - 0.6765 (\pm 0.1459) I_1 \\ - 1.7073 (\pm 0.1811) I_2 \quad (170)$$

$$N = 25, Se = 0.2155, R = 0.9893, R^2_A = 0.9716, F = 137.772$$

12.3.2. Modeling of $\log K_i$ (hCA II)

Following models were proposed for modeling $\log K_i$ (hCA II)

$$(1) \log K_i \text{ (hCA II)} = 2.4156 - 0.0076 (\pm 0.4001) J \\ + 0.3225 (\pm 0.7140) J_{\text{hept}} \\ - 0.2158 (\pm 0.0418) {}^1\chi \\ - 0.5915 (\pm 0.1602) I_1 \\ - 0.7450 (\pm 0.1318) I_2 \quad (171)$$

$$N = 25, Se = 0.2371, R = 0.9507, R^2_A = 0.8295, F = 35.710$$

(2) Deleting J from eq. (171) the following model will with better statistics was obtain

$$\log K_i \text{ (hCA II)} = 2.4059 + 0.3194 (\pm 0.1375) J_{\text{hept}} \\ - 0.2156 (\pm 0.0386) {}^1\chi \\ - 0.5202 (\pm 0.1527) I_1 \\ - 0.7458 (\pm 0.1220) I_2 \quad (172)$$

$$N = 25, Se = 0.2311, R = 0.9507, R^2_A = 0.8846, F = 46.985$$

$$(3) \log K_i \text{ (hCA II)} = 4.5967 - 0.6141 (\pm 0.1393) J \\ - 0.2628 (\pm 0.2419) J_{\text{hept}} \\ - 0.0116 (\pm 0.0205) \text{BAC} \\ - 0.3580 (\pm 0.2530) {}^1\chi \\ - 0.5257 (\pm 0.1631) I_1 \\ - 0.8318 (\pm 0.2029) I_2 \quad (173)$$

$$N = 25, R = 0.9516, R^2_A = 0.8740, F = 28.785$$

$$(4) \log K_i \text{ (hCA II)} = 2.4044 + 0.4457 (\pm 0.2719) J \\ - 0.2166 (\pm 0.0426) {}^1\chi \\ - 0.4588 (\pm 0.1599) I_1 \\ - 0.8487 (\pm 0.1599) I_2 \quad (174)$$

$$N = 25, R = 0.9446, R^2_A = 0.8708, F = 41.438$$

$$(5) \log K_i \text{ (hCA II)} = 1.9598 + 0.5910 (\pm 0.2459) J \\ - 0.2075 (\pm 0.0390) {}^1\chi \\ - 0.5107 (\pm 0.1420) I_1 \\ - 0.7643 (\pm 0.1118) I_2 \quad (175)$$

$$N = 23, Se = 0.2159, R = 0.9467, R^2_A = 0.8732, F = 38.832$$

This model is obtained by deleting two compounds as an outlier.

12.3.3. Modeling of $\log K_i$ (hCA IV)

Following models were proposed for modeling $\log K_i$ (hCA IV) :

$$(1) \log K_i \text{ (hCA IV)} = 1.6296 + 1.8992 (\pm 0.4165) J \\ - 0.5423 (\pm 0.2230) J_{\text{hept}} \\ - 0.2233 (\pm 0.0435) {}^1\chi$$

$$- 0.1295 (\pm 0.1669) I_1$$

$$- 1.2004 (\pm 0.1373) I_2 \quad (176)$$

$$N = 25, R = 0.9647, R^2_A = 0.9123, F = 50.944$$

$$(2) \log K_i (\text{hCA IV}) = 5.8510 + 0.7255 (\pm 1.1604) J$$

$$- 0.6577 (\pm 0.2463) J_{\text{hetp}}$$

$$+ 0.0224 (\pm 0.0207) \text{BAC}$$

$$- 0.4985 (\pm 0.2577) {}^1\chi$$

$$- 1.1417 (\pm 0.1655) I_1$$

$$- 1.3683 (\pm 0.2067) I_2 \quad (177)$$

$$N = 25, R = 0.9669, R^2_A = 0.9131, F = 43.035$$

12.4. QSAR studies on the inhibition of the human carbonic anhydrase cytosolic is enzyme VII : Dominating role of Balaban and Balaban type indices

Khadikar and co-workers¹³⁶ have also reported QSAR study on the prediction of CA I, CA II and CA IV inhibitory activities in developing relative correlation potential of Balaban and Balaban type indices. Good correlations and excellent results were obtained. The models proposed are given below :

$$(1) \log K_i (\text{hCA VII}) = 0.901$$

$$+ 0.827 (\pm 0.112) J_{\text{hetv}} \quad (178)$$

$$N = 32, \text{Se} = 0.445, R = 0.824, F = 63.481, Q = 1.851$$

$$(2) \log K_i (\text{hCA VII}) = 0.137$$

$$+ 1.034 (\pm 0.117) J_{\text{hetv}}$$

$$+ 0.975 (\pm 0.302) \quad (179)$$

$$N = 32, \text{Se} = 0.423, R = 0.855, R^2_A = 0.713, F = 40.754$$

$$(3) \log K_i (\text{hCA VII}) = 1.753$$

$$+ 0.550 (\pm 0.204) J_{\text{hetv}}$$

$$+ 0.335 (\pm 0.105) J_{\text{hetm}}$$

$$+ 0.855 (\pm 0.288) J_{\text{hete}}$$

$$+ 1.947 (\pm 0.942) \eta \quad (180)$$

$$N = 32, \text{Se} = 0.360, R = 0.905, R^2_A = 0.783, F = 29.038$$

13.0. Balaban and Balaban type indices in investigating CA inhibition : A case of topically acting sulfonamides incorporating GABA moieties

Khadikar and co-workers¹³⁷ have used Balaban and Balaban type indices in investigating carbonic anhydrase inhibition using sulfonamides incorporating GABA moieties. The set of compounds used being 52 of which 26

were aromatic and heterocyclic sulfonamides containing amino, emino, hydrazide or hydroxyl group, while the remaining 26 compounds were having GABA moieties. The results have shown that Balaban and Balaban type indices in multi-parametric regression were excellent. The structural and other type of indices is included in the multi-parametric models. The following models were obtained.

13.1. Modeling $\log K_i$ (hCA I)

$$\log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = 6.873 - 0.234 (\pm 0.048) {}^2\chi$$

$$+ 0.784 (\pm 0.529) J_{\text{hetE}}$$

$$- 1.876 (\pm 0.687) I$$

$$- 1.702 (\pm 0.448) d \quad (181)$$

$$N = 51, \text{Se} = 0.580, R = 0.896, R^2_A = 0.782, F = 36.822$$

13.2. Modeling $\log K_i$ (hCA II)

$$\log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = 0.409 + 1.536 (\pm 0.188) J_{\text{hetE}}$$

$$- 0.029 (\pm 4.775 \times 10^{-3}) \text{BAC}$$

$$- 1.521 (\pm 0.441) \text{IOR}$$

$$- 1.148 (\pm 0.255) d$$

$$+ 0.074 (\pm 0.019) \alpha \quad (182)$$

$$N = 53, \text{Se} = 0.297, R = 0.895, R^2_A = 0.802, F = 37.977$$

13.3. Modeling $\log K_i$ (hCA IV)

$$\log K_i (\text{hCA IV}) = 2.195 + 0.556 (\pm 0.322) J_{\text{hetE}}$$

$$+ 0.610 (\pm 0.76) J_{\text{hetv}}$$

$$- 0.290 (\pm 0.090) J_{\text{hetz}}$$

$$+ 9.956 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 2.212 \times 10^{-4}) W$$

$$- 0.0202 (\pm 1.427 \times 10^{-3}) \text{NM} \quad (183)$$

$$N = 53, \text{Se} = 0.346, R = 0.885, R^2_A = 0.760, F = 34.010$$

13.4. QSAR study on the inhibition of human carbonic anhydrase II : Combination of Balaban, Balaban type and quantum theoretical and distance-based topological indices

Khadikar and co-workers¹³⁸ had developed QSAR for the inhibition of human carbonic anhydrase II using topological indices, Balaban and Balaban type indices and their combinations with quantum theoretical descriptors. Mathematical models were developed to find QSAR that correlates chemical structure and inhibition towards human carbonic anhydrase II. A large set of 95 carbonic anhydrase inhibitors with diverse aromatic rings were used

for this purpose. After descriptor generation, multiple linear regressions were performed to find out superior models for the prediction of inhibition. The results indicated the following :

- (1) Models based on topological indices were superior to those based on quantum chemical descriptors,
- (2) Combinations of topological and quantum theoretical descriptors improve the quality of correlation, and
- (3) In both the cases involvement of Balaban and Balaban type indices was beneficial.

In support of aforementioned findings the following 12 models were proposed 145.

$$(1) \log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = 2.144 + 7.79 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 4.600 \times 10^{-4}) W - 1.5933 (\pm 0.1596) J_{\text{hetm}} + 4.4678 (\pm 0.3407) J_{\text{hete}} - 0.0117 (\pm 0.0032) \text{BAC} - 0.9062 (\pm 0.1297) {}^1\chi + 0.0012 (\pm 3.350 \times 10^{-4}) \text{Sz} \quad (184)$$

$N = 95, Se = 0.490, R = 0.913, R^2_A = 0.823, F = 73.755, Q = 1.865$

$$(2) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = 2.550 + 5.79 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 4.604 \times 10^{-4}) W - 1.819 (\pm 0.187) J_{\text{hetm}} + 4.665 (\pm 0.340) J_{\text{hete}} - 0.0113 (\pm 0.0032) \text{BAC} - 0.9077 (\pm 0.1270) {}^1\chi + 0.0013 (\pm 3.343 \times 10^{-4}) \text{Sz} - 0.3575 (\pm 0.1637) I_4 \quad (185)$$

$N = 95, Se = 0.480, R = 0.918, R^2_A = 0.830, F = 63.631, Q = 1.914$

$$(3) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = 1.292 + 1.223 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 4.148 \times 10^{-4}) W - 1.596 (\pm 0.143) J_{\text{hetm}} + 4.780 (\pm 0.310) J_{\text{hete}} - 0.015 (\pm 2.930 \times 10^{-3}) \text{BAC} - 0.901 (\pm 0.117) {}^1\chi + 1.024 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 3.016 \times 10^{-4}) \text{Sz} \quad (186)$$

$N = 91, Se = 0.435, R = 0.934, R^2_A = 0.863, F = 95.200, Q = 2.147$

This and the following models were obtained after deleting 4 compounds as outliers :

$$(4) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = 1.761 + 5.930 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 4.138 \times 10^{-4}) W - 1.951 (\pm 0.190) J_{\text{hetm}} + 5.056 (\pm 0.343) J_{\text{hete}} - 0.013 (\pm 2.920 \times 10^{-4}) \text{BAC} - 0.875 (\pm 0.117) {}^1\chi + 1.286 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 3.003 \times 10^{-4}) \text{Sz} - 0.438 (\pm 0.183) I_4 \quad (187)$$

$N = 91, Se = 0.428, R = 0.936, R^2_A = 0.866, F = 84.048, Q = 2.187$

$$(5) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = -46.958 - 1.5160 (\pm 0.2115) E_H - 25.143 (\pm 4.634) Q_0 - 13.783 (\pm 12.643) Q_N + 0.872 (\pm 0.141) I_1 - 0.469 (\pm 0.140) I_3 \quad (188)$$

$N = 95, Se = 0.554, R = 0.887, R^2_A = 0.774, F = 65.303, Q = 1.601$

$$(6) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = -41.800 - 1.306 (\pm 0.208) E_H - 32.105 (\pm 2.182) Q_0 - 0.485 (\pm 0.179) E_{SL} + 1.032 (\pm 0.160) I_1 + 0.286 (\pm 0.159) I_2 - 0.312 (\pm 0.155) I_3 \quad (189)$$

$N = 95, Se = 0.531, R = 0.897, R^2_A = 0.792, F = 60.553, Q = 1.689$

$$(7) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = -40.663 - 1.238 (\pm 0.171) E_H - 31.363 (\pm 1.823) Q_0 - 0.555 (\pm 0.148) E_{SL} + 0.991 (\pm 0.139) I_1 + 0.340 (\pm 0.129) I_2 - 0.261 (\pm 0.125) I_3 \quad (190)$$

$N = 89, Se = 0.421, R = 0.925, R^2_A = 0.845, F = 90.900, Q = 2.197$

This model was obtained by detecting 6 compounds from the regression procedure.

$$(8) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = -45.321 - 1.237 (\pm 0.0209) E_H - 34.644 (\pm 2.598) Q_0 - 0.533 (\pm 0.179) E_{SL}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - 0.167 (\pm 0.095) E_{SH} \\
 & + 1.035 (\pm 0.158) I_1 \\
 & + 0.286 (\pm 0.157) I_2 \\
 & - 0.300 (\pm 0.154) I_3 \quad (191)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 95, Se = 0.525, R = 0.901, R^2_A = 0.797, F = 53.579, Q = 1.716$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (9) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = & - 42.466 \\
 & - 1.233 (\pm 0.178) E_H \\
 & - 32.306 (\pm 2.229) Q_0 \\
 & - 0.493 (\pm 0.148) E_{SL} \\
 & - 0.124 (\pm 0.080) E_{SH} \\
 & + 0.947 (\pm 0.140) I_1 \\
 & + 0.280 (\pm 0.130) I_2 \\
 & - 0.308 (\pm 0.127) I_3 \quad (192)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 90, Se = 0.432, R = 0.921, R^2_A = 0.835, F = 68.501, Q = 2.352$$

This model is obtained by deleting 5 compounds from the regression procedure.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (10) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = & - 18.489 \\
 & + 8.873 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 3.969 \times 10^{-4}) W \\
 & - 0.824 (\pm 0.197) J_{hetm} \\
 & + 2.616 (\pm 0.428) J_{hete} \\
 & - 7.148 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 2.865 \times 10^{-5}) BAC \\
 & - 0.670 (\pm 0.135) {}^1\chi \\
 & + 6.000 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 3.046 \times 10^{-4}) Sz \\
 & - 0.650 (\pm 0.205) E_H \\
 & - 15.700 (\pm 2.692) Q_0 \\
 & + 0.217 (\pm 0.181) I \quad (193)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 95, Se = 0.416, R = 0.940, R^2_A = 0.872, F = 72.279, Q = 2.260$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (11) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = & - 20.971 + 5.617 \\
 & \times 10^{-4} (\pm 4.795 \times 10^{-4}) W \\
 & - 0.884 (\pm 0.204) J_{hetm} \\
 & + 2.786 (\pm 0.453) J_{hete} \\
 & - 6.817 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 2.876 \times 10^{-3}) BAC \\
 & - 0.622 (\pm 0.142) {}^1\chi \\
 & + 7.780 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 3.424 \times 10^{-4}) Sz \\
 & - 0.691 (\pm 0.207) E_H \\
 & - 16.610 (\pm 2.805) Q_0 \\
 & + 0.318 (\pm 0.210) I_1 \\
 & + 0.011 (\pm 9.651 \times 10^{-3}) I_2 \quad (194)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 95, Se = 0.415, R = 0.941, R^2_A = 0.873, F = 63.394, Q = 2.268$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (12) \log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = & - 22.599 + 2.947 \\
 & \times 10^{-4} (\pm 5.318 \times 10^{-4}) W \\
 & - 0.796 (\pm 0.217) J_{hetm} \\
 & + 2.916 (\pm 0.466) J_{hete} \\
 & - 0.409 (\pm 0.355) J_{hetp} \\
 & + 9.234 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 3.643 \times 10^{-4}) BAC \\
 & - 0.590 (\pm 0.144) {}^1\chi \\
 & + 9.234 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 3.643 \times 10^{-4}) Sz \\
 & - 0.775 (\pm 0.219) E_H \\
 & - 17.315 (\pm 2.866) Q_0 \\
 & + 0.413 (\pm 0.217) I_1 \\
 & + 0.013 (\pm 9.799 \times 10^{-3}) I_2 \quad (195)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$N = 95, Se = 0.415, R = 0.942, R^2_A = 0.873, F = 58.801, Q = 2.270$$

14.0. QSAR study on carbonic anhydrase using classical descriptors

Now we discuss the cases in that classical descriptors alone or in combination of other descriptors are used in proposing QSAR models for modeling carbonic anhydrase inhibition. Below we give some such models proposed for Khadikar and co-workers¹³⁹.

14.1. QSAR study on carbonic anhydrase using chemical and quantum theoretical descriptors

Khadikar and co-workers¹³⁹ have used a set of 24 descriptors consisting of quantum theoretical and chemical descriptors for modeling binding constant (log K) of the benzene sulfonamide to human CA II. Simple as well as multiple regressions had indicated that MNC (most negative charge) was the most dominating parameter to be used in modeling log K. Excellent results were obtained in multiparametric regression analysis. In performing their QSAR analysis, Khadikar and co-workers¹³⁹ had used the benzene sulfonamides of the type given below :

Fig. 9. Type of the benzene sulfonamides used for Khadikar group.

The following six QSAR models were proposed by Khadikar group¹⁴⁶ for modeling log K.

$$(1) \log K = 1114.093 - 1160.177 (\pm 236.611) \text{MNC} \quad (196)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 1.043, R = -0.686, F = 24.042$$

$$(2) \log K = 974.806 - 1012.860 (\pm 163.103) \text{MNC} \\ - 0.811 (\pm 0.430) \text{DMY} \quad (197)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.710, R = 0.874, R^2_A = 0.746, F = 42.101$$

$$(3) \log K = 1038.778 - 1075.229 (\pm 82.690) \text{MNC} \\ - 1.088 (\pm 0.079) \text{DMY} \\ + 0.577 (\pm 0.066) \text{HE} \quad (198)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.359, R = 0.971, R^2_A = 0.935, F = 135.650$$

$$(4) \log K = 975.592 - 977.601 (\pm 64.901) \text{MNC} \\ - 1.108 (\pm 0.072) \text{DMY} \\ - 2.907 (\pm 0.441) \text{SSC} \\ + 1.253 (\pm 0.108) \log P \quad (199)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.280, R = 0.983, R^2_A = 0.901, F = 171.844$$

$$(5) \log K = 962.916 - 954.732 (\pm 62.026) \text{MNC} \\ - 0.947 (\pm 0.105) \text{DMY} \\ - 2.756 (\pm 0.42) \text{SSC} \\ + 1.244 (\pm 0.101) \log P \\ - 0.903 (\pm 0.051) {}^1\chi \quad (200)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.263, R = 0.986, R^2_A = 0.965, F = 156.157$$

$$(6) \log K = 341.593 - 362.447 (\pm 126.664) \text{MNC} \\ - 0.629 (\pm 0.122) \text{DMY} \\ - 0.176 (\pm 0.057) \chi \\ - 0.259 (\pm 0.129) \eta \\ + 0.217 (\pm 0.049) \text{DMz} \\ + 0.043 (\pm 0.013) \text{Hf} \\ + 2.132 (\pm 0.380) \log P \quad (201)$$

$$N = 29, Se = 0.187, R = 0.993, R^2_A = 0.982, F = 223.468$$

14.2. QSAR study on pK_a vis-à-vis physiological activity of sulfonamides using surface tension as an inverse steric parameter

Thakur and co-workers¹⁴⁰ have proposed the use of surface tension in modeling pK_a vis-à-vis physiological activity of sulfonamides which are used as CA inhibitors.

In their study Khadikar and Supuran¹⁴¹ had used a large set of 43 sulfonamides having the general formula given below :

Fig. 10. General formula of sulfonamides used by Khadikar-Supuran group.

Khadikar and co-workers¹⁴⁰ have proposed the following seven models for modeling pK_a and thus the physiological activities of benzene sulfonamides (see above figure)

$$(1) \text{pK}_a = 15.0504 - 0.1120 (\pm 0.0207) \text{ST} \quad (202)$$

$$N = 43, Se = 0.3971, R = 0.9394, R^2_A = 0.8765, F = 150.00, Q = 2.360$$

$$(2) \text{pK}_a = 16.4519 - 0.1401 (\pm 0.0097) \text{ST} \\ + 2.6977 (\pm 0.2145) I_4 \quad (203)$$

$$N = 43, Se = 0.3971, R = 0.9394, R^2_A = 0.8765, F = 150.00, Q = 2.360$$

$$(3) \text{pK}_a = -0.3152 - 0.1546 (\pm 0.0082) \text{ST} \\ + 2.7653 (\pm 0.1706) I_N \\ + 9.4458 (\pm 1.9088) J \quad (204)$$

$$N = 43, Se = 0.3152, R = 0.9632, R^2_A = 0.9227, F = 166.926, Q = 3.06$$

$$(4) \text{pK}_a = -1.1240 - 0.1442 (\pm 0.0080) \text{ST} \\ + 2.6263 (\pm 0.1581) I_N \\ + 9.6607 (\pm 1.7063) J \\ + 0.3537 (\pm 0.1072) I_y \quad (205)$$

$$N = 43, Se = 0.2818, R = 0.9115, R^2_A = 0.9379, F = 159.634, Q = 3.06$$

$$(5) \text{pK}_a = -0.9988 - 0.12481 (\pm 0.01045) \text{ST} \\ + 2.3857 (\pm 0.1726) I_N \\ + 9.4371 (\pm 1.5879) J \\ + 0.5171 (\pm 0.1163) I_y \\ - 8.4817 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 3.2059 \times 10^{-4}) S_z \quad (206)$$

$$N = 43, Se = 0.2617, R = 0.9702, R^2_A = 0.9464, F = 149.269, Q = 3.71$$

$$(6) \text{pK}_a = -14.7461 - 0.1424 (\pm 0.0076) \text{ST} \\ + 2.8341 (\pm 0.1285) I_N \\ + 5.1420 (\pm 1.8217) J \\ + 0.0098 (\pm 0.0020) S_z \\ + 3.0909 (\pm 0.7198) {}^1\chi$$

$$+ 0.0299 (\pm 0.0051) MV \quad (207)$$

$N = 43$, $Se = 0.2140$, $R = 0.9845$, $R^2_A = 0.9641$,
 $F = 189.190$, $Q = 4.60$

$$(7) pK_a = 18.3014 - 0.1416 (\pm 0.0057) ST$$

$$+ 3.0096 (\pm 0.1097) I_N$$

$$+ 6.1887 (\pm 1.3735) J$$

$$+ 0.0103 (\pm 0.0016) Sz$$

$$+ 3.2040 (\pm 0.5583) {}^1\chi$$

$$+ 0.0316 (\pm 0.0039) MV \quad (208)$$

$N = 39$, $Se = 0.1570$, $R = 0.9919$, $R^2_A = 0.9808$,
 $F = 324.991$, $Q = 6.32$

The model is obtained by deleting four outliers.

14.3. Modeling of carbonic anhydrase inhibitory activities of sulfonamides using molecular negentropy

Agrawal and Khadikar¹⁴¹ had discussed modeling of carbonic anhydrase inhibitory activity of sulfonamides using molecular negentropy. They have modeled inhibitory activity against CA I, CA II and CA IV and proposed the following models.

(1) Modeling $\log K_i$ (hCA I)

$$\log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = -0.0516 (\pm 0.0061) N \\ + 0.2946 (\pm 0.1452) I_3 \\ - 0.8732 (\pm 0.1064) I_4 + 5.7072 \quad (209)$$

$N = 40$, $Se = 0.3339$, $R = 0.9025$, $F = 52.674$, $Q = 2.7029$

(2) Modeling $\log K_i$ (hCA II)

$$\log K_i (\text{hCA II}) = -0.0361 (\pm 0.0096) N \\ - 0.2288 (\pm 0.2776) I_1 \\ - 0.5661 (\pm 0.1122) I_4 + 3.3311 \quad (210)$$

$N = 40$, $Se = 0.3469$, $R = 0.7906$, $F = 20.696$, $Q = 2.2934$

(3) Modeling $\log K_i$ (bCA IV)

Following two models were proposed by Agrawal and Khadikar¹⁴⁸ for modeling $\log K_i$ (bCA IV) :

$$(a) \log K_i (\text{bCA IV}) = -0.0458 (\pm 0.0040) N \\ - 0.6045 (\pm 0.0878) I_4 + 3.7488 \quad (211)$$

$N = 40$, $Se = 0.2760$, $R = 0.8800$, $F = 63.493$

$$(b) \log K_i (\text{bCA IV}) = -0.0239 (\pm 0.0075) N \\ + 0.3037 (\pm 0.1773) I_1 \\ - 0.6317 (\pm 0.0870) I_4 + 3.2914 \quad (212)$$

$N = 40$, $Se = 0.2691$, $R = 0.8896$, $F = 45.518$, $Q = 5.3182$

14.4. QSAR study on CA I inhibitory activity : Dominating role of van der Waals volume repulsion energy

Khadikar and co-workers¹⁴² have reported the dominating role of van der Waals volume repulsion energy in investigating CA I inhibitory activity. They have used sulfonamides of the type mentioned below :

Fig. 11. General formula of benzene sulfonamides used.

This group has proposed the following models which establish the dominating role played by van der Waals repulsion energy (E_{vdw}) :

$$(1) \log \pi_{50} = -3.6842 \\ - 0.1738 (\pm 2.0540 \times 10^{-2}) E_{vdw} \quad (213)$$

$N = 20$, $R^2 = 0.7990$, $R^2_A = 0.7879$, $Se = 0.2999$,
 $F = 71.5736$

$$(2) \log \pi_{50} = 3.4684 \\ - 0.1624 (\pm 1.6702 \times 10^{-2}) E_{vdw} \\ + 0.4223 (\pm 0.1252) I_4 \quad (214)$$

$N = 20$, $R^2 = 0.8796$, $R^2_A = 0.8654$, $Se = 0.2389$,
 $F = 62.0995$

$$(3) \log \pi_{50} = -3.9847 \\ - 0.1408 (\pm 2.1279 \times 10^{-2}) E_{vdw} \\ + 0.3160 (\pm 0.1385) I_4 \\ + 0.1959 (\pm 0.1385) {}^2\chi \quad (215)$$

$N = 20$, $R^2 = 0.8953$, $R^2_A = 0.8757$, $Se = 0.2296$,
 $F = 45.6202$

$$(4) \log \pi_{50} = -3.3980 \\ - 0.1041 (\pm 1.953 \times 10^{-2}) E_{vdw} \\ + 0.1879 (\pm 0.1130) I_4 \\ + 0.4123 (\pm 0.1194) {}^0\chi^v \\ + 0.7163 (\pm 0.1794) {}^2\chi \quad (216)$$

$N = 20$, $R^2 = 0.9417$, $R^2_A = 0.9262$, $Se = 0.1770$,
 $F = 60.5564$

15.0. QSAR study on carbonic anhydrase inhibition using spectral parameters as molecular descriptors

We now discuss the use of parameters obtained from molecular spectroscopy as molecular descriptors for modeling carbonic anhydrase inhibition. Chiefly such parameters used being NMR chemical shifts and valency force constants from IR spectra. First we discuss the use of NMR chemical shift. In such a study Khadikar group¹⁴² is considered as the pioneer worker.

15.1. Use of NMR chemical shift

Khadikar and Supuran group¹⁴³⁻¹⁴⁵ had used chemical shifts in NMR spectroscopy as molecular parameters for modeling CA inhibitory activity. Some such cases reported by them are given below.

15.2. First report on modeling of carbonic anhydrase inhibitory activity using chemical shifts in NMR

A novel use of chemical shift of the SO₂NH₂ protons as a molecular descriptor was described by Khadikar group¹⁴³ for modeling the inhibition constant for benzene sulfonamides against CA. The type of the benzene sulfonamides used by them is mentioned below :

Fig. 12. Type of the benzene sulfonamide used.

The regression analysis of the data has shown that the NMR chemical shift was quite useful in modeling CA inhibitory activity. Following models were proposed for modeling pK_i.

$$(1) \text{pK}_i = -5.5140 + 1.7788 \delta \quad (217)$$

$$N = 19, \text{Se} = 0.6227, R = 0.6813, F = 14.7233, Q = 1.0941$$

(2) When three *ortho*-substituted benzene sulfonamides were deleted, the following improved model was obtained :

$$\text{pK}_i = -0.6805 + 2.3091 \delta \quad (218)$$

$$N = 16, \text{Se} = 0.6190, R = 0.9420, F = 110.2236, Q = 1.5198$$

15.3. Use of NMR chemical shift for modeling CA inhibitory activity of yet another type of benzene sulfonamides

Khadikar group¹⁴⁴ has used NMR chemical shift of SO₂NH₂ moiety as a molecular parameters for modeling log K_i (hCA I) using a different group of benzene sulfonamides. This set contained sulfonamides incorporating GABA moieties. The results have shown that log K_i (hCA I) can be decently estimated in multiparametric regression analysis consisting of δ (SO₂NH₂) and two indicator parameters as the correlating parameters. The following three models were proposed :

$$(1) \log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = -5.415 + 1.164 (\pm 0.490) (\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2) - 2.5054 (\pm 0.663) I_2 \quad (219)$$

$$N = 21, \text{Se} = 0.320, R = 0.666, R^2_A = 0.382, F = 7.182$$

$$(2) \log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = -1.900 + 0.715 (\pm 0.406) \delta (\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2) - 1.603 (\pm 0.460) I_1 - 2.371 (0.523) I_2 \quad (220)$$

$$N = 21, \text{Se} = 0.320, R = 0.820, R^2_A = 0.016, F = 11.703$$

The above model eq. (206) contained one compound as an outlier. The deletion of this compound from the regression analysis yielded the following model with slightly improved quality :

$$\log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = -1.359 + 0.641 (\pm 0.0321) \delta (\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2) - 1.619 (\pm 0.363) I_1 - 2.834 (\pm 0.430) I_2 \quad (221)$$

$$N = 20, \text{Se} = 0.200, R = 0.899, R^2_A = 0.770, F = 22.279$$

15.4. Using of ¹³C NMR chemical shift for modeling carbonic anhydrase inhibition

Khadikar group¹⁴⁵ had used the molecular structure and ¹³C NMR shift information of carbonic anhydrase CA I can be combined to form powerful models for modeling carbonic anhydrase inhibition. The following models were suggested the modeling log K_i (hCA I).

$$(1) \log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = -6.8342 + 2.0176 (\pm 0.2753) \delta (^{13}\text{C}) \quad (222)$$

$$N = 16, \text{Se} = 0.8906, R = 0.9128, R^2_A = 0.7784, F = 53.703$$

$$(2) \log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = - 4.1614 \\ + 1.5697 (\pm 0.1946) \delta (^{13}\text{C}) \\ + 0.6369 (\pm 0.1320) I_3 \quad (223)$$

$$N = 16, \text{Se} = 0.0315, R = 0.9627, R^2_A = 0.9145, \\ F = 81.240$$

$$(3) \log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = - 4.5320 \\ + 1.6358 (\pm 0.1957) \delta (^{13}\text{C}) \\ + 0.7374 (\pm 0.1492) I_3 \\ - 0.1584 (\pm 0.1199) I_2 \quad (224)$$

$$N = 16, \text{Se} = 0.0307, R = 0.9601, R^2_A = 0.9191, \\ F = 57.841$$

$$(4) \log K_i (\text{hCA I}) = - 4.7761 \\ + 1.6454 (\pm 0.1749) \delta (^{13}\text{C}) \\ + 0.7600 (\pm 0.1293) I_3 \\ - 0.2131 (\pm 0.0979) I_1 \quad (225)$$

$$N = 16, \text{Se} = 0.0278, R = 0.9731, R^2_A = 0.9336, \\ F = 71.333$$

15.5. Use of valence force constant for models pK_i of benzene sulfonamides

Khadikar and co-workers¹⁴⁶ have used valence force constant, $f(S=O)$ as a molecular descriptor for modeling carbonic anhydrase inhibition (pK_i) by benzene sulfonamides and proposed the following model :

$$(1) pK_i = - 11.7242 + 1.7639 (\pm 0.4039) f(S=O) \\ + 0.9702 (\pm 1.805) I_3 \quad (226)$$

$$N = 19, R^2 = 0.8036, R^2_A = 0.7791, \text{Se} = 0.0479, \\ F = 32.740$$

$$(2) pK_i = - 0.1523 - 1.3223 (\pm 0.6632) f(S=O) \\ + 2.9449 (\pm 0.5595) (^{13}\text{C}) \\ + 0.4849 (\pm 0.1602) I_1 \quad (227)$$

$$N = 19, R^2 = 0.7845, R^2_A = 0.7414, \text{Se} = 0.0538, \\ F = 18.200$$

$$(3) pK_i = - 0.2433 - 0.9296 (\pm 0.3980) f(S=O) \\ + 2.3011 (\pm 0.3635) (^{13}\text{C}) \\ + 0.6509 (\pm 0.1015) I_1 \\ + 0.5148 (\pm 0.1010) I_2 \quad (228)$$

$$N = 19, R^2 = 0.9240, R^2_A = 0.9022, \text{Se} = 0.0312, \\ F = 42.835$$

16.0. Need or otherwise of the use of hydrophobic term ($\log P$) in QSAR study of carbonic anhydrase inhibition

In a very interesting review related to chem-

bioinformatics and QSAR¹⁴⁷ Hansch argued that it seems timely to examine those instances where hydrophobic terms are not significant. To the belief of Hansch at this point in time, further advances in understanding QSAR studies related to carbonic inhibition need to be attained by comparative study. Consequently, Khadikar and co-workers¹⁴⁸ investigated carbonic anhydrase inhibition without and with hydrophobic term i.e. $\log P$. Some such reports are mentioned below.

16.1. Need of hydrophobic parameter for topological modeling of binding constants of sulfonamides to human CA II

Khadikar and co-workers¹⁴⁹ first of all modeled the binding constants of sulfonamides to human CA II by using a large set of distance-based topological indices. The need or otherwise of the hydrophobic parameter ($\log P$) for such topological modeling of $\log K$ was then examined critically by modeling $\log K$ without using $\log P$ and with using $\log P$ together with topological indices. In both the cases excellent results were obtained. In multi-parametric models containing indicator parameter also, Thakur and co-workers¹⁴⁹ observed that introduction of hydrophobic parameter ($\log P$) yielded model with much improved statistics. The models used to arrive at these conclusions are mentioned below :

(1) Modeling of $\log K$ without $\log P$

The following three models were reported by Khadikar and Mandloi¹⁵⁰ which doesn't contain $\log P$ term.

$$(a) \log K = 2.1443 + 0.4220 (\pm 0.0623) {}^0\chi^v \\ + 2.4495 (\pm 0.1959) I_1 \quad (229)$$

$$N = 29, \text{Se} = 0.5050, R = 0.9394, R^2_A = 0.8753, \\ F = 97.666, Q = 1.8751$$

$$(b) \log K = 3.5111 - 0.0255 (\pm 0.0084) W \\ + 0.0200 (\pm 0.0069) Sz \\ + 1.9486 (\pm 0.2285) I_1 \quad (230)$$

$$N = 29, \text{Se} = 0.4545, R = 0.9488, R^2_A = 0.8868, F \\ = 73.942, Q = 1.9979$$

$$(c) \log K = 1.9828 + 0.0238 (\pm 0.00813) W \\ + 0.0199 (\pm 0.0066) Sz \\ + 0.8407 (\pm 0.4450) {}^2\chi^v \\ + 1.9132 (\pm 0.2190) I_1 \quad (231)$$

$$N = 29, \text{Se} = 0.4525, R = 0.9548, R^2_A = 0.8968, \\ F = 61.885, Q = 2.110$$

(2) Modeling of log K using log P

Here also, three models were proposed by Khadikar and Mandloi¹⁴⁶ which involved log P parameter.

$$(a) \log K = 4.8219 + 0.6748 (\pm 0.0979) \log P + 2.4335 (\pm 0.1937) I_1 \quad (232)$$

N = 29, Se = 0.4955, R = 0.9408, R_A² = 0.8763, F = 100.197, Q = 1.8981

$$(b) \log K = 2.2096 + 0.4347 (\pm 0.0987) \log P + 0.4226 (\pm 0.1060) {}^2\chi + 2.5167 (\pm 0.1559) I_1 \quad (233)$$

N = 29, Se = 0.3952, R = 0.9642, R_A² = 0.9213, F = 110.2716, Q = 2.440

$$(c) \log K = 1.6434 + 0.4033 (\pm 0.0546) \log P + 0.4350 (\pm 0.0585) {}^2\chi + 2.0451 (\pm 0.1104) I_1 + 1.0549 (\pm 0.1383) I_2 \quad (234)$$

N = 29, Se = 0.2180, R = 0.9897, R_A² = 0.9761, F = 286.500, Q = 4.5400

This single study, however, is not enough to arrive at a final, valuable and acceptable conclusion. Further investigation, therefore, need to be initiated.

17.0. Conclusions**What molecular factors modulate QSAR?**

From review made above, we observed that, different physico-chemical parameters, molecular, quantum, and graph theoretical descriptors were used to correlate the activity of sulfonamide as CA inhibitors with their chemical structures. The conclusions of different papers are often contradictory, and the best approach for explaining activity this class of compounds has not yet been found. We believe that further work in this area need to be carried out using the following :

- (1) Hansch hydrophobic and related parameters
- (2) Topological (both distance- and connectivity-based) indices
- (3) Separate study on Balaban and Balaban type indices
- (4) Quantum theoretical indices
- (5) Using spectral parameters obtained from molecular spectra as molecular descriptors
- (6) Some valuable combinations of the aforementioned molecular descriptors
- (7) Shape and other type of indices

As stated in our first review⁹⁷, we still believe that a possible explanation for the contradictory results, as well as the possibility of obtaining much better correlations in future study could be the use of kinetic data rather than thermodynamic constants for describing the biological activity of these sulfonamides. This would be feasible now that an accurate method for such determination was developed by Marsen the large examples discussed above established our recommendations for obtained accurate modeling of inhibitory activity of CA inhibitors. In fact this present review fulfills and establishes all our recommendations made in our first review. Our present and exclusive review establishes the greatest contribution of QSAR study in establishing drug action of CA inhibitors. Furthermore, the combination of QSAR with molecular modeling provided clear pictures of drug-receptor interaction and the recognition of active sites at the reactor. The cases discussed above indicate that substituent occurring on aromatic or heteroaromatic nucleus play dominating role in the exhibition CA inhibitory activity. This is probably due to changes in electronic properties occurring in the sulfonamide moiety. We also conclude that in addition to the *meta*-substituent effect *ortho*-substitutions can produce abnormal *ortho*-effect. Other importance of such QSAR study is well documented in the review of Gupta⁶⁴

Appendix I. PRECLAV descriptors

- nra : Number of atoms
- nrh : Number of H atoms
- nrc : Number of C atoms
- nrn : Number of N atoms
- nro : Number of O atoms
- nrf : Number of F atoms
- nrl : Number of Cl atoms
- nrb : Number of Br atoms
- nri : Number of I atoms
- nrs : Number of S atoms
- nrp : Number of P atoms
- mas : Molecular mass
- mam : Molecular mass/Number of atoms ratio
- phi : Percent of hydrogen
- pca : Percent of carbon
- paz : Percent of nitrogen
- pox : Percent of oxygen
- pfl : Percent of fluorine

pcl : Percent of chlorine	rno : Number of NO single or weak bonds/Number of bonds ratio
pbr : Percent of bromine	rcc : Number of CC aromatic bonds/Number of bonds ratio
pio : Percent of iodine	rco : Number of CO aromatic bonds/Number of bonds ratio
psu : Percent of sulphur	rnc : Number of CN aromatic bonds/Number of bonds ratio
pfo : Percent of phosphorus	ron : Number of NO aromatic bonds/Number of bonds ratio
nlg : Number of bonds	rdc : Number of CC double bonds/Number of bonds ratio
lfp : Number of weak bonds	red : Number of CO double bonds/Number of bonds ratio
lgs : Number of single bonds	rdn : Number of CN double bonds/Number of bonds ratio
lga : Number of aromatic bonds	dnd : Number of NO double bonds/Number of bonds ratio
lgd : Number of double bonds	rct : Number of CC triple bonds/Number of bonds ratio
lgt : Number of triple bonds	rtc : Number of CN triple bonds/Number of bonds ratio
lpl : Number of weak bonds/Number of bonds ratio	mdo : Minimum distance between oxygen atoms
lsl : Number of single bonds/Number of bonds ratio	ado : Average distance between oxygen atoms
lal : Number of aromatic bonds/Number of bonds ratio	xdo : Maximum distance between oxygen atoms
ldl : Number of double bonds/Number of bonds ratio	mdn : Minimum distance between nitrogen atoms
ltl : Number of triple bonds/Number of bonds ratio	adn : Average distance between nitrogen atoms
ohs : Number of OH single or weak bonds	xdn : Maximum distance between nitrogen atoms
nhs : Number of NH single or weak bonds	mon : Minimum distance between oxygen or nitrogen atoms
shs : Number of SH single or weak bonds	aon : Average distance between oxygen or nitrogen atoms
ocs : Number of CO single or weak bonds	xon : Maximum distance between oxygen or nitrogen atoms
cns : Number of CN single or weak bonds	mxxh : Minimum distance between OH/NH functional groups
nos : Number of NO single or weak bonds	axh : Average distance between OH/NH functional groups
cca : Number of CC aromatic bonds	xxh : Maximum distance between OH/NH functional groups
coa : Number of CO aromatic bonds	cic : Cyclomatic number
cna : Number of CN aromatic bonds	cyt : Atoms number weighted cyclomatic number
noa : Number of NO aromatic bonds	nlh : Number of bonds (heavy atoms)
ccd : Number of CC double bonds	lth : Number of aromatic bonds/Number of bonds ratio (heavy atoms)
cod : Number of CO double bonds	vol : Molecular volume
cnd : Number of CN double bonds	dns : Molecular mass/Molecular volume ratio
nod : Number of NO double bonds	vlm : Molecular volume/Molecular mass ratio
cct : Number of CC triple bonds	vlh : Molecular volume/Number of atoms ratio
cnt : Number of CN triple bonds	sup : Area of molecular surface
roh : Number of OH single or weak bonds/Number of bonds ratio	spm : Area of molecular surface/Molecular mass ratio
rnh : Number of NH single or weak bonds/Number of bonds ratio	sun : Molecular surface/Number of atoms ratio
rsh : Number of SH single or weak bonds/Number of bonds ratio	vsp : Volume/surface area ratio
roc : Number of CO single or weak bonds/Number of bonds ratio	vlp : Volume of circumscribed parallelepiped
rcn : Number of CN single or weak bonds/Number of bonds ratio	vle : Volume of circumscribed ellipsoid
	vls : Volume of circumscribed sphere
	spe : Area of circumscribed ellipsoid

ifu : Symmetry index	iid : Shannon index of topologic distances
isv : Shannon information index (for atomic volumes)	iis : Shannon index of sum of topologic distances
xdg : Maximum distance to geometric center	xst : Maximum net charge (all atoms)
adg : Average distance to geometric center	nst : Minimum net charge (all atoms)
rms : RMS of distances to geometric center	xsh : Maximum net charge of H atoms
cdg : rms/adg ratio (as percent - see descript.txt)	ash : Average net charge of H atoms
ift : Roughness index	nsh : Minimum net charge of H atoms
ifd : Spherical shape index	xsc : Maximum net charge of C atoms
moa : Moment of inertia A	asr : Average net charge of C atoms
mob : Moment of inertia B	nsc : Minimum net charge of C atoms
moc : Moment of inertia C	xsn : Maximum net charge of N atoms
igu : Gravitation index (all atoms)	asn : Average net charge of N atoms
igd : Gravitation index (bonded atoms)	nsh : Minimum net charge of N atoms
mou : Gyration radius X of molecular mass	xso : Maximum net charge of O atoms
moe : Gyration radius Y of molecular mass	aso : Average net charge of O atoms
mot : Gyration radius Z of molecular mass	nso : Minimum net charge of O atoms
rax : Gyration radius X of molecular area	xf : Maximum net charge of F atoms
ray : Gyration radius Y of molecular area	asf : Average net charge of F atoms
raz : Gyration radius Z of molecular area	nsf : Minimum net charge of F atoms
pon : RMS of distances to geometric center (H and halogen atoms)	xsl : Maximum net charge of Cl atoms
pax : cdg descriptor (see descript.txt) for H and halogen atoms	asl : Average net charge of Cl atoms
ran : Randic topologic index	nsl : Minimum net charge of Cl atoms
rag : Randic topologic index/Heavy atoms number ratio	xsb : Maximum net charge of Br atoms
bal : Balaban topologic index	asb : Average net charge of Br atoms
bag : Balaban topologic index/Heavy atoms number ratio	nsb : Minimum net charge of Br atoms
pla : Platt topologic index	xsi : Maximum net charge of I atoms
plg : Platt topologic index/Heavy atoms number ratio	asi : Average net charge of I atoms
zag : Zagreb topologic index	nsi : Minimum net charge of I atoms
zgg : Zagreb topologic index/Heavy atoms number ratio	xss : Maximum net charge of S atoms
khd : Kier-Hall (order 2) topologic index	ass : Average net charge of S atoms
khg : Kier-Hall (order 2) topologic index/Heavy atoms number ratio	nss : Minimum net charge of S atoms
wie : Wiener topologic index	xsp : Maximum net charge of P atoms
wig : Wiener topologic index/Heavy atoms number ratio	asp : Average net charge of P atoms
har : Harary topologic index	nsp : Minimum net charge of P atoms
hag : Harary topologic index/Heavy atoms number ratio	nfc : Minimum force in CH bonds
ijh : Jh (Ivanciuc) topologic index	afc : Average force in CH bonds
ijg : Jh (Ivanciuc) topologic index/Heavy atoms number ratio	xfc : Maximum force in CH bonds
hyw : Hyper-Wiener topologic index	nfo : Minimum force in OH bonds
hyg : Hyper-Wiener topologic index/Heavy atoms number ratio	afo : Average force in OH bonds
	xfo : Maximum force in OH bonds
	nfn : Minimum force in NH bonds

afn : Average force in NH bonds
 xfn : Maximum force in NH bonds
 nfs : Minimum force in SH bonds
 afs : Average force in SH bonds
 xfs : Maximum force in SH bonds
 nff : Minimum force in CF bonds
 aff : Average force in CF bonds
 xff : Maximum force in CF bonds
 nfl : Minimum force in CCl bonds
 afl : Average force in CCl bonds
 xfl : Maximum force in CCl bonds
 nfb : Minimum force in CBr bonds
 afb : Average force in CBr bonds
 xfb : Maximum force in CBr bonds
 nfi : Minimum force in CI bonds
 afi : Average force in CI bonds
 xfi : Maximum force in CI bonds
 hix : Percent of hydrogen * Maximum charge for H atoms
 hia : Percent of hydrogen * Average charge for H atoms
 hin : Percent of hydrogen * Minimum charge for H atoms
 cax : Percent of carbon * Maximum charge for C atoms
 caa : Percent of carbon * Average charge for C atoms
 can : Percent of carbon * Minimum charge for C atoms
 azx : Percent of nitrogen * Maximum charge for N atoms
 aza : Percent of nitrogen * Average charge for N atoms
 azn : Percent of nitrogen * Minimum charge for N atoms
 oxx : Percent of oxygen * Maximum charge for O atoms
 oxa : Percent of oxygen * Average charge for O atoms
 oxn : Percent of oxygen * Minimum charge for O atoms
 flx : Percent of fluorine * Maximum charge for F atoms
 fla : Percent of fluorine * Average charge for F atoms
 fln : Percent of fluorine * Minimum charge for F atoms
 clx : Percent of chlorine * Maximum charge for Cl atoms
 cla : Percent of chlorine * Average charge for Cl atoms
 cln : Percent of chlorine * Minimum charge for Cl atoms
 brx : Percent of bromine * Maximum charge for Br atoms
 bra : Percent of bromine * Average charge for Br atoms
 brn : Percent of bromine * Minimum charge for Br atoms
 iox : Percent of iodine * Maximum charge for I atoms
 ioa : Percent of iodine * Average charge for I atoms
 ion : Percent of iodine * Minimum charge for I atoms
 sux : Percent of sulphur * Maximum charge for S atoms
 sua : Percent of sulphur * Average charge for S atoms
 snu : Percent of sulphur * Minimum charge for S atoms
 fox : Percent of phosphorus * Maximum charge for P atoms
 foa : Percent of phosphorus * Average charge for P atoms
 fon : Percent of phosphorus * Minimum charge for P atoms
 acs : Absolute net charge sum
 aac : Absolute net charge sum/Atoms number ratio
 ssu : 0.001 * Absolute charge sum * Molecular surface product
 sss : Absolute net charge sum/Molecular surface ratio
 miu : Dipole moment
 mix : Dipole moment (X component)
 miy : Dipole moment (Y component)
 miz : Dipole moment (Z component)
 miv : Volume weighted dipole moment
 mxv : Volume weighted dipole moment (X component)
 myv : Volume weighted dipole moment (Y component)
 mzv : Volume weighted dipole moment (Z component)
 mpv : Volume weighted square of dipole moment
 xpv : Volume weighted square of dipole moment (X component)
 ypv : Volume weighted square of dipole moment (Y component)
 zpv : Volume weighted square of dipole moment (Z component)
 dfs : Molecular polarity
 prm : Polarity parameter
 teu : Topologic electronic index (all atoms)
 ted : Topologic electronic index (bonded atoms)
 poz : Area of positive charged surface
 neu : Area of neutral surface
 neg : Area of negative charged surface
 dis : Positive area - negative area gap
 dip : dis/Molecular surface area ratio (see descript.txt)
 pzs : Area of positive charged surface/Molecular surface area ratio
 nus : Area of neutral surface/Molecular surface ratio
 ngs : Area of negative charged surface/Molecular surface ratio
 ehp : Sum of net charge * Exposed atomic surface products (charge > 0)
 ehz : Sum of net charge * Exposed atomic surface products

(weak charge)	dhb : Heat of formation/Bond number ratio
chn : Sum of net charge * Exposed atomic surface products (charge < 0)	feh : $1 - E_{\text{HOMO}}$ gap
cht : Sum of net charge * Exposed atomic surface products (all atoms)	fel : $10 + E_{\text{LUMO}}$ sum
chp : ehp (see descript.txt)/Molecular surface area ratio	lup : $E_{\text{LUMO}+1}$ energy
chs : chn (see descript.txt)/Molecular surface area ratio	hom : $E_{\text{HOMO}-1}$ energy
cht : eht (see descript.txt)/Molecular surface area ratio	lha : $E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$ gap
chs : ehz/cht ratio (see descript.txt)	lhb : $E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}-1}$ gap
dif : ehp-ehn gap (see descript.txt)	lhc : $E_{\text{LUMO}+1} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$ gap
rap : dif/cht ratio (see descript.txt)	lhd : $E_{\text{LUMO}+1} - E_{\text{HOMO}-1}$ gap
prp : $0.001 * \text{sup} * \text{poz}$ product (see descript.txt)	lhe : $1/E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$ ratio
prz : $0.001 * \text{sup} * \text{neu}$ product (see descript.txt)	lhf : $1/E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}-1}$ ratio
prn : $0.001 * \text{sup} * \text{neg}$ product (see descript.txt)	lhg : $1/E_{\text{LUMO}+1} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$ ratio
ppp : $0.01 * \text{eht} * \text{ehp}$ product (see descript.txt)	lhh : $1/E_{\text{LUMO}+1} - E_{\text{HOMO}-1}$ ratio
ppz : $0.01 * \text{eht} * \text{ehz}$ product (see descript.txt)	veh : HOMO energy weighted molecular volume
ppn : $0.01 * \text{eht} * \text{ehn}$ product (see descript.txt)	vel : LUMO-HOMO gap weighted molecular volume
sol : Bond order sum	qom : QSPR of molecular orbital energies
olm : Average bond order (all bonds)	niv : Number of double occupied molecular orbitals
olb : Average bond order (heavy atoms)	xbo : Molecular orbital maximum bonding contribution
pte : Average bond order * Average absolute net charge prod- uct	xab : Molecular orbital maximum antibonding contribution
ban : Minimum aromaticity of aromatic chemical bonds	xvh : Maximum free valence of H atoms
baa : Average aromaticity of aromatic chemical bonds	nvh : Minimum free valence of H atoms
bax : Maximum aromaticity of aromatic chemical bonds	xvc : Maximum free valence of C atoms
fle : Flexibility index no.1	nvc : Minimum free valence of C atoms
irg : Rigidity (hardness) index no.1	xvn : Maximum free valence of N atoms
fli : Flexibility index no.2	nvn : Minimum free valence of N atoms
iri : Rigidity (hardness) index no.2	xvo : Maximum free valence of O atoms
nof : Number of fragments	nvo : Minimum free valence of O atoms
amg : Average mass of fragments	xvf : Maximum free valence of F atoms
xmg : Maximum mass of fragments	nvf : Minimum free valence of F atoms
qgf : QSPR of mass fragment percents	xvl : Maximum free valence of Cl atoms
war : Approximate wavelength of absorbed radiation	nv1 : Minimum free valence of Cl atoms
mdf : variation coefficient of mass fragments	xvb : Maximum free valence of Br atoms
cdf : variation coefficient of charge module sum of fragments	nvb : Minimum free valence of Br atoms
fvu : fle * vol product (see descript.txt)	xvi : Maximum free valence of I atoms
fvd : fli * vol product (see descript.txt)	nvi : Minimum free valence of I atoms
dhf : Heat of formation	xvs : Maximum free valence of S atoms
dhm : Heat of formation/Molecular mass ratio	nvs : Minimum free valence of S atoms
dhn : Heat of formation/Atoms number ratio	xvp : Maximum free valence of P atoms
	nvp : Minimum free valence of P atoms
	avh : Average free valence of H atoms
	avc : Average free valence of C atoms

avn : Average free valence of N atoms	ten : Total energy/1000
avo : Average free valence of O atoms	teb : Bonds number weighted total energy
avf : Average free valence of F atoms	een : Electronic energy/1000
avl : Average free valence of Cl atoms	eeb : Bonds number weighted electronic energy
avb : Average free valence of Br atoms	ccn : Core-core energy/1000
avi : Average free valence of I atoms	ccb : Bonds number weighted core-core energy
avs : Average free valence of S atoms	hba : Capability to form hydrogen bonds (function no. 1)
avp : Average free valence of P atoms	hbb : $100 * (hba + 1)/mas$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
xec : $100 * \text{Max. atomic electrophilic reaction index for C atoms}$	hbc : $100 * (hba + 1)/vol$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
xnc : $100 * \text{Max. atomic nucleophilic reaction index for C atoms}$	hbd : $100 * (hba + 1)/sup$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
xrc : $100 * \text{Max. atomic one-electron reaction index for C atoms}$	hbe : $mas * (hba + 1)/100$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
xen : $100 * \text{Max. atomic electrophilic reaction index for N atoms}$	hbf : $vol * (hba + 1)/100$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
xnn : $100 * \text{Max. atomic nucleophilic reaction index for N atoms}$	hbg : $sup * (hba + 1)/100$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
xrn : $100 * \text{Max. atomic one-electron reaction index for N atoms}$	hbh : Capability to form hydrogen bonds (function no. 2)
xeo : $100 * \text{Max. atomic electrophilic reaction index for O atoms}$	hbi : $100 * (hbh + 1)/mas$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
xno : $100 * \text{Max. atomic nucleophilic reaction index for O atoms}$	hbj : $100 * (hbh + 1)/vol$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
xro : $100 * \text{Max. atomic one-electron reaction index for O atoms}$	hbk : $100 * (hbh + 1)/sup$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
aec : $100 * \text{Average atomic electrophilic reaction index for C atoms}$	hbl : $mas * (hbh + 1)/100$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
anc : $100 * \text{Average atomic nucleophilic reaction index for C atoms}$	hbm : $vol * (hbh + 1)/100$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
arc : $100 * \text{Average atomic one-electron reaction index for C atoms}$	hbn : $sup * (hbh + 1)/100$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
aen : $100 * \text{Average atomic electrophilic reaction index for N atoms}$	hbo : Capability to form hydrogen bonds (function no. 3)
ann : $100 * \text{Average atomic nucleophilic reaction index for N atoms}$	hbp : $100 * (hbo + 1)/mas$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
arn : $100 * \text{Average atomic one-electron reaction index for N atoms}$	hbq : $100 * (hbo + 1)/vol$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
aeo : $100 * \text{Average atomic electrophilic reaction index for O atoms}$	hbr : $100 * (hbo + 1)/sup$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
ano : $100 * \text{Average atomic nucleophilic reaction index for O atoms}$	hbs : $mas * (hbo + 1)/100$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
aro : $100 * \text{Average atomic one-electron reaction index for O atoms}$	hbt : $vol * (hbo + 1)/100$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
	hbu : $sup * (hbo + 1)/100$ function (see <i>descript.txt</i>)
	xxx : unallowed descriptor
	udu : user descriptor no. 1
	udd : user descriptor no. 2
	udt : user descriptor no. 3
	udp : user descriptor no. 4
	udc : user descriptor no. 5
	uds : user descriptor no. 6
	uda : user descriptor no. 7
	udo : user descriptor no. 8
	udn : user descriptor no. 9
	udz : user descriptor no. 10
	Grid descriptors
	M(n) Average chemical bonds parallax for probe atom n
	P(n) Maximum chemical bonds parallax for probe atom n

A(n) Attraction force sum on probe atom n

R(n) Rejection force sum on probe atom n

F(n) Resultant electrostatic force on probe atom n

With this much knowledge of QSAR approaches we now discuss the QSAR of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors (CAI) and will give priority to the applications of PRECLAV program in modeling carbonic anhydrase inhibition as well as activation.

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